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Executive Summary

Technologies for landfill leachate (LL) treatment for per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) removal and degradation are of high importance for the European Green Deal zero pollution ambition and for a toxic-free environment. The complex composition of LL creates an environmental challenge, especially with its high concentrations of organic pollutants, heavy metals, and contaminant of emerging concern like PFAS. The aim of this deliverable is to present the developed and investigated innovative treatment processes as part of the PROMISCES project for decreasing the concentration of PFAS and toxicity assessment from LL, their performance and comparative analyses. Various treatment options were tested at laboratory and pilot scales including membrane filtration technologies, thermochemical treatment (pyrolysis), plasma treatment.

A conventional landfill leachate treatment plant (LLTP) in the Marche Region of Italy was selected as the location for installing membrane filtration technologies (nanofiltration (NF) / reverse osmosis (RO)) at pilot scale. The LLTP effluent of the plant after ultrafiltration was used as the influent for the pilot plant. The NF/RO pilot was operated in continuous mode and monitoring parameters were collected online using several installed sensors, which was supplemented by weekly sampling campaigns. The collected samples were analysed for conventional parameters and PFAS. The NF/RO concentrate produced by the pilot plant was then evaporated and collected as salts to be treated later in a pyrolysis reactor together with LLTP sludge.

A thermochemical treatment reactor was built and installed in one of UNIVPM laboratories, and to close the loop of LL treatment, sludge produced from the LLTP was collected and dried before being introduced to the pyrolysis reactor along with the dried concentrate salts at different percentages. Several control parameters were addressed during the experiments, with temperature and residence time playing a particular role. All 3 products of pyrolysis (biochar, bio-oil, and syngas) were then analysed for PFAS contamination.

Pilot scale study to evaluate PFAS removal by membrane filtration technologies showed that no PFAS were detected in any RO permeate sample with a LOQ of 20 ng/L, whereas NF permeate contained on average 635 ng/L PFBS and 6 other PFAS with average concentrations between 20 and 133 ng/L. Concentrate contained higher load of PFAS compared to sludge coming from biological treatment. Hence, when concentrate was mixed with the sludge during pyrolysis process, complete removal of PFAS from biochar was observed only at the highest tested temperature of 600 °C

Various laboratory scale non-thermal plasma systems operating at atmospheric pressure were developed and applied for the treatment of landfill leachate and model solutions with different PFAS substances and concentrations at UNISOFIA. The plasma systems tested include the DBD (dielectric barrier discharge) with liquid electrode, the underwater diaphragm discharge, the MW (microwave) plasma torch (in continuous flow and batch modes), the Surfaguide plasma source and specially designed at UNISOFIA lab Beta plasma device (in continuous flow and batch modes). The plasma characteristics of different plasma sources can vary widely, leading to very different results in PFAS degradation. To test for plasma replication and upscaling potential, LL samples from the Rastatt landfill (Stuttgart, Germany) were treated by Fraunhofer IGB using a laboratory scale pilot reactor.

A new method for assessment of impaired biological activity and toxicity based on fluorescent staining and digital image analyses was developed and applied for detection of complex toxicity of leachate and assessment of impaired biological activity of sludge/membrane concentrates during

landfill leachate treatment. Based on the created method for assessing the toxicity of landfill leachates, mathematical relationships between toxicity and PFOA concentration as a model PFAS representative have been derived.

All results obtained in plasma treatment experiments demonstrate that plasma treatment is a potential method for PFAS degradation. When the plasma is produced in Argon as a working gas the PFAS degradation is much higher than for plasma produced in the air (DBD device) or directly in the water (underwater discharge). All plasma devices operating in Argon (MW plasma torch, Surfaguide and Beta device) show high effectiveness in long-chain PFAS compounds degradation. However, only one plasma device (Beta) displayed similar degradation amounts of short-chain PFAS as for long-chain PFAS, even though not complete removal was achieved.

The results obtained and analysed with the fluorescence method show that treatment with various plasma sources reduces the toxicity of the leachate, and the leachate spiked with PFAS depends on both the concentration of PFAS, the type of plasma device and the treatment regimes. However, in the 5L batch plasma replication experiments, PFAS CALUX showed higher activity and therefore higher toxicity in the treated LL than before plasma treatment. The current knowledge of the processes during plasma treatment is still limited and further investigations are needed in order to find correlations and explanations of the effects observed.

Assessment of performance (life cycle assessment - LCA, life cycle costing - LCC) and comparative analyses of removal of PFAS was also conducted and presented. An LCA was conducted to evaluate and compare the environmental impacts of treatment options applied (NF and RO systems, pyrolysis, plasma systems). Overall, pyrolysis resulted to be more energy efficient than incineration with a higher production of thermal energy, which can be obtained by combustion of syngas and bio-oil, and a lower consumption of electrical energy. Systems using NF had lower electrical energy consumption than systems using RO. This fact is related to the lower production of concentrate that needs to be evaporated and to the lower electrical energy consumption of NF membranes compared to RO membranes. However, it has to be highlighted that those life cycle studies were accomplished using Italian energy site-specific data, which may be different from other countries in Europe. In addition, the applied health impacts of PFAS abatement might be underestimated due to the substantial knowledge gaps.

On the other side, results obtained in the Bulgarian case study indicate that plasma technologies may be useful, especially after pretreatment to reduce flux and increase concentration. Further research and additional analysis are needed to gain a deeper understanding of two key areas: first, the optimal concentration and flux before plasma reactors; and second, the most economically, technically and environmentally feasible pretreatment technologies to concentrate the fluxes.

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List of Abbreviations

AOF	Adsorbable organic fluorine
Ar	Argon
ATP	Adenosine triphosphate
BEQ	Bioanalytical equivalent
COD	Chemical oxygen demand
DBD	Dielectric barrier discharge
DOC	Dissolved organic carbon
DW	Drinking water
EBT	Effect-based trigger values
EPA	Environmental Protection Agency
GC-MS	Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry
H ₂	Hydrogen
HRGC	High-Resolution Gas Chromatograph
ICAL	Internal Calibration
IBT	Installation for biological treatment
ICP-MS	Inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry
ICP-OES	Inductively Coupled Plasma – Optical Emission Spectroscopy
IN	Incineration
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
LCC	Life Cycle Costing
LCI	Life Cycle Inventory
LCIA	Life Cycle Impact Assessment
LL	Landfill leachate
LLTP	Landfill Leachate Treatment Plant
LOD	Limit of detection
LOQ	Limits Of Quantification
LOQ	Limit of quantification
LRMS	Low-Resolution Mass Spectrometer
MSD	Mass Spectral Detector
NF	NanoFiltration
NPV	Net Present Value
O ₂	Oxygen
PB	Procedure blank
PCDD	Polychlorinated dibenzodioxin
PCDF	Polychlorinated dibenzofuran
PFAS	Per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances
PY	Pyrolysis
QA/ QC	Quality Assurance/ Quality Control
RO	Reverse Osmosis
RONS	Reactive oxygen and nitrogen species
ROS	Reactive oxygen species
SEM	Scanning Electron Microscopy
SIM	Selected Ion Monitoring
SW	Surface water
TDS	Total Dissolved Solids
TOC	Total organic carbon

TOP	Total oxidizable precursor
TS	Total Solids
TTR	Transporter protein transthyretin
TVS	Total Volatile Solids
UPLC-MS	Ultra-Performance Liquid Chromatography - Mass Spectrometry
VOC	Volatile Organic Compound
WHO	World Health Organization
WWTP	Wastewater Treatment Plant

1 Introduction

The goal of the investigations presented here was to apply innovative treatment processes for decreasing the concentration of PFAS and toxicity reduction in waste streams from landfill leachate treatment plants (LLTP). The technologies tested included reverse osmosis (RO) and nanofiltration (NF) for the treatment of landfill leachate, pyrolysis for the treatment of sludge and dry concentrate, and plasma for the treatment of landfill leachate. Model solutions containing PFAS were investigated and the degree of PFAS concentration decrease was obtained. New methods for toxicity evaluation were developed and presented here. Assessment of performance (Life Cycle Assessment - LCA, Life Cycle Costing - LCC analysis) and comparative analyses of removal of PFAS were also conducted and presented.

1.1 Overview

1.1.1 Italian Study Site

Overview of the study site

The goal of the research was to develop and investigate an innovative approach to treat landfill leachate (LL) which would be able to obtain a near zero PFAS discharge and safe resource recovery.

The research activities were done on two phases:

- First phase of an advanced filtration pilot plant featuring Nanofiltration (NF) and Reverse Osmosis (RO) at the effluent of landfill leachate treatment plant (LLTP), followed by an evaporator to transform NF/RO concentrate into dry salts for further processing.
- Second phase of Thermochemical Treatment experiments at one of UNIVPM’s laboratories, where pyrolysis was applied to both LLTP sludge and NF/RO dry concentrate.

The LLTP studied is located in the Marche Region, Italy, and it treats non-hazardous liquid wastes such as LL, sewage sludge from septic tanks, and waste derived from sewer cleaning (Figure 1). The leachate represents around 46% of the total non-hazardous liquid wastes treated by the plant. The effluent from the LLTP is mixed with the influent of the municipal wastewater treatment plant (WWTP). Thus, the LLTP can be considered as “plant in a plant” (Figure 2). However, installing the NF/RO pilot plant enabled the direct use of the LLTP effluent as the influent of NF/RO pilot plant, isolating it for targeted treatment and research.

Figure 1: Process overview of the March region LLTP

Figure 2: Marche region LLTP satellite image

Research Context and Relevance

The complex composition of LL creates an environmental challenge, especially with its high concentrations of organic pollutants, heavy metals, and emerging contaminants like per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS). In the Marche Region of Italy, LLTP treated effluent is typically combined with municipal wastewater for further treatment, adding PFAS and other contaminants into the WWTP which eventually end up in the adjacent water bodies, as was discussed in Lancioni et al. (2024). So, there is an urgent need for innovative treatment technologies that can effectively remove and treat these contaminants.

The research aimed to treat PFAS using an integrated approach of:

1. Nanofiltration/Reverse Osmosis (NF/RO): This method effectively concentrates PFAS from LL, making sure they do not reach the steps downstream.
2. Thermochemical Treatment (Pyrolysis): Pyrolysis is a thermal destruction of PFAS concentrated using NF/RO pilot, and the ones found in LLTP sludge, to achieve complete mineralization of these compounds.

By combining NF/RO with pyrolysis, a circular economy approach where NF/RO concentrate and LLTP sludge are transformed into value-added products like biochar, bio-oil, and syngas while achieving PFAS destruction, is explored.

A Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) was also conducted to evaluate and compare the environmental impacts of treating LLTP effluent using NF and RO systems, combined with either incineration or pyrolysis for the treatment of salts from the concentrates.

1.1.2. Bulgarian Case Study – Sofia Solid Waste Treatment Plant

The municipal enterprise “Sofia Waste Treatment Plant” is a specialised division of the Sofia Municipality, established to provide local activities and services related to receiving and processing solid municipal waste, recovering recyclable materials, producing fractions of modified solid recovered fuel (RDF-fuel), processing and treating separately collected biowaste to produce biogas, and processing and treating separately collected green waste to produce compost.

The structure of the integrated system of municipal waste treatment facilities of Sofia Municipality includes multiple parts. A plant for mechanical-biological treatment of solid municipal waste which produces RDF-fuel, a landfill for non-hazardous waste, and a WWTP (WWTP 1) located at the "Sadinata" site. WWTP 1 treats water from the non-hazardous waste landfill and the installation for biological treatment “Khan Bogrov” – installation for biogas producing and installation for biological treatment/IBT of green waste. WWTP 2 treats wastewater from the mechanical and biological treatment of municipal waste with production of RDF-fuel. At the "Khan Bogrov" site, a facility for biological treatment of separately collected green and bio-waste is installed.

The Sofia waste treatment plant has a total capacity of 3,234,000 tonnes and can handle up to 450 tonnes per day of waste in solid aggregate form, including separated collected fractions from commercial, industrial, and administrative activities. Sofia landfill facilities treat waste from about 24% of the country's population using a conventional treatment scheme (mechanical and biological stage). The solid waste enters the receiving bunker first (Figure 3).

Figure 3: The site of the Sofia landfill and municipal enterprise “Sofia Waste Treatment Plant”

The solid waste suitable for recycling and RDF are separated, and the remaining fraction is then sent to the landfill cell (Figure 4).

Figure 4: Solid wastes and wastewater flow at Sofia solid waste collection and treatment plant

Figure 5 and Figure 6 depict the two WWTPs available at the site. WWTP1 treats the LL and water from IBT, while WWTP2 treats the leachate from the receiving bunker and mainly condensate generated during the production of RDF.

Figure 5: Technological scheme of the “Sadinata” WWTP. The facilities are presented in the following sequence: 1- Distribution crane shaft; 2- Building with coarse grates; 2,3,4- Balancing tanks for leachate from the landfill, MBT plant, IBT “Khan Bogrov”; 6- Sc

Figure 6: Technical scheme for treating wastewater from mechanical and biological drying for the purpose of obtaining RDF fuel: 1/tank-averager with two compartments; 2/pre-denitrifier; 3/nitrifier; 4/ Post-denitrifier; 5/membrane bioreactor

Figure 7: Reservoir – mechanical and biological treatment

Figure 8: Reservoir–depot treatment and IBT "Khan Bogrov" treatment

The average values of sampling locations used for experiments are shown in Table 1. The exact values of the filtrate samples and the sample before the membrane filters are shown in the results. The plasma source treatment samples were taken from WWTP1 before the coarse screens, and from WWTP2 before the membrane ultrafiltration.

Table 1: Average values of the indicators in the three reservoirs

Indicator	Reservoir "Depot"	Reservoir "MBT"	Reservoir "Khan Bogrov"
COD [mgO₂/L]	2 920	300,0	15 000
BOD₅ [mgO₂/L]	700	48	2 800
SS [mg/L]	1 300	30	7 000
N-NH₄ [mg/L]	1 600	5.5	1 900
P-PO₄ [mg/L]	30.0	4.90	49.0
Q_m.(charging) [m³]	13.0	3	7.6

1.2 Objectives of research activities

1.2.1 Italian Study Site

The goals were the following:

1. Evaluate PFAS Removal Efficiency of NF/RO: assess the performance of the NF/RO pilot plant in the removal of PFAS. Finding the optimal operational parameters for achieving high removal rates and minimizing environmental impacts.
2. Investigate PFAS pathways and fate in the Thermochemical Treatment: assess the effectiveness of pyrolysis in degrading PFAS from the complex matrices (LLTP sludge and NF/RO dry concentrate) by checking the final products of pyrolysis, including biochar, bio-oil, and syngas, for any residual PFAS content.
3. Conduct an LCA of the Integrated System: Evaluating the environmental impacts of the NF/RO and pyrolysis processes, comparing it with different scenarios. And identifying areas for improvement to enhance sustainability.
4. Evaluate the Economic Feasibility and Scalability of the Treatment Approach: performing a Life Cycle Costing (LCC) analysis to estimate the economic convenience to treat LL by NF or RO filtration.

1.2.2. Bulgarian Study Site

The goals were the following:

1. To develop and test different plasma systems (Surfatron Microwave plasma torch, Beta device, Surfaguide plasma source and Pin-jets) for landfill leachate and model solutions treatment and to evaluate the degree of PFAS degradation and toxicity reduction.
2. To optimise the operational condition of the plasma systems (input power, treatment duration, initial PFAS concentration) and treatment modes (batch and continuous flow).
3. To establish, adapt, and apply new methods based on fluorescent staining coupled with the activity of the bacterial enzymes for detection of toxicity of PFAS and other hazardous compounds on biological treatment of LL.

4. To apply the created methods for assessing the reduction of the toxicity of the leachate and leachate enriched with PFAS and PFAS solutions.
5. To apply the created methods in technological solutions after treatment with cold plasma to reduce the amount and complex toxicity of PFAS and leachates and sludges containing PFAS.

2 Methodology

2.1 RO/NF membranes pilot plant

The pilot plant was designed and installed at the LLTP of Jesi, in the Marche Region (Italy), with the goal of evaluating the effectiveness of both advanced membrane filtration systems in removing PFAS from LLTP effluent. NF and RO were tested as alternative technologies.

A simplified block flow diagram of the pilot is presented in Figure 9 showing the general configuration of the NF/RO pilot, which is modifiable based on the experiment needs.

The pilot plant consists of two containers (Figure 10), almost identical, one for NF and the other for RO able to treat up to 2 m³/h, and each one of them contains:

- A pretreatment unit:
 - Cartridge filters for suspended solids removal
 - Antiscalant Chemical dosing pump to prevent scaling.
- A high Pressure pump to provide enough pressure for each of the two systems.
- A membrane filtration system equipped with either NF or RO membrane module.
- A Monitoring and Control System which includes flow meters, pressure meters, pH, conductivity, and temperature with an online monitoring of all these key parameters.

In addition to all these components, the pilot plant also has a control for pH before entering the system and at the final concentration tank. The concentrate produced in the system is then moved to an evaporator to be treated to recover dry salts, which are subsequently used as a catalyst for thermochemical treatment in the pyrolysis reactor. In this way clean water can be recovered and waste generation is minimized.

Figure 9: Simplified Block flow diagram (BFD) of the NF/RO pilot plant

It is worth mentioning that pressure ranges were adjusted in both systems to balance the permeate flow with the possibility of enhancing membrane fouling. As presented in Figure 9, there is the possibility of doing an internal recycle in each of the systems to maximise permeate production and decrease the amount of waste (concentrate) generated. Running and normal washing cycles (with permeate water) were optimised automatically to keep the system running smoothly. On the other hand, chemical washing was done once the differential pressure reached a set point proving high fouling of the system. These cleaning protocols were put in place to keep system efficiency and extend membrane lifespan.

Figure 10: NF and RO Pilot Plant Containers

Sampling strategy

Grab samples (Table 2) were collected at the following locations to give a good representation of the process and its efficiency.

- System Influent
- Nanofiltration Permeate and Concentrate
- Reverse Osmosis Permeate and Concentrate
- Evaporator influent, dry salts, and liquid condensate

Samples were taken at different operational parameters of the plant and even with high recirculation rates stressing the membrane. Sampling campaigns of the NF/RO pilot plant were done on a weekly basis. In total 18 sampling campaigns were carried out.

Table 2: Sampling campaign for the NF/RO pilot plant

Sampling Point	Description	Sample type	N. Samples	Frequency
1	Influent	Grab sample	1	≈Every 7 days
2	NF Permeate	Grab sample	1	≈Every 7 days
3	NF Concentrate	Grab sample	1	≈Every 7 days
4	RO Permeate	Grab sample	1	≈Every 7 days
5	RO Concentrate	Grab sample	1	≈Every 7 days
Total Samples per sampling campaign			5	
Total Samples in all sampling campaigns (n=18)			90	

2.2 Pyrolysis reactor

The thermochemical treatment reactor is a laboratory-scale fixed bed reactor with a screw conveyor, controlled temperature, and controlled sample resident time, in addition to the possibility of controlling nitrogen flux into the system to keep it under anaerobic conditions. A schema of the pyrolysis reactor is provided in Figure 11 and a photo of the full set up is shown in Figure 12.

Figure 11: Schematic preview of Pyrolysis reactor

Material for feeding the reactor can be provided before running the reactor or even while it is running. The system generates two effluents: a solid phase product (biochar) and a gas phase

product (bio-oil after condensation and syngas). To separate bio-oil from syngas in the stack emission stream, the gas effluent from the thermal reactor is sent to a condensation system. The system is also equipped with a stack emission collection system (after the condensation step), differential pressure measurement, and Syngas analyser.

Sampling strategy

Biochar and Bio-Oil samples were collected during the experiments along with the operating parameters especially temperature and residence time. Syngas samples were collected in Inert Foil Gas Sampling bags for direct measurements of PFAS at ACEA Infrastructure Labs. The stack emission collection system was used for trapping PFAS to reach more accurate measurements of PFAS present in the gas effluent after condensation.

Figure 12: Pyrolysis reactor full setup

2.3 Analytical methods

In this chapter is described for the first time the application of methods to quantify PFAS in new matrices that were not investigated in D1.1. The list of new tested matrices include:

- Solids salts recovered by RO/NF concentrate after evaporation
- Biochar (i.e.; solid product from pyrolysis treatment)
- Stack emissions from pyrolysis

Analysis of PFAS in stack emissions samples included analysis of PFAS in different type of matrices:

- Bio-oil obtained after stack emission condensation
- Trapped liquids obtained from the stack emission collection system
- XAD-2 Resin

- Silica
- Liquids obtained from washing solution of the stack emission collection system

In addition, syngas obtained after condensation was collected in gas bag, and it was analysed in gas form for PFAS determination. Details about methods for measuring PFAS in the abovementioned matrices are described below in this document.

2.3.1 Analysis of conventional parameters of liquid wastes and sludges

Conventional parameters to characterize the liquid leachate and sludge were determined according to standard methods (APAH, 2012). The parameters pH, electrical conductivity, chemical oxygen demand (COD), and total dissolved solids (TDS), were analysed in liquid samples. The content of total solids (TS%) and total volatile solids (TVS/TS%) were determined for the solid samples. A SEM analysis was also performed.

2.3.2 Analysis of heavy metals, dioxins and furans in solid samples

ACEA analysed 2 sludge samples, 4 biochar samples and 4 bio-oil samples, for metals and PCDD/F.

a) Metals:

- The metals analysed were: Aluminium, Antimony, Silver, Arsenic, Barium, Beryllium, Boron, Cadmium, Calcium, Cobalt, Chromium, Iron, Phosphorus, Magnesium, Manganese, Molybdenum, Nickel, Lead, Potassium, Copper, Silicon, Sodium, Tin, Tellurium, Vanadium, Zinc, and Mercury.
- For all metals except mercury, the EPA 3052:1996 method was used, which involves microwave digestion with a HNO₃ + HCl mixture at 220 °C and subsequent measurement using the ICP-OES technique.
- The mineralizer used was an Ultrawave from Milestone, while the ICP-MS was an AVIO 550 Max from Perkin Elmer.
- The same mineralization procedure was used for the mercury analysis, while the analysis was conducted in ICP-MS in KED mode, on a Nexion 300X instrument from Perkin Elmer.

b) PCDD+PCDF:

- The 17 congeners WHO of polydichlorodioxins and polydichlorofurans were analysed. The method used was UNI EN 11199:2007. For the sample analysed, 1g of matrix (spiked with labelled internal standard) was extracted by using microwave system with Hexane/Acetone 50/50 (20 mL each) as solvent. The extracted was then filtered and evaporated to a volume of approximately 8 mL. After that the solution has been purified on an LC-Dex automatic system where the sample was eluted through 3 purification columns respectively with the following phases: acid-silica, aluminium oxide and active carbon. After this purification step, the purified sample undergoes evaporation of the solvent and then added with injection standard. One µL sample is injected into a high-resolution gas chromatograph (HRGC) interfaced to a low-resolution mass spectrometer (LRMS), capable of the acquisition of individual ions. The identification of compounds of interest is based both on retention time, determined by means of appropriate calibration solutions, and on the response of the mass spectrometer.
- The instruments utilized was a MS Agilent 7000C coupled to GC Agilent 7890. The LOQ of the method was 1 ng/Kg TEQ for the sum of the 17 congeners.

2.3.3 Target PFAS analysis in liquid and solid samples

ACEA developed a cost-effective method to determine PFAS on different complex matrices. The method is applicable for complex solid matrices, such as sludge, biosolids (e.g. biochar), adsorbents and sediments, and liquid matrices, such as leachate, bio-oil, adsorption and washing liquids.

Different procedures of matrix treatment are performed with the aim of obtaining a matrix-free aliquot of extract for direct injection into a UPLC-MS/MS system. The UPLC-MS/MS system is calibrated in the concentration range of 1-250 ng/L.

a) Leachate, concentrate NF/RO, bio-oil and adsorbent liquid

- Leachate is the solution (or suspension) that forms when liquid travels through a solid and removes some components of that solid with it. Those components may be dissolved or suspended within the liquid. In this case, we refer to leachate produced by the percolation of water in landfilled waste
- Bio-oil is a form of liquid biofuel produced from diverse feedstocks such as waste plastic, crop residues, municipal wastes, algae, waste biomass, agricultural and forestry wastes, etc. by thermochemical conversion techniques. In this case, we refer to bio-oil produced by a pyrolysis process. Bio-oil is a dark brown, organic liquid. It consists of highly oxygenated compounds and is produced through fast pyrolysis or flash pyrolysis. Bio-oil produced during the trial is characterized by a variable content of water and carbon residues.
- Adsorbent liquids refer to aqueous or organic solutions contained in an impinger assembled to capture the condensable phases of an exhaust gas. In this case, we refer to spent gas capture solutions and impingers washing solutions.

b) Sewage sludge, biosolid (biochar) and adsorbent solid

- Sewage slurry is a slurry residue produced from wastewater treatment operations. Typically, sewage sludge comprises approximately 1-3% solids and 97-99% liquids). Sludge can undergo dewatering processes that result in an increase in dry matter content to values between 20-25 %. The method was applied to sludge with a dry matter content of more than 20 %.
- On the other hand, biosolids are treated sewage sludge that adheres to specific standards for its utilization or disposal, with an approximate solid content of nearly 75-90%.
- Adsorbent materials refer to resins and carbons and Glasswool used to capture contaminants in exhaust gases from a pyrolysis process.

c) Method description

- For liquid (influent, concentrate, permeate) samples was used the method described in Zietzschmann et al. (2024).
 - The test method was designed to be easily replicable and transferable to any testing laboratory operating in support of industrial operators. The developed procedure and the obtained performance ensure robustness, reliability and fast turnaround time, with low material costs, high throughput (more than 20 samples per day) and meet the needs for continuous PFAS control and monitoring in complex matrices.
 - For the list of analytes (N.30 target PFAS) see Table 3

- Here is a brief description of the procedures.
 - For permeate and washing water, direct injection of the aliquot taken after filtration on RC 0.2 µm is used. Samples are analysed using the same LC-MS/MS conditions as used to generate the Internal Calibration. Samples are warmed to room temperature and mix well prior to transferring to vials.
 - Internal Calibration (ICAL) is performed continuously, at the head of each analytical session, on N.5 levels in the working range 10- 250 ng/l. If the concentration of any target analyte exceeds the ICAL range of the system, the prepared sample or sample extract should be diluted with 30:70 methanol-water containing and reanalysed. If dilutions cannot be performed, concentrations that exceed the calibration range must be qualified as estimated.
 - For liquid waste such as leachate, feed and concentrate, it was decided to apply a dilution procedure.
 - The limits of quantification (LOQ) for leachate and liquid waste (concentrate) are 1 µg/L and are calculated as described in EPA Method 8327:2021 and EPA 40 CFR Appendix B to Part 136. For permeate and wash water LOQ is 0.02 µg/L.
 - Methods has been assessed on multiple real samples and have been validate for all compounds.

- For solid (sludge) samples was used the method described in D.1.1 - Methods for PFAS in waters and complex matrices - filename and version: PROMISCES_D1-1_Methods for PFAS_V2 (Version 2) – 18/09/2023, p.3.1. The method was also extended to biochar samples.
 - The test method was designed to be easily replicable and transferable to any testing laboratory operating in support of industrial operators. The developed procedure and the obtained performance ensure robustness, reliability and fast turnaround time, with low material costs, high throughput (more than 20 samples per day) and meet the needs for continuous PFAS control and monitoring in complex matrices.
 - For the list of analytes (N.30 target PFAS) see Table 3.

- Here is a brief description of the method.
 - Procedure: 1 g of solid matrix is weighted into a 15-50 mL polypropylene (or glass) centrifuge tube.
 - Extraction deuterated standard M2PFUdA 100 µg/kg for sludge is added. After an equilibration time of 30 minutes, the extraction is done with 10 mL of methanol. The sample is vortexed and sonicated for 30 minutes at room temperature.
 - After centrifugation (4000 rpm, 5 min), supernatant is transferred into glass or polypropylene conical-bottomed vials and dried (T ≤ 55 °C) under flux of N₂
 - The sample is resolved with 1 mL of Methanol, transferred in centrifuge tube (4000 rpm, 5 min)
 - Supernatant is diluted 100 times (for sludges), resulting in a 70:30 Water: Methanol mixture. The extract is injected after adding of the internal standard mixture. Samples are analysed using the same LC-MS/MS conditions as used to generate the Internal Calibration (see D.1.1).
 - Samples are warmed to room temperature and mix well prior to transferring to vials.

- Internal Calibration (ICAL) is performed continuously, at the head of each analytical session, on at least N. 5 levels starting from a minimum concentration of not less than 10 ng/L until 250 ng/L.
- The operator can use a different criterion if he can demonstrate the effectiveness of the solution
- If the concentration of any target analyte exceeds the ICAL range of the system, the prepared sample or sample extract should be diluted with 30:70 methanol-water containing and reanalysed. If dilutions cannot be performed, concentrations that exceed the calibration range must be qualified as estimated.
- The laboratory monitors the recoveries of isotopically labelled surrogate for each matrix. The percent recovery of each surrogate should fall within the acceptance criteria (70 %-130 %). If surrogate do not meet the acceptance criteria, reanalysis and/or preparation of samples may be warranted. Otherwise, the associated target analytes may be reported with appropriate data qualifiers.
- The method for biochar was validated. LOQ was in the range 1-10 µg/kg. Accuracy was in the range 82.0-104.0 %. Precision was in the range 4-18 %, for N.30 target PFAS.

2.3.4 Target PFAS analysis in stack emission

2.3.4.1 Stack emission sampling

Stack emission collection system was set and configured based on Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) methods available as “Other Test Method 45 (OTM-45)” which has an objective of collecting and quantifying analysis of specific semi-volatile (Boiling point > 100 °C) and particulate-bound per- and polyfluorinated alkyl substances (PFAS) in air emissions from stationary sources.

The method does not include syngas for bio-oil collection as the measurement are usually in industrial stacks not directly at the effluent gas of Pyrolysis Reactor.

In Figure 13 and Figure 14 you can see the original sampling train as mentioned in OTM-45 and the modified one that was used, respectively.

Figure 13: OTM-45 Original Sampling Train

Figure 14: Modified OTM-45 Sampling Train

The collection system starts with the effluent of the pyrolysis reactor followed by water-jacketed coil that cools the gas stream to allow for condensation of moisture, Volatile Organic Compounds (VOCs) and Hydrocarbons (i.e., bio-oil). The bio-oil is then collected in a bottle and the gas continues its path to reach the Glasswool then the water-jacketed XAD[®]-2 resin tube to adsorb the PFAS

available in the effluent gas emission (20 g of resin with length to width ratio 2:1). The XAD[®]-2 resin tube is followed by four bottles each containing 100 ml of Deionized water. The final step of the collection system is a second water-jacketed XAD[®]-2 resin tube as refining step to capture any PFAS that may break through the primary module and the water impingers, followed by a bottle of 200 g of Silica to absorb any extra humidity.

The XAD[®]-2 resin is kept at temperature no more than 20 °C, and this is guaranteed thanks to the ice bath (chiller) circulating the whole system to ensure optimal PFAS adsorption.

After the end of each experiment, in addition to the collection of all the samples inside the tubes and impingers, washing cycles has been to all the system to make sure nothing goes uncollected. And you can see in the Figure 15 a small diagram showing sampling points and washing collection points.

Figure 15: Samples and Washings collection train

2.3.4.2 PFAS analysis in bio-oil

For bio-oil samples was developed a specific method. For the list of analytes (N.30 target PFAS) see Table 34 in section 3.1. of Deliverable D.1.1.

Bio-oil produced during the trials was characterized by a highly variable composition that made it difficult to validate the method. Special care must be taken when preparing the sample for LC-MS/MS analysis.

In particular, it is necessary to ascertain the water content of the bio-oil sample and the presence of carbon residues to select the correct sample transfer and dilution procedure.

The procedure was as follows: one millilitre of bio-oil was measured by a volumetric flask and weighed the sample. The sample is transferred into a polypropylene or glass centrifuge tube, rinsing the volumetric flask with a quantity of methanol sufficient to dilute the sample by at least 10 times.

The sample was shaken manually and centrifugated at 4000 rpm for 5 min. An aliquote of the supernatant was prelevated and diluted 10 times to obtain a water-methanol mixture (70:30 v/v + 0.1 % v/v of formic acid), then adding internal standards at a known concentration within the range of the calibration curve.

The extract is injected after adding of the internal standard mixture. Samples are analysed using the same LC-MS/MS conditions as used to generate the Internal Calibration (see D.1.1). Samples are warmed to room temperature and mix well prior to transferring to vials.

Internal Calibration (ICAL) is performed continuously, at the head of each analytical session, on at least n. 5 levels starting from a minimum concentration of not less than 10 ng/L until 250 ng/L.

The operator can use a different criterion if he can demonstrate the effectiveness of the solution

If the concentration of any target analyte exceeds the ICAL range of the system, the prepared sample or sample extract should be diluted with 30:70 methanol-water containing and reanalysed. If dilutions cannot be performed, concentrations that exceed the calibration range must be qualified as estimated.

The laboratory monitors the recoveries of isotopically labelled surrogate for each matrix. The percent recovery of each surrogate should fall within the acceptance criteria (70 %-130 %). If surrogate do not meet the acceptance criteria, reanalysis and/or preparation of samples may be warranted. Otherwise, the associated target analytes may be reported with appropriate data qualifiers.

The method was validated. LOQ was 1-5 µg/kg. Accuracy was in the range 72.0-109.0 %. Precision was in the range 5-18 %, for N.30 target PFAS.

2.3.4.3 PFAS analysis in syngas

For PFAS analysis in syngas, the following matrices were analysed, in addition to the biochar and bio-oil produced:

- spent gas capture solutions
- impingers washing solutions
- XAD-2
- carbon black and glasswool
- exhaust gas

For the list of analytes (N.30 target PFAS) see Table 34 in section 3.1. of Deliverable D.1.1.

Spent gas capture solutions and impingers washing solutions

Spent gas capture solutions and impingers washing solution were analysed by the method for liquid (influent, concentrate, permeate) samples in Deliverable D.1.1. A known amount of internal standard was added to 0.5ml of sample and the solution was brought to 1ml with methanol. The limit of quantification (LOQ) was in the range 0.1-0.5 µg/L. No further validation was necessary, as the analysed matrices have similar characteristics to those already validated in Deliverable D.1.1.

XAD-2, carbon black and glasswool

XAD-2, carbon black and glasswool were analysed by the same method for solid (sludge and biochar) samples in D.1.1. A known amount of isotope dilution standard was added, and the methanol was allowed to dry 15 minutes. The XAD-2 was then extracted by ultrasonication with a methanol solution. The solution was ultrasonicated for 1h, and each 15 minutes the solution was manually shaken. After the solution has been decanted, the entire extraction procedure was repeated with methanol solution. After the final extraction the entire XAD-2, carbon and glasswool were filtered and the residue were washed several times with fresh methanol. A split of the extract was made, half of the solution was evaporated to near dryness and made up to 30:70 methanol-water.

Validation tests were carried out to demonstrate the applicability of the method for adsorbents.

QA/QC parameters performed and evaluated were:

- Calibration for each batch (minimum of 5 points to be retained)
- Second source calibration verification (where available)
- Assessment of the isotopically labelled internal standard recovery (evaluation criteria of 30-200%). Internal standard recoveries outside of the evaluation criteria of 30-200% were periodically observed. As results are calculated using the internal standard response to correct for potential low extraction efficiency or analytical variation, the results should be minimally impacted by these deviations. The recoveries were >30%, indicating that sufficient sensitivity was likely maintained. The laboratory identifies these exceedances in the Analytical Reports.
- Matrix spikes on samples (evaluation criteria 70-130%). No recoveries outside of the 70-130% criteria were observed in some cases in laboratory-fortified blanks and samples.
- Method blanks were analysed with the impinger solution samples with periodic detections of individual PFAS.
- The maximum of the following three parameters was rounded up and utilized as the LOQ for samples:
 - o The lowest valid calibration standard in the instrument calibration.
 - o The Maximum STPB + 10 standard deviation.
 - o The Maximum STFB + 10 standard deviation

The limit of quantification (LOQ) was in the range 1-5 ng/g.

Gas-exhaust

Gas samples were delivered to the laboratory in Tedlar® bags. The analytical instrument used for this analysis was an Agilent GCMS (6890B GC, 5973 mass spectral detector [MSD]) coupled with a Markes TD TD100-xr desorption injection system. The gaseous calibration standards included the components listed in Table 3. at a concentration in the range of 0.5 – 10 ng injected. The compounds were measured in selected ion monitoring (SIM) mode to achieve the lowest reporting limits.

The calibration of the analytical system was performed by diluting the gaseous calibration standards at different concentrations into individual canisters and injecting 500 ml from these to the system to achieve a multi-point calibration curve.

The system accurately samples 500 ml of gas out of the gasbag in a desorption tube, removes the water and traps the components of interest on a Markes Greenhouse gas cold trap TD100-xr at -30°C. During injection, the trap is rapidly heated (12°C/s) until 275°C for 5 min, to desorb the volatile components and transfer them to the GC.

For the analysis of components, the GC was equipped with a Agilent DB 624 UI, 30 m × 0.25 mm × 1.40 mm fused silica on the MS end acting as a restrictor while the GC oven program is 35°C for 2,5 min, then at 15°C/min to 260°C for 3 min with MS in SIM mode recording the ions 69 (CF₃), 131 (C₃F₅) and 181 (C₄F₇).

QA/QC parameters performed and evaluated were:

- Calibration (4 points)
- Calibration verification check standards
- Method blanks were run with each sequence. (Applied criterion: below ½ reporting limit).

The maximum of the following three parameters was rounded up and utilized as the LOQ for samples:

- The lowest valid calibration standard in the instrument calibration.
- The Maximum STPB + 10 standard deviation.
- The Maximum STFB + 10 standard deviation

The limit of quantification (LOQ) was in the range 50-100 ng/m³.

Table 3: PFAS analytes and their Limit of Quantification (LOQ) for different matrices

	NF Permeate	RO Permeate	Evaporation Condensate	LLTP Effluent	NF Concentrate	RO Concentrate	Bio-Oil	Stack emission Trapping liquids	Stack emission washing liquids	Biochar	RO dried concentrate	LLTP Sludge	XAD-2 Resin	Silica	Glasswool
	µg/l	µg/l	µg/l	µg/l	µg/l	µg/l	µg/l	µg/l	µg/l	µg/kg	µg/kg	µg/kg	µg/kg	µg/kg	µg/kg
4:2 FTS	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	1	1	1	1	1	1
6:2 FTS	0.02	0.02	0.02	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
8:2 FTS	0.02	0.02	0.02	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
C6O4	0.07	0.07	0.07	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
FOSA	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	1	1	1	1	1	1
GENX	0.02	0.02	0.02	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
N-EtFOSAA	0.02	0.02	0.02	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
N-MeFOSAA	0.02	0.02	0.02	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
NaDONA	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	1	1	1	1	1	1
PFBA	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	1	1	1	1	1	1
PFBS	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	1	1	1	1	1	1
PFDA	0.02	0.02	0.02	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
PFDoA	0.02	0.02	0.02	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
PFDoS	0.02	0.02	0.02	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
PFDS	0.02	0.02	0.02	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
PFHpA	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	1	1	1	1	1	1
PFHpS	0.02	0.02	0.02	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
PFHxA	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	1	1	1	1	1	1
PFHxS	0.02	0.02	0.02	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
PFNA	0.02	0.02	0.02	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
PFNS	0.02	0.02	0.02	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
PFOA	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	1	1	1	1	1	1
PFOS	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	1	1	1	1	1	1
PFPeA	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	1	1	1	1	1	1
PFPeS	0.02	0.02	0.02	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
PFTeDA	0.02	0.02	0.02	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
PFTrDA	0.02	0.02	0.02	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
PFTrDS	0.02	0.02	0.02	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
PFUdA	0.02	0.02	0.02	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
PFUdS	0.02	0.02	0.02	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1

2.4 Assessment of impaired biological activity and toxicity

2.4.1 Experimental setups

The experimental set-ups used can be summarized as follows:

1st experimental series: General characterization of leachate and sludge from the Sofia Solid Waste Treatment Plant

Characterization and toxicity assessment of leachate was performed. The activated sludge from the biological stage of LLTP were also investigated. Conventional physicochemical and chemical indicators, toxicological and enzymological parameters were used (see the next chapter). Toxicity of leachates was assessed in samples from different stages of treatment (crude leachate; after biological treatment; effluent from the treatment plant). Also, the leachate toxicity was evaluated at different dilutions of the leachate (5, 10, 50 and 100 times).

2nd experimental series: Assessment of changes in complex toxicity of leachate and in metabolic activity of sludge after plasma treatment

The changes in toxicity of leachates were also determined in samples treated with plasma sources and devices described in section 2.5. The leachates without any additives were treated with microwave plasma torch in continuous flow at different power of 50, 75 and 100 W. The effect on the toxicity of multiple processing with plasma (1, 3, 5 times) was also tested at continuous flow.

Additionally, another experiment was conducted to assess the toxicity of untreated and plasma-treated leachate on activated sludge. The activated sludge for this part of the experiments was taken from a municipal WWTP and is well-functioning with high metabolic activity. After treating the leachate with plasma, the activated sludge was incubated for one hour in its presence and then the degree of inhibition/damage to metabolic activity was measured using the fluorescence method described below. For better visualization, the fluorescence images of activated sludge from LLTP and activated sludge from a municipal WWTP without leachate were also compared to track metabolic activity.

3rd experimental series: Experiments with model solution of PFAS at high and low concentrations

The model solutions with high concentrations of PFOA for simulation of acute toxic effects on biological systems were analysed. The reduction of PFOA toxicity was monitored in samples treated with microwave plasma torch in continuous mode and Dielectric Barrier Discharge (DBD) plasma. The PFOA concentrations used were 2.5, 5, and 10 mg/L. The toxicity of untreated and treated samples was analysed, coupled with the morphological change in cells of test microorganism.

The effect of low concentrations of different PFAS (PFOA and PFDA) was also investigated in model solutions (aqueous solution of single PFAS compounds) and plasma treated ones. The concentrations used were 100, 75, and 25 µg/L. The plasma sources used in these experiments were Beta-device and Surfaguide.

4th experimental series: Toxicity reduction of leachate spiked with PFOA after plasma treatment

In the last series of experiments, the leachate was additionally spiked with PFOA (high concentrations of 2.5, 5, and 10 mg/L). The parameters studied were the same as above. The plasma used was a microwave torch in continuous flow and batch mode at 100 W input power.

2.4.2 Fluorescence methods and indicators

2.1.1.1 Staining with CTC/DAPI

The adapted and specially modified methods based on fluorescent staining and digital image analyses were developed and applied for detection of complex toxicity of leachate and assessment of impaired biological activity of sludge/membrane concentrates during LL treatment. The method was also adapted and verified for assessment of toxicity of individual PFAS in model solutions and leachates spiked with PFAS. The advantages of fluorescence methods are their quickness, high precision, combination of qualitative and quantitative information, flexibility, and applicability to almost all matrices.

The method uses different test microorganisms and biological systems for assessment of the toxic effect of leachate and PFAS:

- *Escherichia coli* (Migula) Castellani and Chalmers (ATCC 700728) – reference strain in quality control of environmental samples;
- *Pseudomonas aureofaciens* AP-9 (current classification and phylogenetic affiliation – *P. chlororaphis*) – the strain isolated from contaminated soils with high proven potential for biodegradation of xenobiotic compounds;
- Activated sludge from WWTP of municipal wastewater.

The biomass of the 18-hour bacterial cultures or activated sludge was washed in physiological solution by centrifugation at 5000 rpm for 5 min. A 50 µL volume of cell suspension was used and centrifuged at 5000 rpm for 5 min. The volume of the supernatant was replaced with the different samples being tested. A cell suspension with test bacteria or activated sludge in a glucose medium was used as a positive control.

Fluorescent analyses were done after homogenization and 2 hours of incubation to assess metabolic inhibition and cell survival. Fluorescent analysis was performed using 5-cyano-2,3-ditolyl tetrazolium chloride (CTC) at 5 mM and 4',6-diamidino-2-phenylindole (DAPI) at 1 µM/mL. CTC accumulates in metabolically active cells as the fluorescent compound CTC-formazan, whose concentration is proportional to the hydrogen cations transported in the respiratory chains (Smith and McFeters 1997; Schaule, Flemming, and Ridgway 1993). DAPI binds to DNA and stains all cells, providing information about their total number and morphology in the samples (Günther et al. 2009). To stain, use CTC for 45 minutes at room temperature or DAPI for 15 minutes at 4°C. The samples were imaged in triplicate with an epifluorescence microscope Leica DM6 B, using the same camera and LAS X Core software settings (Figure 16).

Figure 16: Epifluorescence microscope Leica DM6 B

2.4.2.1 Digital image analysis and indicators used

The images were digitally analysed using the software DAIME (Daims, Lücker, and Wagner 2006). The following parameters were used as toxicity indicators:

- share of viable microorganisms, based on the ratio of the cells, stained with CTC and DAPI;
- mean number of active microorganisms per image, based on CTC;
- metabolic activity, based on CTC fluorescence intensity;
- changes in the cell morphology (based on average cell circumference and degree of cell elongation, called circularity, DAPI dyeing).

Calculations were performed on the basis of digital analysis of 15-20 pairs of CTC and DAPI images. The processing of the obtained data was carried out with Microsoft Excel.

2.4.2.2 Enzyme activities assays

In addition to the toxicity assessment based on fluorescence techniques, the analysis of key enzyme activities of the test microorganism in the presence of leachate was also performed (Table 4). The succinate dehydrogenase activity (SDH) was investigated as an indicator of the activity of the central metabolic pathways in the cells and their inhibition from leachate. This was done by the method of Veeger et al., 1969. The oxygenases are enzymes determining the biodegradation of aromatic compounds. The catechol 1,2-dioxygenase (C12DO), the catechol 2,3-dioxygenase (C23DO), and the protocatechuate 3,4-dioxygenase (P34DO) activities were measured. The methods are described by Farr and Cain, 1968; Willets and Cain, 1972 and Fujisawa and Hayaishi, 1968.

Table 4: Enzyme activities used as indicators

	Enzyme activity	Indicator for:
1	succinate dehydrogenase activity (SDH)	Impaired central metabolic pathways in a biological system
2	catechol 1,2-dioxygenase (C12DO)	Impaired peripheral metabolism of toxic compounds
3	catechol 2,3-dioxygenase (C23DO)	
4	protocatechuate 3,4-dioxygenase (P34DO)	

2.4.2.4 SEM analyses

The electron microscopic analysis was performed on SEM-JEOL 5510 to verify the changes in the morphology of cells due to the toxic effect of leachate and PFAS after plasma treatment. The samples were treated using increasing concentrations of ethyl alcohol and covered with a gold layer before the observation.

2.4.2.5 Analyses of conventional parameters of leachates and sludge

The COD was used for the determination of the total organic content of the leachate and its changes after different treatments by a standardized dichromate method. For the description of leachate and sludge, the following indicators were also used dissolved oxygen (mg/L), temperature (°C), pH, conductivity (mS/cm), BOD5 (mg/L), total phosphorus (mg/L), total nitrogen (mg/L), ammonium (mg/L), nitrites (mg/L), nitrates (mg/L), sulfates (mg/L), chlorides (mg/L), insoluble and soluble suspended solids (mg/L). All parameters were determined by standard methods according to BDS-EN-ISO standards.

2.5 Plasma treatment of concentrates and sludge

2.5.1 Plasma sources and plasma reactive species

Plasma can be produced at atmospheric pressure by various types of plasma sources operating with different working gases and gas mixtures. Such a plasma is a non-equilibrium one, with electron temperature of 1–2 eV and much lower gas temperature (temperature of the heavy particles as ions, excited atoms, molecules, and radicals). Non-equilibrium plasma is highly reactive. The reactive plasma components include charged particles (electrons and ions), excited atoms and molecules, radicals, UV and VUV radiation, electromagnetic fields, and the heating component, all of which simultaneously act on the sample (Figure 17). Many other active particles are produced as a result of the interactions of plasma with the surrounding air and the sample surface. Both oxidation and reduction reactions are possible during the plasma treatment. Plasma has already demonstrated its bactericidal, virucidal, fungicidal and disinfection effects as well as its ability to destroy organic and inorganic pollutants (Todorova et al. 2022). This is the reason for considering plasma treatment as a promising technology also for PFAS reduction.

Figure 17: Plasma active components and reactive particles produced in the air and the sample surface

2.5.2 Experimental setups

The plasma characteristics and its ability to degrade PFAS compounds significantly depend on the plasma source and its operational regime. Systematic investigations of the effectiveness of three plasma sources (Surfatron Microwave plasma torch, Beta device, and Surfaguide) at various operational modes for degradation of long- and short-chain PFAS substances were performed at the Plasma technology laboratory, Clean & Circle CoC at UNISOFIA. In addition, similar joint experiments were done with Pin-jets plasma source at the Institute of Physics at the University of Belgrade. The previous investigations of PFAS degradation by single Pin-jet plasma system treatment show high removal efficiency (>90%) for longer chain PFAS (Topolovec et al. 2024). The joint experiments are performed with a new triple Pin-jets plasma system. All four plasma sources are presented in Table 5. Three series of experiments were performed, and the corresponding operational modes are denoted as (1), (2) and (3) in Table 5.

For plasma treatment various types of samples were used:

- landfill leachate;
- landfill leachate spiked with PFAS;
- model solutions of various PFAS compounds (PFAS compounds diluted in ultrapure or distilled water).

Series of experiments:

- (1) Comparison of the effectiveness of Microwave plasma torch and Beta device in flow and batch operational modes for degradation of PFAS compounds in LL. The operational conditions are presented in Table 5.
- (2) Investigation and optimisation of Beta device treatment parameters (input power, treatment time) in two modes – underwater and surface treatment (Table 5) for higher effectiveness of PFAS degradation in model solutions.
- (3) Comparison of the effectiveness of three plasma sources: Atmospheric pressure plasma jet – Pin-jets, Belgrade; Beta plasma device, Sofia; Surfaguide plasma device, Sofia. All three operating in batch surface mode for treating PFAS compounds diluted in ultrapure water.

More details about the plasma sources and their operational regimes can be found in Marinova et al. (in preparation).

2.5.3 Plasma replication and potential upscaling

To test for plasma replication and upscaling potential, LL samples from the Rastatt landfill (Stuttgart, Germany) were treated by Fraunhofer IGB using their plasma device.

The total organic carbon (TOC) content, as well as the chemical oxygen demand (COD) of the untreated LL (R0) was reduced by flocculation with 508 mg/L of anhydrous aluminium chloride. The decanted and filtered LL (R1) resulting from flocculation was used for nine tests, consisting of three parameter sets with three repeat attempts each. Process duration and plasma parameters were kept constant, and only the process gases – argon (Ar), oxygen (O₂), and hydrogen (H₂) - were varied (Table 6). Although the plasma parameters were kept constant, different discharge types resulted from different process gases, which appear in slightly different plasma powers (Table 6). The 5L test batches were continuously circulated through the reactor for the duration of the treatment.

Table 5: Plasma sources and operational modes used for the experiments with Bulgarian LL

Operational modes	Plasma source			
	Surfatron Microwave Plasma torch	Beta device	Pin-jets	Surfaguide
Flow	<p>(1) Power: 20 W Frequency: 2.45 GHz Repetitions: 1x, 2x, 3x Gas: Argon, 3 L/min Liquid samples flow: 1.13 mL/min</p>			
Batch under water		<p>(2) Power: 15 W, 30 W Frequency: 2.45 GHz Treatment time: 5, 10, 20 min Volume: 50 mL</p>		
Batch at the surface	<p>(3) Power: 500 W, 1000 W Frequency: 2.45 GHz Treatment time: 5 min, 3 min Volume: 50 mL, 35 mL Gas: Argon, 4 L/min Temperature at t0: > 280 °C</p>			

Table 6: Parameters of plasma tests performed with LL from Rastatt landfill (sccm = standard cubic centimetres per minute).

Sample	Gas Mixture	Duration in h	Mean Plasma Power in W	Plasma Energy in kWh	pH after Treatment
R0	None, raw LL				
R1	None, pretreated LL				
A1	Ar: 200 sccm	6	493	2.96	8.3
A2	Ar: 200 sccm	6	492	2.95	8.2
A3	Ar: 200 sccm	6	500	3	8.8
B1	Ar: 120 sccm O ₂ : 80sccm	6	542	3.25	7.9
B2	Ar: 120 sccm O ₂ : 80sccm	6	537	3.22	8.1
B3	Ar: 120 sccm O ₂ : 80sccm	6	543	3.26	8.1
C1	Ar: 195 sccm H ₂ : 5sccm	6	519	3.11	8
C2	Ar: 195 sccm H ₂ : 5sccm	6	499	2.99	8.3
C3	Ar: 195 sccm H ₂ : 5sccm	6	513	3.08	7.9

Figure 18: Schematic drawing of the plasma reactor (left) and photo of the experimental setup. Figures provided by Fraunhofer IGB.

With a test duration of six hours, the effective direct plasma contact time of the water was around 200 seconds, considering the water film thickness and the flow rates. The chemical reactions also took place outside the direct plasma contact zone.

2.6 Assessment methods

2.6.1 LCA analysis of membranes and pyrolysis

LCA is a tool for assessing the possible environmental impacts of a product, activity or process along all stages of the life cycle, i.e. ‘from cradle to grave’. This assessment is carried out through the quantification of inputs (resources such as water, energy and raw materials) and outputs (emissions into the environment such as air, water and soil). The structure of LCA can be summarised in 4 successive steps, as outlined in ISO 14044 (Bhakar et al. 2016 ; Bonton et al. 2012 ; Razman, Hanafiah, and Mohammad 2022 ; ISO 2006) :

1. Definition of scope and objectives: Planning phase of the study. The scope, the functional unit, the system boundaries, the necessary data (quality and category), assumptions, and limitations are defined.
2. Life Cycle Inventory (LCI): It is the most important phase. Input and output flows are defined by building a representative model of the system and an inventory table with all data collected on which the next step is based.
3. Life Cycle Impact Assessment (LCIA): The potential environmental impacts are determined by linking the inventory to damage categories using specific calculation methodologies.

4. Interpretation of the results: This phase offers a comprehensive and critical analysis of relevant data and may identify the changes needed to reduce the environmental impact of processes.

Each LCA analysis is constructed differently based on the process under study, and the necessary data tends to include the quantities of material used and transported, the type of transport carried out, the origin, the quantity and source of energy consumed, the presence of waste and its fate. From this information, it is possible to associate and derive environmental impacts, which fall into several categories (e.g. global warming, eutrophication, ecotoxicity, acidification). Impacts can be assessed at the midpoint level when considering environmental effects (e.g. acid rain, eutrophication, global warming...) or endpoints when considering the consequences of environmental effects (e.g. biodiversity reduction, human longevity...). Midpoints can be converted into endpoints, which can be aggregated into a single value (Pt) that expresses the score of each impact, leading to simplifying the results of the LCIA phase but also to an increase in the associated uncertainty.

2.6.1.1 Definition of scope and objective

This study assesses and compares the environmental impacts of four different operational scenarios for treating effluent from a LLTP. The four scenarios are:

1) NF membrane + Pyrolysis (NF + PY)

In this scenario, the effluent of the LLTP passes through the NF membranes and the resultant permeate and concentrate are discharged and evaporated. The salt resulting from the evaporation of the concentrate is treated through pyrolysis with the sludge produced in the LLTP and a part of the sludge produced in the municipal WWTP. The amount of salt is 30% of the sum of the sludges (dry weight). The sludges are previously dried in bio-dryers to pass from a solid content of 25% to a solid content of 70%. The resulting biochar is sent to the landfill as hazardous waste.

2) RO membrane + Pyrolysis (RO + PY)

This scenario is the same as #1, except an RO membrane is used instead of an NF membrane.

3) NF membrane + Incineration (NF + IN)

In this scenario, the effluent of the LLTP passes through the NF membrane and the resultant permeate and concentrate are discharged and evaporated. The salt resulting from the evaporation of the concentrate is sent to an incineration plant together with the sludge produced in the LLTP and a part of the sludge produced in the municipal WWTP. The amount of salt is 30% of the sum of the sludges (dry weight). The sludges have a water content of 75%. The resulting ash goes to the landfill as hazardous waste.

4) RO membrane + Incineration (RO + IN)

This scenario is the same as #3, except an RO membrane is used instead of an NF membrane.

The system boundaries were defined in [Figure 20](#). The functional unit was set as 1 m³ of effluent of the LLTP entering the system.

2.6.1.2 Inventory Analysis (LCI)

Once the scope of the study was defined, the data were collected and validated (Table 49, Table 50, Table 51 and Table 52, Annex B). The data in the tables are primary data, i.e. specific to the site under study. There are also secondary data, i.e. not directly collected, measured or estimated, which are inferred during the calculation phase from third-party LCI databases included in the calculation software, to quantify unknown information such as, for example, the input and output flow for the production of a specific reagent or its transport. Specifically, the Swiss Ecoinvent v3.10 database was used within the Umberto® LCA+ v11 software.

Mass flow data used for the evaluation were obtained by pilot experiments described in previous paragraph, and data were scaled-up to consider scenarios able to treat the whole liquid waste flowrate at Jesi LLTP. Missing data for elaboration were taken by literature studies as explained in Table 49 to Table 52 in Annex B.

The material usage in the NF and RO membranes fabrication is listed in Table 53 (Bordbar et al. 2022).

Figure 19: System boundaries of landfill leachate treatment and management

2.6.1.3 Impact Assessment (LCIA)

The main steps for assessing the environmental impacts associated with the activities identified in the inventory are:

1. **Classification of impacts:** choice of the environmental impact categories where to cluster the potential impacts (emissions, raw material consumption, energy and water).
2. **Characterisation of impacts:** quantification through standardised formulas of the impact score of each impact category to obtain the environmental profile of the process considered (characterised by environmental impact scores for each category).
3. **Normalisation of impacts:** comparison of the impacts produced and those that would occur in a common production system, through the ratio of a reference value (usually world, European or regional average data with reference to a given time interval).

In this study, the Life Cycle Impact Assessment (LCIA) phase was largely automated thanks to the use of LCA software Umberto LCA+ v11. This software uses graphic modelling of the product life cycle and allows analysing, assessing, and visualising the environmental impacts in different categories. The impact calculation methodology used in this work is Recipe 2016 H. ReCiPe is one of the most widely used methods that aims to transform the results of the LCI phase into a limited number of indicators expressing the relative severity of an environmental impact category. Indicators are determined at two levels: midpoint indicators and endpoint indicators.

The normalization of the impacts allows in a semi-quantitative way to identify which categories can be considered more relevant than the others, facilitating the interpretation of the results (Sleeswijk et al. 2008). A commonly used reference is the average yearly environmental load in a country or continent, divided by the number of inhabitants. In this study the normalisation was performed according to the revised normalization scores of ReCiPe 2016 (“Normalization Scores ReCiPe 2016 | RIVM” 2024).

Table 7 shows the midpoint indicators considered for this case and their possible influence on the endpoint indicators

Table 7: Midpoint indicators and their influence on endpoint indicators

Category MIDPOINT	Abbreviation	UoM	Brief description	ED	RA	HH
Climate change	GWP	kg CO2 eq.	Effects caused by the emission of greenhouse gases into the atmosphere, in addition to human activities, which influence their atmospheric concentration.	X		X
Fine particulate matter formation	PMFP	kg PM2.5 eq.	It considers the impact on human health, generated by particulate matter (total suspended dust, PM10, PM2.5, PM0.1) of primary or secondary (SO2 and NOx) emission.			X
Fossil resource scarcity	FFP	kg oil eq.	They examine resource depletion by considering the effects on both the		X	

Category MIDPOINT	Abbreviation	UoM	Brief description	ED	RA	HH
Mineral resources scarcity	SOP	kg Cu eq.	use of renewable resources (such as water, wind and wood) and non-renewable resources (such as minerals and fossil fuels).		X	
Freshwater ecotoxicity	FETP	kg 1.4-DBC eq.	Toxic effects are based on the relative risk and consequences associated with chemicals that are released into the environment. In particular, they are based on a model that considers the fate of these chemicals, species exposure and differences in toxicological responses (probability of effects and severity).	X		
Terrestrial ecotoxicity	TETP	kg 1.4-DBC eq.		X		
Marine ecotoxicity	METP	kg 1.4-DBC eq.		X		
Marine eutrophication	MEP	kg N eq.	Impacts on aquatic and terrestrial ecosystems from the macronutrients nitrogen and phosphorus, present in bioavailable forms.			
Freshwater eutrophication	FEP	kg P eq.		X		
Water use	WCP	m ³	Effects on water use.	X		X
Human toxicity: cancer	HTPc	kg 1.4-DBC eq.	Probability of a human health effect associated with the emission of a certain amount of a chemical. Based on USES-LCA 2.0 (toxic pollutants: metals and organics) and EUTREND (atmospheric transport for primary and secondary aerosols) models.			X
Human toxicity: non-cancer	HTPnc	kg 1.4-DBC eq.				X
Ionising radiation	IRP	kBq Co-60 eq.	Impacts on human health and ecosystems generated by ionising radiation, which is capable of producing, directly or indirectly, the ionisation of atoms and molecules in the medium through which it passes.			X
Land use	LOP	m ² x y	Effects on land use.	X		
Photochemical ozone formation: ecosystems quality	EOFP	kg NOx eq.	It considers the impacts on human health (respiratory diseases) and ecosystems (damage to vegetation) caused by photochemically created ozone. It is based on the European LOTOS-EUROS atmospheric transport model.	X		
Photochemical ozone formation: human health	HOFP	kg NOx eq.				X
Ozone depletion	ODP	kg CFC11 eq.	Assesses the depletion of the ozone layer. Impacts assessed by considering the residence time of the substance considered, the formation of Equivalent Effective Stratospheric Chlorine (EESC) and the resulting destruction of the ozone layer, all using CFC-11, i.e. trichlorofluoromethane, as the reference substance.	X		
Terrestrial acidification	TAP	kg SO ₂ eq.	It considers the impacts caused by acidification generated by emissions of acidifying gases into the atmosphere, which, when deposited in water and soil, lead to an increase	X		

Category MIDPOINT	Abbreviation	UoM	Brief description	ED	RA	HH
			in the concentration of hydrogen ions and thus an increase in acidity.			

LEGEND: X contributes to the calculation of the endpoint indicator; ED: Impact on biodiversity; RA: Impact on resource availability; HH: Impact on human health

2.6.2 LCC analysis of the membrane pilot system

Life Cycle Costing (LCC) is a methodology aimed at calculating the overall cost of a product or a service over its life span or life cycle. Traditionally, it takes into account mainly investment, operation, maintenance and end of life disposal costs. Conventional LCC techniques are mainly applied in the framework of decisions over products or investments requiring high initial capital (e.g., transport systems, energy systems). In wastewater infrastructures usually, the operational costs exceed the initial investment costs, and this is important to consider when balancing a more expensive investment with lower operational costs or longer lifetime against an alternative with lower initial investment costs but higher operational costs.

LCC is seen alongside LCA as one of the main pillars in an evaluation of sustainability. LCC has some similarity to LCA. For LCC, like for LCA, goal and scope (system boundaries, the object of study, allocation, impact assessment), and other aspects need to be defined and aligned with the decisions taken for the LCA in order to obtain an overall consistent analysis. The life cycle and system boundaries need to be equivalent, but not necessarily the same (“A Guide to Life Cycle Costing - PRé Sustainability” 2024).

Methodology

In this study, LCC was limited to the operation of the RO/NF pilot system, where consumption and costs were scaled to treat the total flow rate of LL treated at Jesi treatment plant.

The scenarios considered include the NF or the RO systems, the evaporation of the concentrate, and the transport and incineration of the derived salts. The cost components considered for the LCC evaluation are listed in Table 8.

Table 8: Cost items of NF and the RO scenarios.

Costs	UoM - Unit of Measurement	NF	RO
Capital	€	153.450,00 €	157.850,00 €
Maintenance	€/y	60.416,40 €	72.196,42 €
Energy: - membrane filtration - concentrate evaporation	€/y	128.649,64 €	172.445,00 €
Plant operation: - membrane replacement - reagents consumption	€/y	369.627,83 €	383.371,24 €
Transport and disposal (incineration) of concentrate	€/y	105.886,50 €	166.148,00 €

Costs of maintenance, energy and plant operation in Table 8 have been discounted to calculate their Present Value using equation (1) (Fuller and Petersen 1995):

$$PV = A_0 \times \sum_{t=1}^n \frac{1}{(1+d)^t} = A_0 \times \frac{(1+d)^n - 1}{d(1+d)^n} \quad (1)$$

Where “d” is the discount rate and “t” is the lifetime period. The discount rate was assumed to be equal to 5%, according to the study of Rathore et al. (2022), and the period considered was 25 years.

To consider the Net Present Value for the NF or RO plant, the equation (2) was applied, according to Feng, Song, and Mo (2021):

$$NPV = Capital\ cost + \sum_{t=1}^n \frac{O_t + E_t + M_t}{(1+d)^t} \quad (2)$$

Where O_t is the operational costs, which includes the reagents and the membrane replacement costs, E_t energy costs, and M_t is the maintenance cost, taken as the 10% of the total operational costs (Fatone, 2020).

2.6.3 LCA of plasma technology

The assessment is conducted in accordance with the ISO 14040 series of standards on LCA. The four phases of the LCA process are (1) Goal and scope definition; (2) Life cycle inventory; (3) Impact assessment; and (4) Interpretation. Phases 1, 2 and 4 do not necessitate the utilisation of specialised tools and are relatively straightforward to execute, provided that the requirements stipulated in the ISO 14040 series of standards are adhered to. The third phase, however, poses a significant challenge due to its reliance on the richness of the available database for the requisite calculations, a process that demands the use of specialised software. In this study, the third phase is carried out utilising two software and database applications:

- A. Software: Umberto LCA software
Data base: Ecoinvent
- B. Software: OpenLCA 2.2.0 (EN 15804 +A2 Method; EF 3.0 normalisation and weighting set)
Data base: ELCD (European reference Life Cycle Database of the Joint Research Center, version 3.2 from October 2015)

The LCA was conducted on the plasma treatment technology employed to reduce the PFAS content in the leachate from the Sofia landfill. The goal of the study was twofold:

- to evaluate the environmental impact of the application of the plasma technology for the treatment of PFAS in LL; and
- to assess the relative performance of two alternatives using plasma treatment, and to compare them with a technology, that has been successfully used for large scale PFAS destruction, involving evaporation of the main flow and off-site incineration of the remaining sludge/salts.

Three scenarios were compared:

Scenario 1: Plasma treatment of the entire main concentrate

This scenario entails the utilisation of plasma treatment on the complete main concentrate of the main single stage RO unit. The concentrate flow rate is lower than that of the landfill leachate flow, but the concentration is higher, making this flow a more economically viable option than installing the plasma treatment in the main LL flow.

Scenario 2: Second stage RO unit added to reduce the concentrate volume and increase PFAS concentration + plasma treatment

This scenario represents an enhancement over Scenario 1, with a more concentrated concentrate. The installation of an additional RO unit prior to the plasma reactor is intended to reduce the flow rate and increase the concentration of PFAS in comparison to Scenario 1.

Scenario 3: Second stage RO unit added to reduce the concentrate volume, followed by an evaporation installation, after which the sludge/salts are transported for incineration off-site

This scenario is analogous to Scenario 2, with the exception that plasma treatment is not included. Instead, the implementation of an evaporation unit is proposed to facilitate the separation of the liquid from the solid phase. The liquid fraction (distillate) is then returned to the permeate water, while the solid residue (sludge/salts) is transported to an incineration facility off-site. PFAS removal occurs outside the system boundaries in this particular case, since there is no available on-site incineration unit. It should be noted that, in this particular case, the environmental impact of incineration is not encountered; however, there will be impacts arising from transportation. The boundaries of these 3 scenarios are provided in Figure 20.

A. Scenario 1

B. Scenario 2

C. Scenario 3

Figure 20: LCA boundaries of 3 scenarios.

3 Results and discussion

3.1 NF/RO pilot plant operation and PFAS removal

The NF/RO pilot plant was operated under the following conditions: daily flow of 5 m³ of LLTP effluent to the pilot, NF pressure of around 20 bars, RO pressure of around 50 bars, and filtration with no recirculation operations of the concentrate and with a recycle of concentrate (50% of influent flowrate) to stress the membrane and minimize the concentrate production.

Table 9 shows the operational conditions of NF/RO pilot plant and obtained data on energy consumption and water recovery. As expected, operation of the plant with concentrate recirculation was able to significantly increase the permeate production.

Table 9: NF/RO pilot plant operation parameters

Parameters	No Recirculation		50% Recycle	
	NF	RO	NF	RO
Influent (m ³ /d)	5	5	5	5
Permeate Flow (m ³ /d)	1.7	1.2	2.8	2.1
Concentrate Flow (m ³ /d)	3.3	3.8	2.2	2.9
Recovery (%)	34%	24%	56%	42%
Energy Consumption (kWh/permeate)	5.1	7.0	8.4	12.2

Washing the membrane with permeate water was done every 40 minutes of operation to keep the production of permeate constant. However, after several days and running cycles, the fouling of the membrane increased, and the normal washing with permeate water was insufficient to clean the membrane. Chemical washing was therefore used when either nominal permeate flow rate fell by 10%, nominal salinity of permeate increased by 10%, or the differential pressure between the supply and the concentrate increased by 15%.

As an example, in Figure 21, the change in differential pressure during NF filtration, which is an indicator of need for chemical washing of the membrane, can be seen. The increase of differential pressure was higher during operation with concentrate recirculation. Therefore, more frequent chemical washings are needed when the membrane is stressed with recirculation.

Figure 21: Changes of differential pressure (ΔP in bar) during NF operation

Several water quality parameters of the collected samples from both systems (i.e.; NF and RO filtration systems) were measured, including chemical oxygen demand (COD), total kjeldahl nitrogen (TKN), pH, total dissolved solids (TDS), and conductivity. The range of these values are provided in Table 10. These analyses were done at UNIVPM laboratories and in the field using portable kits.

Removal of COD and total dissolved solid (TDS) was higher in the RO system, whereas similar concentration of ammonia (i.e., TKN) was observed in both the permeates.

Table 10: Typical quality parameters of landfill leachate before and after NF/RO treatment

	COD (mg/L)	TKN (mg/L)	pH	TDS (mg/L)	Cond. ($\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$)
Pilot Influent	1508	56.2	6.7	5116	7227.3
	± 726	± 23.9	± 1.0	± 611	± 870
NF Permeate	242	1.5	6.7	3413	4810
	± 73	± 2.5	± 1.1	± 583	± 828
NF Concentrate	2682	91.9	6.1	6091	8599
	± 1115	± 2.6	± 1.2	± 795	± 1143
RO Permeate	5	0.5	6.2	28	51
	± 5	± 0.6	± 1.5	± 15	± 47
RO Concentrate	3580	129.6	6.4	7445	10651
	± 1577	± 17.6	± 1.0	± 1105	± 1632

Collected samples were also sent to ACEA Infrastructure for PFAS analysis. Table 11 and Table 12 show the concentration of different PFAS in the influent and permeate for both the filtration systems, presenting good removal of PFAS for NF system and a complete removal of PFAS for RO system. PFAS were not detected in any RO sample with LOQ of 20 ng/l. The rejection rate of NF system for PFAS is illustrated in Figure 22.

Table 11: PFAS concentrations observed in the influent and permeate of NF

PFAS (ng/L)	NF Influent				NF Permeate			
	Min	Average	Max	No. Of observations	Min	Average	Max	No. Of observations
PFBA	<100	944	1200	16 Out Of 18	30	133	350	18 Out Of 18
PFBS	2800	4006	5600	18 Out Of 18	200	635	1530	18 Out Of 18
PFHpA	<100	233	500	12 Out Of 18	<20	28	60	5 Out Of 18
PFHxA	900	1333	1900	18 Out Of 18	20	123	360	18 Out Of 18
PFOA	<100	1850	5300	16 Out Of 18	20	63	130	17 Out Of 18
PFPeA	<100	646	900	13 Out Of 18	20	82	190	18 Out Of 18
PFHxS	<1000	<1000	<1000	0 Out Of 18	<20	-	20	01 Out Of 18

Table 12: PFAS concentrations observed in the influent and permeate of RO

PFAS (ng/L)	RO Influent				RO Permeate			
	Min	Average	Max	No. Of observations	Min	Average	Max	No. Of observations
PFBA	900	1600	2600	18 Out Of 18	<20	<20	<20	0 Out Of 18
PFBS	3800	6344	10600	18 Out Of 18	<20	<20	<20	0 Out Of 18
PFHpA	<100	377	600	13 Out Of 18	<20	<20	<20	0 Out Of 18
PFHxA	1200	2261	3300	18 Out Of 18	<20	<20	<20	0 Out Of 18
PFOA	<100	3725	10200	16 Out Of 18	<20	<20	<20	0 Out Of 18
PFPeA	<100	1088	1600	17 Out Of 18	<20	<20	<20	0 Out Of 18

Figure 22: Observed PFAS removal during NF operation

3.2 PFAS removal and fate during pyrolysis treatment

As mentioned previously, the pyrolysis reactor had two main feed sources: LLTP sludge and NF/RO concentrate (as a catalyst salt). Both matrices were dried and evaporated before entering the pyrolysis reactor. The drying of the sludge was done at low temperature of 70°C to prevent any possible volatilisation of PFAS (Figure 23). On the other hand, NF/RO concentrate was evaporated in an industrial evaporator with temperature around 140°C, and the produced condensate was collected to check for any volatilised PFAS. The PFAS concentrations in the materials used for pyrolysis experiments were analysed by ACEA Infrastructure, and the results are presented in Table 13.

Figure 23: Dried sludge and concentrated salts used to feed the pyrolysis reactor

Table 13: PFAS concentrations detected in RO concentrate, condensed water after evaporation, concentrated dry salts, sludge from landfill leachate treatment

PFAS	RO Concentrate (ng/L)	Condensate after evaporation (ng/l)	Concentrate Salts (ng/kg)	Sludge from landfill leachate treatment (ng/kg)
N-EtFOSAA	< LOQ	< LOQ	< LOQ	2000 – 5000
N-MeFOSAA	< LOQ	< LOQ	< LOQ	1000 – 5000
6:2 FTS	< LOQ	< LOQ	< LOQ - 2000	< LOQ
PFBA	1800.0 - 2900	<LOQ - 20	43000 - 64000	< LOQ – 2000
PFBS	6100 - 10800	<LOQ - 50	228000 - 301000	5000
PFDA	< LOQ	< LOQ	< LOQ	2000 – 3000
PFHpA	500.0	<LOQ - 30	4000 - 11000	< LOQ - 1000
PFHxA	2700.0 - 3800	<LOQ - 50	51000 - 92000	2000 – 3000
PFHxS	< LOQ	< LOQ	2000	< LOQ - 1000
PFOA	1100.0 - 1200	30 - 120	3000 - 8000	7000 – 20000
PFPeA	1400.0 - 1800	< LOQ	34000 - 41000	7000
PFPeS	< LOQ	< LOQ	1000	< LOQ – 3000

After preparing the matrices, the operating parameters of the pyrolysis system were selected:

- Operating Temperature: 400 °C to 600 °C
- Residence Time: 20 min to 60 min
- Different percentages of mixed RO dried concentrate (from 0 to 25-30%) and LLTP Sludge (70% – 100%).

Figure 24 shows a simplified schematic of the pyrolysis reactor with the feed and products specifications. Based on the aforementioned parameters, the experiments resulted in 3 products (i.e.; biochar, bio-oil, and syngas) (Figure 25).

Figure 24: Schematic with range of measured PFAS concentrations in pyrolysis products under the different tested conditions

Syngas

Char

Bio-oil

Figure 25: Images of obtained pyrolysis products: char, bio-oil, syngas

The biochar and bio-oil were characterised for PFAS, heavy metals, dioxins, and furans. The syngas was characterised for different gases percentages and for PFAS. The different gases percentages were analysed by a direct gas analyser and the effluent syngas had around 12% methane, considering that nitrogen gas was introduced into the system to keep anaerobic conditions during operation. To better control the process and check the syngas production, a differential pressure meter with online data acquisition and recording was mounted on the reactor (Figure 26).

Figure 26: Pyrolysis reactor equipped with gauges for pressure and gas flow measurements and device for syngas characterization

Table 14 presents the results of PFAS measurements done at ACEA Infrastructure for both bio-oil and biochar at different feed, different temperature, and different residence time related to pyrolysis reactor operation. Stack emissions samples are presented in Figure 27. It is visible clearly from the results that the removal of PFAS increases with increasing temperature, and this in line with the understanding of PFAS bonds and the energy required to destroy these bonds. It is also noticeable that the higher the temperature, the higher the reduction in weight for the organic part of the feed.

Due to the time needed for the samples to reach the heated zone at the selected temperature, there was a temperature gradient affecting the feed and this gradient prolonged with higher retention times. This fact also impacted PFAS removal in the solid part, with lower removal with high retention time. It is noticeable that when there was no RO concentrate added, the retention time had no visible effect on PFAS concentration, and those compounds were completely removed in all cases due to lower PFAS concentration in comparison to the cases when RO concentrate was added.

The most complicated product for PFAS analysis was the syngas, and two types of analysis were done on it: direct collection using gas bags, as well as OTM-45, as explained previously. No PFAS were detected in the direct measurement, and the very low concentrations of PFAS were detected in the stack emission collection system as presented in Figure 28. Particularly, PFHxA was detected in the impinger water placed soon after the first trap with XAD-2 resin.

Table 14: PFAS concentrations in biochar and bio-oil after pyrolysis treatment and weight percentage of pyrolysis products compared to the feed

Test Specifications							PFAS in Bio-Oil (ng/L) With LOQ as:						PFAS in BioChar (ng/kg) With LOQ as:						
							100	1'000	100	1'000	1'000	100	1'000	1'000	1'000	1'000	1'000	1'000	1'000
Sludge (g)	Dry Concentrate (g)	Temperature (°C)	Reten. Time (min)	Biochar (%)	Bio-Oil (%)	Syngas (%)	FOSA	6:2 FTS	PFHpA	PFDA	PFNA	PFOA	PFBA	PFBS	PFHxA	PFHxS	PFOA	PFOS	PFPeA
300	0	600	20	52%	14%	34%	<	<	<	<	<	<	<	<	<	<	<	<	<
300	0	600	40	53%	15%	31%	<	<	<	<	<	<	<	<	<	<	<	<	<
300	0	600	60	56%	11%	33%	<	<	<	<	<	<	<	<	<	<	<	<	<
300	0	400	60	79%	4%	18%	<	<	<	<	<	<	2000	8000	<	2000	<	9000	<
300	90	600	20	58%	9%	33%	<	<	<	<	<	<	<	<	<	<	<	<	<
300	90	600	40	70%	8%	22%	<	<	<	<	<	<	1000	4000	<	<	<	<	<
300	90	600	60	63%	12%	26%	<	<	<	<	<	200	2000	14000	4000	<	1000	<	2000
300	90	400	60	76%	5%	19%	3000	<	<	<	<	1000	1000	59000	3000	<	1000	3000	<
300	60	600	40	59%	7%	34%	<	<	<	<	<	<	<	2000	1000	<	1000	1000	<
300	60	400	60	74%	7%	19%	2000	<	<	<	<	<	1000	35000	1000	<	1000	2000	<
300	30	600	40	63%	10%	27%	<	<	<	<	<	<	<	<	<	<	<	<	<
300	30	400	40	73%	13%	15%	<	<	100	<	<	100	<	<	<	<	<	<	<
300	0	600	20	56%	9%	35%	<	<	<	<	<	100	<	<	<	<	<	<	<
900	0	600	20	62%	11%	27%	<	200	<	200	100	<	<	<	<	<	<	<	<
700	0	600	20	64%	12%	23%	<	<	<	<	<	100	<	<	<	<	<	<	<
900	90	600	20	65%	8%	27%	<	<	<	<	<	<	<	<	<	<	<	<	<

Figure 27: Samples collected from stack emission sampling system for PFAS determination

PFAS in Stack Emissions With LOQ = 100 ng/l		*PFHxA 100 ng/l Washing 1
Test	Detected PFAS	*PFHxA 100 ng/l Sample 4
1	None	
2*	PFHxA	
3**	PFHxA	**PFHxA 100 ng/l Sample 4

Figure 28: Syngas Stack Emission Collection system samples collection and analysis results

Heavy metals were measured in biochar and bio-oil samples (Table 15). Significant concentrations of heavy metals were found in the biochar. On the other hand, in the bio-oil samples, the concentration of metals was always very low. The most representative metals in bio-oil were silicon (1415-1790 mg/kg), sodium (594-669 mg/kg) and boron (179-224 mg/kg), which are the most volatile metals. Overall, pyrolysis tends to concentrate heavy metals in the solid products, and they cannot be eliminated. Heavy metals occurrence seems to be the main limitation for valorisation of char in agriculture if sludges impacted by heavy metals are treated by pyrolysis.

Table 15: Heavy metals detected in the bio-oil and biochar after pyrolysis treatment

Heavy metal	Bio-oil (mg/kg)			Biochar (mg/kg)		
	Min	Max	Average	Min	Max	Average
Aluminum	154	194	182	12970	21110	16650
Antimony	0.4	0.9	0.6	4.8	7.7	6
Silver	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	2.1	3.2	2.7
Arsenic	1.4	3.3	2.15	3.8	6.9	5.2
Barium	0.2	0.28	0.3	471	1080	770.3
Beryllium	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	0.4	0.7	0.5
Boron	179	224	210	205	339	280.5
Cadmium	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	1.1	1.9	1.6
Calcium	<40	<40	<40	69260	113700	98020
Cobalt	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	4.9	8.2	7.0
Chromium	0.1	0.8	0.4	165	379	281.3
Iron	3.8	7.6	5.3	9380	14700	12270
Phosphorus	10	10	10	14110	21780	18615
Magnesium	8.3	10.6	8.9	9502.0	15530.0	12473.3
Manganese	<1	<1	<1	252	408	338.8
Molybdenum	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	11	16.6	14.2
Nickel	1.7	4	2.85	35.2	57.3	49.5
Lead	0.44	0.51	0.5	58.5	108	87.5
Potassium	180	210	197.5	8420	22180	16525
Copper	6.94	23.6	15.27	314	582	471.3
Silicon	1415	1822	1685.5	2254	4650	3868.5
Sodium	594.8	669.1	635.7	9390	41680	25605
Tin	0.3	0.4	0.35	54.7	104	79.15
Tellurium	<1	<1	<1	1.4	3.4	2.2
Vanadium	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	33.4	62.8	47.4
Zinc	2	22	14.7	1140	1890	1500
Mercury	<0.010	<0.010	<0.010	<0.2	0.9	0.6

Dioxins and furans were also measured in biochar and bio-oil. While not detected in biochar samples, values between 1.1-15.3 ng/Kg were measured in the bio-oil samples (Table 16).

Table 16: Dioxins and furans detected in the bio-oil and biochar after pyrolysis treatment

Furanes and dioxines	Bio-oil (ng/kg)			Biochar (ng/kg)
	Min	Max	Average	
2,3,4,7,8-PCDFs	0.5	6.7	2.6	<1
2,3,7,8-TCDD	0.3	0.3	0.3	<1
2,3,7,8-TCDFs	0.3	15.8	6.8	<1
1,2,3,7,8-PCDD	0.5	16.6	6.8	<1
1,2,3,6,7,8-HxCDFs	0.5	0.5	0.5	<1
1,2,3,7,8-PCDFs	0.5	0.5	0.5	<1
2,3,4,6,7,8-HxCDFs	0.5	0.5	0.5	<1
1,2,3,7,8,9-HxCDFs	0.5	0.5	0.5	<1
1,2,3,4,7,8-HxCDD	0.5	0.5	0.5	<1
1,2,3,6,7,8-HxCDD	0.5	14.0	3.9	<1
1,2,3,7,8,9-HxCDD	0.5	0.5	0.5	<1
1,2,3,4,7,8-HxCDFs	0.5	0.5	0.5	<1
1,2,3,4,6,7,8-HpCDD	0.5	56.3	33.2	<1
1,2,3,4,7,8,9-HpCDFs	0.5	0.5	0.5	<1
1,2,3,4,6,7,8-HpCDFs	0.5	0.5	0.5	<1
OCDD	2.5	91.4	33.8	<1
OCDFs	2.5	2.5	2.5	<1
Σ PCDD, PCDF (ng/kg) in TEF	1.2	15.3	6.4	<1

Table 17 displays reassumed possible valorisation scenarios for pyrolysis products according to results obtained in this study.

Table 17: Possible valorisation and disposal scenarios for products of co-pyrolysis treatment

Pyrolysis product	Biochar	Bio-oil	Syngas
Valorisation/disposal	<p>Disposal in landfill</p> <p>PFAS are removed under optimal treatment conditions. Dioxins and furans were not detected. However, high concentration of heavy metals was found. Valorisation opportunity of char in agriculture can be hypothesized for municipal sludge not impacted by heavy metals. Use of char as waste fuel can be tested due to its residual carbon content.</p>	<p><i>Thermal energy production</i></p>	<p><i>Thermal energy production</i></p>

3.3 Assessment of leachate complex acute toxicity

3.3.1 Characterization of leachate from Sofia LLTP

The general characteristics of leachate from Sofia are presented in Table 18. The leachate used in experiments for assessment of toxicity has a high organic content as COD (more than 5500 mgO₂/L) but a low share of biodegradable organics (below 10%) – BOD₅ is 330 mgO₂/L. The nitrogen is also high, especially ammonium.

Table 18: Main parameters of crude leachate

Crude leachate	mean ± stdev
Dissolved oxygen (mg/L)	2.52 ± 0.55
Temperature (°C)	11.4 ± 1.1
pH	8.49 ± 0.03
Conductivity (mS/cm ¹)	19.36 ± 1.1
COD (mgO ₂ /L)	5755 ± 357
BOD ₅ (mgO ₂ /L)	329 ± 1
P (total) (mg/L)	8.76 ± 0.7
N (total) (mg/L)	1330 ± 70
NH ₄ – N (mg/L)	982 ± 98
NO ₃ – N (mg/L)	54 ± 11.4
NO ₂ – N (mg/L)	0.8 ± 0.6
Chlorides (mg/L)	3222 ± 207
SO ₄ (mg/L)	500 ± 40
Insoluble suspended solids (mg/L)	135 ± 7
Soluble suspended solids (mg/L)	13137 ± 817

The toxicity of leachate was assessed by fluorescent methods – staining with CTC and DAPI dyes with digital image post-processing. The two test bacterial cultures *E. coli* ATCC 700728 and *Ps. aureofaciens* AP-9 were used for these experiments. The changes in the complex toxicity of the samples were assessed by two indicators of the test bacterial culture: (1) the share of viable cells; and (2) the intensity of bacterial fluorescence as a measurement of metabolic activity.

3.3.2 Assessment of leachate complex toxicity

Assessment after different stages of treatment in the plant

The leachate with an average composition indicated in the table above was studied to assess its complex toxicity. As can be seen from the composition, the high COD, which is not associated with a high biodegradable fraction (very low BOD₅), suggests the presence of various difficult-to-degrade organic compounds with probable high toxicity. Therefore, the studied toxicity is a complex indicator that combines the toxicity of all hazardous components in the crude leachate. The toxicity was also studied on leachates that have undergone various stages of treatment by inhibition of metabolic activity of test bacteria, and the results are shown in Figure 29. The fluorescent images are presented in Figure 30.

Figure 29: Share of viable cells and fluorescence intensity of test bacterial culture in the presence of crude leachate (LL), water after biological treatment (LLb), and effluent at the exit of treatment (Eff). *Control is the bacterial culture in nutrient media only; **The sampling points are presented in Fig. 5, section 1.1.2 and are respectively marked with number 1 (for LL), 6 (for LLb) and 8 (for Eff) in the figure

Figure 30: Fluorescent images of test bacteria after different stages of treatment (pink – CTC staining of metabolic active cells; blue – DAPI staining of all cells)

The results show that the share of active cells decreases by more than 400 times in the presence of leachate, and the complex non-specific toxicity is very high. The toxicity of the samples decreased in the different stages of the treatment, with the percentage of viable test bacteria increasing up to 15% in the effluent. The metabolic activity of *P. aureofaciens* AP9 was lowest in the presence of leachate due to the high concentration of toxic compounds.

Assessment of leachate toxicity after dilution

The toxicity of leachate was measured at different dilutions. The used test bacteria strain was *E. coli* ATCC 700728. The additional parameter “circularity of cells” was included in the assessment (Figure 31). The changes in the cell morphology are an important indicator of the degree of intoxication in bacteria, in the range of lower-than-lethal concentrations of substances. The results show the high toxicity of crude leachate and a significant reduction of toxicity after 100 times dilution. All studied parameters increased their values at dilution. An interesting result is found at a 50-fold dilution - the toxicity of the sample is higher than at a 10-fold dilution, and the tested indicators have lower values. The differences are not statistically significant, but are noted in the figures and require more in-depth future research.

Our assumption is that at this dilution the balance between water-soluble and water-insoluble toxic compounds is altered. Most of the toxic compounds dissolve and become bioavailable and bio-damaging to the cells of the test microorganism. For this reason, the viable cells that emit a fluorescent signal are fewer. Other indicators of viable cells also support this assumption.

Figure 31: Share of viable cells, circularity and fluorescence intensity of test bacterial culture in the presence of leachate and diluted leachate

3.3.3 Impaired biological activity of sludge

The activity of sludge treating leachate was assessed to determine the degree of damage to its structure and functions. The comparison was made with activated sludge (AS) from a conventional treatment plant treating municipal wastewater (Figure 32). The orange fluorescence signal presents the metabolic active cells in the sample, and it is more intensive for activated sludge from municipal WWTP. Fluorescence images confirm the low metabolic activity of the sludge treating the leachate. The digital image analyses of samples of municipal activated sludge in the presence of leachate were also performed. Activated sludge without the presence of leachate has a high metabolic activity - fluorescence intensity of 138 and a share of viable, metabolic active cells of 63%. In the presence of crude leachate, its activity is strongly inhibited - fluorescence intensity of 58 and share of viable, metabolic active cells of 10%. The leachate after biological treatment and effluent has lower toxicity (Figure 33).

Figure 32: Metabolic activity of activated sludge, assessed by fluorescence signals: a) activated sludge, treated landfill leachate and b) activated sludge from the municipal WWTP of Sofia city. Magnification 1000x

Figure 33: Share of viable cells and fluorescence intensity of activated sludge (AS) from municipal WWTP in the presence of crude leachate, leachate after the biological stage, and effluent

3.3.4 Enzyme activities as indicators of impaired biological activity

Enzyme activities were studied as additional indicators - the aim is to confirm or reject the results obtained for the toxic effect of leachate on activated sludge according to fluorescent methods. Two types of enzymological indicators were studied: specific enzyme activities involved in the detoxification processes of pollutants in activated sludge and enzyme activities, and indicators of general metabolic pathways. In activated sludge metabolizing high concentrations of difficult-to-degrade pollutants (activated sludge from LLTP), there is a diversification of peripheral metabolic pathways through activation of more dioxygenases, but with lower activities and strong inhibition of enzyme activities from central metabolic pathways.

3.3.5 Assessment of leachate toxicity after plasma treatment

Microwave plasma source

The effect of plasma treatment of LL with different devices and modes was assessed on test bacteria *E. coli* by fluorescent indicators. The different input power of the microwave plasma source in continuous mode of treatment was used. An increase in the share of the active bacterial cells is clearly registered when increasing the input power in the range of 50 W – 100 W (Kirilova et al., submitted).

Eighty-one percent of the bacteria are active when harmful substances are not present. This share drops to only 0.6 % when placing them in an environment with leachate (Table 19). There was no effect from treating the leachate with a 50 W plasma source, and the active bacteria remained relatively constant. When the input power is increased to 75 W, the number of active cells stays very low, but their proportion of all cells slightly increases. With an additional increase in the microwave source's input power to 100 W, the percentage of living cells increased to nearly 2 %. Although the treatment's impact was minimal (the metabolically active microorganisms were 81 % in the glucose control), the data show that the plasma treatment may be able to reduce the toxicity of xenobiotic-polluted leachate.

Table 19: Share of metabolically active cells and fluorescence intensity of *E. coli* - control (bacterial cells in glucose), leachate, and treated leachates with 50, 75 and 100 W input power of microwave plasma

Sample	Share of active cells (%)	Fluorescence intensity
Control (in glucose)	81	250
Crude leachate	0.6	150
Leachate, treated with 50 W plasma	0.6	170
Leachate, treated with 75 W plasma	1	188
Leachate, treated with 100 W plasma	2	90

At the maximum applied input power during plasma treatment, a notable reduction in the test microorganism's metabolic activity (assessed by indicator “fluorescence intensity”) was observed, two times that of the other leachate samples. Higher survival is probably the cause of this; more microorganisms are active in the extremely toxic environment, but their metabolic activity is lower even though they have survived. This effect is probably caused in part by the plasma's destructive action, which produces a large number of oxidizing particles, and some of them remain active for a long time, even though the samples were treated first and then incubated with the test bacteria. The examination of the sample cell sizes lends credence to this theory.

In order to thoroughly investigate the effects described, an environment with a pollutant concentration below the one that inhibited the test microorganisms had to be created. As a result, a number of samples with lower levels of pollutants were created by dilutions of 5X, 10X, 50X, and 100X. To maximize the impact of the plasma treatment, the wastewater was treated in continuous flow mode not only once but also three and five times. The experimental set-up is presented in Table 5, series (1) and a flow diagram of the experimental set up is shown in Figure 34.

At dilutions up to ten times, the percentage of active microorganisms in the samples stays extremely low (Figure 35, bottom graph). The results of the triplicate treatments are similar to those of the quintuple and are not shown separately in the figures. This is an example of how the pollutants in the leachate have a major inhibitory effect. In the samples that were not exposed to plasma, this effect only became noticeable at a 100-fold dilution. When treated with plasma, the the positive effect of plasma on metabolic activity of the test microorganism is detected at a lower dilution (50 times). The single plasma treatment yields the highest average value of active bacteria, and the average number of live microorganisms for fluorescence imaging is more than twice as high as all other variants. At the lowest dilution, the fluorescence intensity for the variant without plasma treatment was 47 % of the maximum, and at 100X dilution, it reached 77 %. The test microorganism appears to have a reduced intensity of life processes as a result of the plasma-treated wastewater. In other words, more bacteria survive in the presence plasma-treated leachate, but their metabolic activity is reduced, most likely due to the interaction between the plasma and the pollutants in the leachate.

Figure 34: Flow diagram of experimental set up.

Figure 35: Fluorescence intensity (top graph) and share of metabolically active cells (bottom graph) of leachate diluted 1, 5, 10, 50 and 100-fold and treated at continuous flow mode one and five times

Changes in cell morphology are a key indicator of the level of intoxication in bacteria, especially in the range of lower than lethal concentrations of substances. According to the obtained results, this indicator decreases with single and five treatments as well as with more concentrated leachate, which is linked to an elongation of the cell shape. On average, the single-treatment variant of these microorganisms had a 25 % larger perimeter, while the triple-treatment variant had an 18 % larger one. Cell perimeter data, however, were significantly lower for the single plasma treatment variant (58 %) and the fivefold treatment variant (four times lower) than for the microorganisms with glucose in the medium. This is an obvious sign that the microorganisms in the landfill leachate are seriously intoxicated (Kirilova et al., submitted).

3.4 Toxicity reduction of PFAS model solutions after plasma treatment

3.4.1 Assessment of leachate toxicity after plasma treatment

At high concentrations of PFOA

For experiments in controlled conditions, a representative of PFAS (PFOA) was initially selected as a model compound from the PFAS group for the creation of the methods and their validation. With this compound, the method for fluorescence assessment of the biological activity of the test microorganism *Escherichia coli* was introduced in cleaner conditions (saline solution spiked with different concentrations PFOA). The following analyses were performed:

1. Monitoring the reduced biological activity of the test microorganism with increasing PFOA concentration. The concentrations used are 2.5, 5.0, and 10 mg/L. It should be noted that these are much higher concentrations compared to those found in the environment. By studying these high concentrations, two goals are pursued. First, to obtain information about the intoxication processes during the accumulation of PFOA in various resources –sludge, and living organisms, and second, when treating with plasma solutions of PFOA and other PFAS, toxins are eliminated to a greater extent at higher concentrations.
2. The relationship between PFOA concentration and toxicity reduction after plasma treatment was investigated.

In both cases, mathematical relationships that predict the intoxication and detoxification effect of PFOA and the treatment of PFOA solutions with plasma were derived. The following plasma treatments were studied: Flow plasma treatment with microwave torch and Dielectric Barrier Discharge (DBD) treatment. Figure Figure 36 indicates the working hypothesis of this series of experiments.

Figure 36: Working hypothesis

Figure 37: Fluorescence signals of Control /Escherichia coli ATCC 700728 under action of PFOA /10 mg/L and of samples treated with Flow Plasma and DBD. The strong pink color indicates the decrease of toxicity and the increase of the number of metabolic active cells: : 1/ control 10 mg/L PFOA; 2/ Flow plasma treatment – 10 mg/L PFOA; 3/ DBD plasma treatment – 10 mg/L PFOA

Dependence of intoxication parameters on PFOA concentration

The decrease in biological activity of the test indicator microorganism was observed with increasing PFOA concentration. The parameters of biological activity were monitored using fluorescent techniques - glow intensity, cell perimeter, cell roundness, and % physiologically active cells.

The obtained results show that intensity, mean perimeter, and % of metabolically active cells depend inversely on PFOA concentration with high confidence. Cell circularity is directly proportional to PFOA concentration with high confidence. These dependencies can be used to assess the toxicity of PFOA. These conclusions are confirmed by the following SEM images: Figure 38 and Figure 39 show that the roundness of the cells and the reduction of their perimeter after 1 hour of exposure to 10 mg/L PFOA.

Figure 38: Control cell Escherichia coli 18 hour culture in saline solution (1) and Sample 1- cell Escherichia coli 18 hour culture in saline solution with 10 mg/L PFOA – 60 min exposition (2)

Figure 39: Control cell *Escherichia coli* 18 hour culture in saline solution /1/ and Sample 1- cell *Escherichia coli* 18 hour culture in saline solution with 10 mg/L PFOA – 60 min exposition/2/

Cell Parameters of Intoxication after Flow Plasma Treatment of Saline Solution with increased PFOA concentration

Changes in the same parameters after treating the solutions with different concentrations of PFOA with a plasma source – flow treatment with plasma with a power of 100 W - was studied. The aim is to trace how the plasma source affects the toxicity and what is the relationship between the concentrations of PFOA and the plasma effect.

The results showed that flow plasma-treated PFOA solutions with increasing concentrations decreased their toxicity towards the test microorganism. The dependence between toxicity parameters/intensity, cell perimeter, circularity, % area, and % metabolically active cells is changed from directly proportional to polynomial. The most reliable are the **relationships between intensity, roundness, and % metabolically active cells**. Underflow plasma treatment conditions, these parameters (intensity, cell perimeter, circularity, % area, and % metabolically active cells) are suitable for measuring toxicity.

Cell Parameters of Intoxication after DBD Plasma Treatment of Saline Solution with increased PFOA concentration

The results showed that DBD-treated plasma solutions of PFOA with increasing concentrations changed their toxicity towards the test microorganism (Figure 40 and Figure 41). The dependence between toxicity parameters /intensity, cell perimeter, circularity, % area, and % metabolically active cells is changed to polynomial. The greatest credibility is the relationships between intensity and toxicity. Under conditions of DBD treatment, this parameter is most suitable for measuring toxicity. With significantly less reliability, the relationship between toxicity and % metabolically active cells and average perimeter can be used. The relationships (Table 20) allow us to predict the effects of different concentrations of PFOA on living systems, as well as to predict the degree of reduction in PFOA toxicity after exposure to plasma sources. To the extent that there are coefficients that allow

other PFAS to be equated with PFOA, the predictive results can be extended to other PFAS representatives. These results of toxicity are confirmed by SEM analysis at 20000X magnification in Figure 40 and Figure 41.

Table 20: Summarized dependences

Dependence	Without plasma treatment	Flow plasma treatment	DBD plasma treatment
Intensity/ concentration	$Y=25,32x+169,63$ $R^2=0,89$	$Y=8,841x^2-47,085x+181,83$ $R^2=0,98$	$Y=9,300x^2-41,927x+175,78$ $R^2=0,95$
Perimeter/ concentration	$Y=1,4105X+13,574$ $R^2=0,79$	$Y=1,230x^2-7,264x+18,058$ $R^2=0,66$	$Y=1,543x^2-8,032+18,663$ $R^2=0,74$
Circularity/ concentration	$Y=0,0295X+0,412$ $R^2=0,88$	$Y=-0,0403x^2+0,227+0.252$ $R^2=0,93$	$Y=-0,285x^2+0,149+0,323$ $R^2=0,59$
%Area/ concentration	$Y=0,0187X+0,2125$ $R^2=0,159$	$Y=5,925x^2-30,301x+47,455$ $R^2=0,75$	there is no reliable correlation
%cell number/ concentration	$Y=0,2261X+1,2352$ $R^2=0,75$	$Y=24,23x^2-134,56+224,38$ $R^2=0,97$	$Y=10,94x^2-63,088+163,93$ $R^2=0,70$

(1)

(2)

Figure 40: Effects of PFOA toxicity on Escherichia coli after treatment of the solution with flow plasma and with DBD at 20000X increase: (1) Sample 4- cell Escherichia coli 18-hour culture in saline solution with 10 mg/L PFOA – 60 min exposition, treated with with flow plasma source; (2) Sample 5- cell Escherichia coli 18-hour culture in saline solution with 10 mg/L PFOA – 60 min exposition, treated with DBD

Figure 41: Effects of PFOA toxicity on Escherichia coli after treatment of the solution with flow plasma and with DBD at 50000X increase: (1) Sample 4- cell Escherichia coli 18-hour culture in saline solution with 10 mg/L PFOA – 60 min exposition, treated with flow plasma source; (2) Sample 5- cell Escherichia coli 18-hour culture in saline solution with 10 mg/L PFOA – 60 min exposition, treated with DBD

A comparison of the % change in toxicity indicators was made during treatment with flowing plasma and DBD. The results obtained are shown in Figure 42 and Figure 43.

Figure 42: Changes in % cell indicators of decreased toxicity after treatment with plasma in flow mode. The control is distilled water enriched with PFOA and not treated by plasma. Its toxicity parameters are assumed to be 100 %.

Figure 43: Changes in % cell indicators of decreased toxicity after treatment with DBD plasma source. The control is distilled water enriched with PFOA and not treated by plasma. Its toxicity parameters are assumed to be 100 %.

Flow plasma and DBD reduce the toxicity of PFOA. The effect is greater at higher concentrations. DBD has a more drastic effect on PFOA but leaves in the solution more plasma components that damage more sensitively the morphological parameters of the test objects. This does not significantly affect cell metabolism.

More parameters can be used to assess toxicity in flow plasma treatment, while at DBD the appropriate parameters to assess toxicity are intensity and metabolically active cells. It is our opinion that these two parameters are most suitable for monitoring PFAS toxicity and complex toxicity. The derived linear and polynomial relationships can be used to predict the complex toxicity of the particular plasma treatment.

These results were obtained based on one model representative of PFAS – PFOA. Since there are derived coefficients equating the toxicity of PFOA to other PFAS compounds, the derived relationships can be used for other PFAS representatives.

Plasma treatment is a promising approach to reduce toxicity and complex toxicity, but the specific plasma source and gradations of treatment must be selected depending on the particularity of the technology. For pre-treatment of wastewater, flow-through treatment is more suitable, while for post-treatment and the presence of pathogenic bacteria, DBD treatment is more suitable.

At low concentrations of PFAS

Figure 44 presents results obtained also in experiments with model solutions, but at low concentrations of PFAS. PFOA and another new model pollutant PFDA were used. The concentrations tested were 100, 75 and 25 µg/L, and the solutions with 100 µg/L were treated with plasma to

monitor how the toxicity of the samples changed. Fluorescence intensity, number per image, and cell perimeter were again used as indicators in the fluorescence analyses. The test microorganism was *E. coli*. The plasma sources used for the treatment of samples were the beta-device and surfaguide. The notations used are presented in Table 21.

Table 21: Notations used for samples

1		SU_1_PFOA	sample with approx. 100 µg/L PFOA
2		SU_2_PFOA	sample with approx. 75 µg/L PFOA
3		SU_3_PFOA	sample with approx. 25 µg/L PFOA
4		SU_4_PFOA	sample with unknown concentration but lower than 100 µg/L PFOA, treated with surfaguide
5		SU_5_PFOA	sample with unknown concentration but lower than 100 µg/L PFOA, treated with β plasma source
6		SU_6_PFDA	sample with PFDA, approx. 12 µg PFOA-EQ/L
7		SU_7_PFDA	sample with PFDA, approx. 9 µg/L PFOA-EQ/L
8		SU_8_PFDA	sample with PFDA, approx. 3 µg/L PFOA-EQ/L
9		SU_9_PFDA	sample with unknown concentration PFDA but lower than 12 PFOA-EQ/L, treated with surfaguide
10		SU_10_PFDA	sample with unknown concentration PFDA but lower than 12 µg PFOA-EQ/L, treated with β plasma source

The intensity of fluorescence is lower at high concentrations of PFAS. The decrease in concentration of the model solution leads to an increase in this indicator of metabolic activity and this is more clearly for PFDA. The plasma treatment of the PFOA solution does not increase the metabolic activity of the test bacterial culture. The treatment of the PFDA solution (12 PFOA-EG/L) has a clear positive effect – intensity increases almost twice and thus in the range of the 3-9 µg/L PFOA-EQ/L solutions, especially with surfaguide (Figure 44). The perimeter of cells and the number per image confirm this.

Figure 44: Digital image analysis of CTC/DAPI stained *E. coli* cells in the presence of PFOA and PFDA in concentrations 100 $\mu\text{g/L}$ (1 and 6 respectively), 75 $\mu\text{g/L}$ (2 and 7), 25 $\mu\text{g/L}$ (3 and 8), treated with surfaguide (4 and 9) and with beta-device (5 and 10)

3.4.2 Toxicity reduction of leachates spiked with PFOA and treated with plasma

Treatment with microwave plasma torch at continuous flow and batch modes

To investigate the impact of plasma treatment on the toxicity of PFAS present in landfill leachate, PFOA was added to leachate samples. PFOA concentrations of 2.5 mg/L, 5 mg/L, and 10 mg/L were used. The plasma was treated in two ways: continuously flowing and in batch using a microwave plasma torch with an input power of 100 W. LC-MS analysis provided preliminary confirmation that there were no PFAS present in the landfill leachate.

The amount of active bacteria in landfill leachate samples decreased by 2.5 times, reaching 32% (Table 22). Comparing this percentage to earlier sections of the study, it is noticeably higher and the reason is the operation of the Sofia Waste treatment plant. Due to equipment damage, a mixed

untreated household waste was dumped in the landfill prior to the sampling, and the biodegradable portion was not separated. This reduced the samples' overall toxicity by increasing the BOD5 by two times, to 667 mg/L. After adding PFOA, the wastewater's intoxicating effect increased dramatically, as the share of active cells dropped from 32 % to values of 5.3 to 0,5 % .

Table 22: Share of active, viable cells and intensity of fluorescence as indicators of change in leachate toxicity of samples, spiked with 2.5, 5, and 10 mg/L and plasma treated at flow mode and batch mode

Sample	Share of viable cells, %	Fluorescence intensity
Control with glucose	81	254
Leachate, non-treated	32	192
Leachate + 2.5 mg/L PFOA	5.3	190
Leachate + 5 mg/L PFOA	4.1	167
Leachate + 10 mg/L PFOA	0.5	136
Treated leachate + 2.5 mg/L PFOA flow	38	200
Treated leachate + 5 mg/L PFOA flow	33	188
Treated leachate + 10 mg/L PFOA flow	45	170
Treated leachate + 2.5 mg/L PFOA batch	18	170
Treated leachate + 5 mg/L PFOA batch	20	155
Treated leachate + 10 mg/L PFOA batch	50	155

The highest concentration of PFOA in the leachate was associated with the lowest fluorescence intensity (136, or 53 % of the control). .

The share of active microorganisms and fluorescence intensity, which are indicators of toxicity, show that the variant with leachate and 10 mg/L PFOA is the most toxic. The average cell perimeter, another indicator, also makes this experimental variant stand out. Compared to the other variants with PFOA, the average size increased by 2 to 7 times in the presence of the high PFAS concentration, indicating the formation of filaments in the wastewater. The high level of intoxication is another factor contributing to this.

There is a noticeable reduction in toxicity when landfill leachate is plasma treated with additional PFOA. Two treatment modes—continuous flow and batch—were employed in the current study section. The percentage of active microorganisms increases from 0.5-5.3 % to 38-45 % for flow plasma treatment and to 18-50 % for batch plasma. The highest increased is seen at the highest PFOA concentration (10 mg/L). When PFOA concentrations are lower, a notable difference is seen between the two treatment modes. When comparing the variant with 2.5 mg/L PFOA to the variant without plasma treatment, a 9.7-fold difference is observed. In batch mode, this difference is 4.5 times. Similarly, at a higher concentration of PFOA (5 mg/L), differences are observed of 13.6 times in the continuous flow mode and 8.3 times in the batch mode.

In this particular experiment, the leachate samples had a lower complex toxicity caused by other toxic compounds, which was due to a technical malfunction in the landfill. However, this provides a good opportunity to track the contribution of the added PFOA to the toxicity and to what extent the plasma leads to a reduction of PFOA toxicity. The results clearly show that both types of treatments reduce the cumulative toxicity of the leachate with added PFOA, as compared to the untreated

samples, spiked with PFOA, the fluorescence intensity and the percentage of viable cells increase significantly. This is also found for the treatments in batch mode, but to a lesser extent.

Along with a rise in the share of active microorganisms, the test microorganisms also show increased metabolic activity, with the variant containing 10 mg/L PFOA showing the highest metabolic activity assessed by fluorescence intensity (average 21 %). The combination of the pollutants' increased bioavailability and decreased toxicity is most likely what causes the cells in this variant to become activated following plasma treatment.

The results obtained indicate that the water treated in this manner is also less toxic. At 2.5 mg/L PFOA, the percentage of active cells is 2.2 times higher than in batch mode, and at 5 mg/L PFOA, it is 64% higher. At the maximum PFOA concentration, the difference is negligible (14 %), favoring the batch mode of plasma treatment. However, notable alterations in cell morphology are noted in this variant. The samples microscopically reveal the formation of distinct zones of fluorescence within a single cell and numerous small zones of fluorescence outside the cells, despite the fact that the average size of the cells is very similar to that observed at lower PFOA concentrations.

3.4.3 Validation of fluorescence-based toxicity test by other methods

The newly developed fluorescent method was validated by two other methods – ATP (adenosine triphosphate) assay and PFAS-CALUX assay. The samples analysed were model solutions of PFOA and PFDA in low concentrations (100, 75, and 25 µg /L) for PFAS CALUX assay and PFOA in the same concentrations for the ATP assay. In addition to untreated PFAS solutions, samples treated with the beta-device and surfaguide were also examined.

Comparison with the results from ATP assay

Measuring the amount of ATP in a sample can yield accurate estimates of the number of living cells because ATP is a main metabolite of living cells and is rapidly lost in dead cells. This makes it possible to use the amount of ATP in the cell as an indicator parameter in toxicity tests when assessing the endpoint of cell death. ATP assay is based on the bioluminescent product that luciferase produces when it reacts with ATP. Light is released as a result of the enzyme reaction. When ATP standards are used for calibration, it is possible to determine the ATP content of the sample, which is directly proportional to the intensity of the detected light emission (Pavlova et al., 2024).

The results show a significant reduction of ATP content at concentrations of 100 and 75 µg /L (Figure 45). The treatment with different plasma sources reduces the toxicity of samples, especially the beta-device increases the content of ATP almost twice, i.e. more cells survive in these conditions.

Figure 45: Luminescence intensity of bacterial cells of *E. coli* in: saline (K1), nutrient media (K2), PFOA solutions of 100 $\mu\text{g/L}$, 75 and 25 $\mu\text{g/L}$, treated samples PFOA 100 $\mu\text{g/L}$ with surfaguide and β device

Comparison with the results from PFAS CALUX

PFAS are known to be able to interfere in thyroid hormone metabolism by e.g., disrupting the transport of the natural ligand thyroxine (T4) by a major transporter protein transthyretin (TTR). The PFAS CALUX[®] assay uses this important property to measure the effect of the range of PFAS compounds in chemical mixtures, independent of prior knowledge of their structure. The PFAS CALUX consists of a TTR binding assay in combination with the TRbeta CALUX bioassay. Disruption of TTR binding by T4 is benchmarked against the reference compound PFOA and expressed as PFOA equivalents/L sample processed (Behnisch et al., 2021). The analyses were conducted by BDS (BioDetection Systems). The results are shown in Table 23. The notations are the same as used in chapter 3.4.1.

For all samples except for SU_0_C (blank control from ultrapure water), the activity was above the activity found in the procedure blank. Furthermore, the PFAS activity in all samples highly exceeded the EBT (evidence-based toxicology) derived for drinking water (DW) and surface water (SW). The blank sample did not exceed EBT values. Treatment of PFAO-spiked solution with the 100 $\mu\text{g/L}$ PFOA, treated with surfaguide plasma source reduced toxicity by about factor 2, but the remaining toxicity still was higher compared to the untreated solution with 75 $\mu\text{g/L}$ PFOA. The β plasma source had no effect for the PFOA spiked solution. For PFDA spiking solution (12 $\mu\text{g/L}$ PFOA-EQ), both plasma sources resulted in a decrease of toxicity. For both plasma sources the remaining toxicity was above the solution spiking with 9 $\mu\text{g/L}$ PFOA-EQ.

Although there is no explanation for why the PFAS-CALUX results are so high, data demonstrate a significant reduction in the toxicity of the samples after treatment with both plasma sources (compare the values of BEQ (bioanalytical equivalent) for samples SU-4 and SU-5 versus SU-1; and SU-9 and SU-10 versus SU-6).

Table 23: BEQ values of untreated and plasma-treated solutions of PFOA and PFDA

Code of samples		PFAS Calux		Fold EBT exceedance	
		BEQ (µg PFOA/L)	LOQ	EBT DW	EBT SW
SU_0_C	Control – ultra pure water	<LOQ	5.4	<1	<1
SU_1_PFOA	100 µg/L PFOA	330000	5.2	110000	76000
SU_2_PFOA	~75 µg/L PFOA	100000	4.7	34000	23000
SU_3_PFOA	~25 µg/L PFOA	92000	5.0	31000	21000
SU_4_PFOA	100 µg/L PFOA, treated with surfaguide plasma source	170000	5.3	58000	40000
SU_5_PFOA	100 µg/L PFOA, treated with β plasma source	320000	5.1	110000	74000
SU_6_PFDA	sample with PFDA, approx. 12 µg PFOA-EQ/L	100000	5.0	34000	23000
SU_7_PFDA	PFDA, approx. 9 µg/L PFOA-EQ/L	9100	5.0	3100	2100
SU_8_PFDA	PFDA, approx. 3 µg/L PFOA-EQ/L	3800	5.0	1300	880
SU_9_PFDA	PFDA 12 PFOA-EQ/L, treated with surfaguide plasma source	22000	5.1	7200	5100
SU_10_PFDA	PFDA 12 µg PFOA-EQ/L, treated with β plasma source	16000	5.3	5500	3800

Conclusion

A method for assessing the toxicity of landfill leachates, PFAS-enriched leachates, and PFAS solutions have been created, applied, and verified. In the proposed method, the most applicable indicators are the intensity of light and the % content of metabolically active cells of the microorganisms used – *Escherichia coli (Migula)* and *Pseudomonas aureofaciens AP9*.

Based on the created method, mathematical relationships between toxicity and PFOA concentration as a model PFAS representative, have been derived, as well as mathematical relationships linking toxicity as a function of increasing PFOA concentration and treatment with flow and DBD plasma sources. The results can be used to predict toxicity and its reduction when treated with plasma sources.

The results obtained and analysed with the fluorescence method show that treatment with various plasma sources reduces the toxicity of the infiltrate and the infiltrate spiked with PFAS depends on both the concentration of PFAS and the type of plasma treatment. Flow plasma treatment has better and more favourable effect on the reducing of toxicity PFAS, but the effects of the various plasma sources are subject to refinement depending on numerous technological parameters.

3.5 PFAS reduction by plasma treatment

3.5.1 Comparison between Microwave plasma torch and Beta device performance

The experiments in series (1) are performed by plasma treatment of landfill leachate from sampling point 2 of the "Sadinata" site of wastewater treatment plant as in 3.4 (see Figure 4). Six PFAS compounds were identified in the leachate before the plasma treatment with the concentrations given in Table 24. The plasma treatment condition of the two plasma sources used, the Microwave plasma torch and the Beta device in flow and batch modes are presented in Table 5 (in section 2.5.2 Experimental setups).

Table 24: PFAS concentration in landfill leachate detected in samples collected from sampling point 2 of the "Sadinata" site of wastewater treatment plant before the plasma treatment

Compound	PFOA	PFHpA	PFHxA	PFPeA	PFBS	PFBA	SUM
Concentration (µg/L)	0.2	0.1	1.0	0.6	1.1	0.4	3.4

The obtained reduction of total PFAS concentration after the plasma treatment reaches 39 %. It is similar for both plasma sources in batch mode and Beta device in flow mode. Much lower reduction is obtained in flow mode of Microwave plasma torch (Table 25). As the Microwave plasma torch operates at power of 100 W while the Beta device is at 20 W in these experiments performed, it can be concluded that the Beta device is only more effective compared to surfatron device. Because of this, the Microwave plasma torch is not used in the further investigation of the PFAS reduction.

This experiment was conducted and the results were obtained with plasma treatment of landfill leachate. The results obtained cannot be directly compared to most of the previously reported studies in which the treatment was applied to PFAS-contaminated distilled or model water (e.g. Topolovec et al. 2024).

When treating the same volume in a vessel with the same open surface of the liquid, similar results can be obtained. This is due to the same volume-surface ratio, which is of significant importance for the interaction of the plasma with the liquid. At the same time, in the treatment in the flow mode, an important factor is the geometry of the plasma column.

Table 25: Effectiveness in degradation of PFAS (% reduction of sum of six PFAS) in landfill leachate of Microwave plasma torch and Beta device in batch and flow treatment modes

Plasma device	Mode	Treatment	Degradation, %
Microwave plasma torch	Batch	1 min	28
		2 min	39
		5 min	31
	Flow	1 recirculation	13
		2 recirculations	2
		3 recirculations	-2
Beta Device	Batch	1 min	28
		2 min	31
		5 min	31
	Flow	1 recirculation	26
		2 recirculations	30
		3 recirculation	30

3.5.2 Optimization of the discharge and treatment parameters

For further optimisation of Beta device operation systematic investigation was conducted. Since different active particles are produced in the liquid and in the plasma–liquid interface when the plasma touches the liquid surface (surface mode) and when the plasma is produced inside the liquid (underwater mode) these two cases need to be investigated separately (experiments series (2) in Table 5, (in section 2.5.2 Experimental setups)).

The PFAS concentration detected in the landfill leachate before the plasma treatment in the previous experiments is relatively low and not controllable. For this reason, the experiments in series (2) are performed by treating samples of model solution of ultrapure water (Milli-Q) spiked with five PFAS (PFOA, PFPeA, PFDA, PFHxA and PFBA). These PFAS compounds have been chosen on the base of PFAS detected in the landfill leachate in the previous experiments. The LL was spiked with 2 µg/L of each PFAS.

Comparing the effectiveness in degradation of PFAS in the two treatment modes, the surface and the underwater ones (Figure 46), similar results are obtained for substances with longer chains (e.g. 39–45 % for PFDA). For shorter chains PFAS compounds the surface treatment regime is almost two times more effective than the underwater mode (6 % degradation for underwater treatment and 11–13 % for surface treatment for 20 minutes), but overall removal rates are very low. Beta device operating in surface mode demonstrates increasing effectiveness with input power increasing at fixed treatment time (20 min.). For long chain PFDA and PFOA two times higher degradation was obtained in comparison to the short chain PFAS compounds. In this case the degradation of PFDA obtained is 44 %. All PFAS substances in the model solution have almost two times higher degradation degree at 25 W compared to that at 15 W (Figure 46).

Figure 46: Comparison of the effect of the variation of the input power of Beta device operating in surface mode – 15 W and 25 W, Argon flow 5 l/min and treatment time 20 min. Treatment of 50 ml model water with contaminants of PFOA and PFDA in concentration of 2 µg/l of each compound.

OPTIMIZATION OF THE DISCHARGE AND TREATMENT PARAMETERS

Figure 47: Comparing the effectiveness in degradation of PFAS of Beta plasma device in the two treatment modes, the underwater and the surface mode, in PFAS-spiked ultrapure water. Plasma input power 25 W.

Increasing the treatment time at fixed input power (25 W) results in clear increasing of the degree of degradation of long chains compounds (Figure 47). This dependence is difficult to be assess for substances with shorter chains due to the presence of reactions that lead to the formation of by-products during the longer treatment times which was studied in details in the following experiments.

All the treatment variants performed in this experiment lead to more significant reduction in the concentration of substances with longer chains and lower reduction in the concentrations of the shorter chain compounds. In all cases, the dependence of the degree of degradation on the chain length is preserved except for PFBA concentration, which is an exception to this behaviour.

The processes during the plasma treatment lead to reactions not only with the PFAS substances in the solution but also with the ambient air and the solvent (water) producing reactive oxygen and nitrogen species (RONS). In addition to the changes in PFAS concentrations when model water was treated with plasma, the reactive nitrogen particles obtained in the solutions were also considered.

Through systematic experimentation, the plasma performance in producing reactive species crucial for pollutant degradation is being evaluated. In the treatment of landfill with a high content of various pollutants, it is important how the additional contaminants affect the degradation of PFAS. The competitive reactions to the PFAS defluorination occurring during the treatment need to be investigated. Determining the dependence between the concentrations of contaminants as NO_x and the suppression in degradation of persuasive compounds will help to increase the degradation ratio and to understand the mechanisms of PFAS degradation. Concentrations of reactive oxygen and nitrogen species RONS in model waters contaminated with PFAS treated by plasma in surface and

underwater configuration and treatment time 10 min (input power 25 W for Surface mode and 30 W for underwater mode), Argon flow 5 L/min) were determined. The NO_2 , NO_3^- and H_2O_2 concentration obtained were determined according to the composition of the model water – five single PFAS compound and a mixture of them. The conducted study shows a decrease in the concentrations of reactive particles obtained during plasma treatment in the presence of PFAS contaminants (Figure 48).

Figure 48: RONS in plasma treated model water contaminated with PFAS. Wave power of 30 W (underwater) and 25 W (surface), Argon flow 5 l/m, treatment time 10 min.

3.5.3 Comparison of performance of Pin-jets, Beta device and Surfaguide plasma device

The comparison of effectiveness of the three different plasma system (Table 5, series (3), in section 2.5.2 Experimental setups) was made by treating samples of model water of five PFAS compounds diluted in ultrapure water. The model solution was spiked with PFDA, PFOA, PFPeA, PFHxA and PFBA also used in the previous stage of the investigation (series (2)). The operational parameters are presented in Table 5 (in section 2.5.2 Experimental setups). Plasma tests were performed on individual PFAS compounds (PFDA, PFOA, PFHxA, PFPeA, PFBA) in 10 mL and 50 mL ultrapure water with an initial concentration of 100 $\mu\text{g/L}$. Furthermore, plasma tests were performed on a mixture of all 5 PFAS with a total concentration of 500 $\mu\text{g/L}$ in ultrapure water and in landfill leachate.

Both in the individual PFAS compounds and in their mix, the Pin-jets plasma device demonstrates the highest effectiveness of 95 % in degradation of long-chain PFAS (PFDA) but for short-chain it is very low (below 5 % for PFBA) (Figure 49). The Pin-jets PFAS degradation depends also on the surface-to-volume ratio. In contrast, the Beta device exhibited higher efficacy at higher volumes (PFAS-mixture in 50 mL ultrapure water), with degradation rates ranging from 17 % (PFHxA, short-chain PFAS) to 25 % (PFDA, long-chain PFAS)..

Figure 49: Comparing the effectiveness of Pin-Jets device degradation in solutions of individual PFAS compounds (PFDA, PFOA, PFHxA, PFPeA, PFBA) in ultrapure water and mixture of them in ultrapure water and in landfill leachate (MIX WW). Treatment time 10 min. Treated samples: 10 mL.

Individual compounds degradation in solution and mixtures

The degradation rate of the individual compounds as a result of plasma treatment applied to individual solutions differs from that obtained when treating mixtures of all five of them. For all contaminants, the treatment of the mixture with the Pin-jets plasma system leads to lower degradation than treating individual solutions. Comparison between the degradation rate of Pin-jets and Beta device (Figure 50) show that the Pin-jets is very effective for long-chain compounds (more than 90 % for PFDA) while the Beta device is more effective than Pin-jets for short-chain substances (PFBA) and in mixtures with higher volume (50 mL).

Figure 50: Comparison of the effectiveness of Pin-jets plasma system and Beta device. Treatment time 10 min. Treated samples: 10 mL solutions of individual PFAS compounds (PFDA, PFOA, PFHxA, PFPeA, PFBA) and 10 mL (MIX 10) and 50 mL (MIX 50) mixture of them in ultrapure water and in landfill leachate (MIX WW).

The formation of PFAS by-products as a result of plasma treatment was investigated. The individual solution of each of these 5 PFAS with concentration of 2 µg/L were treated by Pin-jets and Beta device. Results show the transformation of long-chain to short-chain PFAS as an effect of plasma treatment (Table 26). Additionally, two new substances are found in the samples after the plasma treatment, PFNA and PFHpA. The values marked in red show appearance of small amount of longer-chain PFAS substances than the treated ones. We assume that this may be due to some impurity or contamination but not to the plasma treatment.

Table 26: By-products concentration obtained after plasma treatment with Pin-jets and Beta device of individual PFAS compounds (PFDA, PFOA, PFHxA, PFPeA, PFBA) in ultrapure water

Compounds treated		Plasma system	By-products obtained (concentration, µg/L)						
			PFDA	PFNA	PFOA	PFHpA	PFHxA	PFPeA	PFBA
			C10	C9	C8	C7	C6	C5	C4
C10	PFDA	Pin-jets		2.8	1.7	0.8	0.6		0.5
		Beta		4.5	1.9	0.6	0.2		
C8	PFOA	Pin-jets				2.2	1		0.5
		Beta				0.3			
C6	PFHxA	Pin-jets			0.4			2.1	0.7
		Beta				0.4			
C5	PFPeA	Pin-jets					0.3		22.4
		Beta							
C4	PFBA	Pin-jets							
		Beta							

A study was also conducted on the newly obtained representatives of PFAS after plasma treatment, which were not present in the solution before the treatment, PFNA and PFHpA (in red in Table 26). For every individual compound solution treated products from the degradation with shorter chain length than the spiked compound occurs and the concentrations of these by-products decrease as the chain lengths get shorter. The degradation of PFAS compounds leading to higher concentrations of PFBA obtained occur when plasma treatment was performed with the Pin-jets plasma system but not when Beta device was used. This relates to the higher degree of short-chain PFAS degradation by Beta device than by the Pin-jets.

Surfaguide device (see Table 5 in Section 2.5.2) was used for treatment of PFAS compounds (PFDA, PFOA, PFHxA, PFPeA, PFBA) in 50 mL model water mixture in ultrapure water with initial total concentration of 500 µg/L. The obtained results were compared with the degrader rate obtained when the solution was treated with Pin-jets and Beta devices. Since Surfaguide device allows operation at higher input power the treatment was performed at 500 W and 1000 W and shorter treatment time – 3 min and 5 min – in order to reduce the heating to the liquid. The total degradation of PFAS obtained as a result of Surfaguide device treatment for 3 minutes with input power of 1000 W is similar to the degradation when treating with Beta device with input power only 20 W but for longer treatment time – 10 min (Figure 51). It is also found that the Surfaguide device is most effective for PFDA especially at higher power (25 % in 3 min with power of 1000 W).

Figure 51: Degradation of PFAS compounds (PFDA, PFOA, PFHxA, PFPeA, PFBA) in 50 mL model water mixture in ultrapure water with initial total concentration of 500 µg/L. Input power 500 W (SG 500) and 1000 W (SG 1000). Plasma treatment with Pin-jets plasma device, Beta device and Surfaguide device. .

All results obtained in these series of experiments demonstrate the plasma treatment as a perspective method for PFAS degradation. All plasma devices show high effectiveness in long-chain PFAS compounds degradation. The degradation rate of Pin-jets is above 90 % for PFDA in ultrapure water. This is connected with the C-C bond destruction and formation of shorter-chain PFAS compounds. Only by plasma treatment with Beta device, degradation of shorter-chain PFAS is obtained with degree similar to that of long-chain PFAS.

The results are obtained in the lab-scale experiments by treating samples with volumes 10–50 mL. The direct upscaling of the devices is not possible and the energy consumption does not increase linearly in upscaling. Some evaluation of the specific energy consumption for each plasma device and operational mode is done and the results are presented in Table 27. The triple Pin-jets system specific energy consumption is evaluated to about 850 kWh/m³.

Table 27: Specific energy consumption of plasma treatment experiments with plasma sources in batch and flow operational modes.

Plasma source	Input power, W	Treatment mode	Treatment time, min	Treatment volume, mL	kWh/m ³
Microwave plasma torch	100	Batch	1	10	367
			2	10	733
			5	10	1833
		Flow	1 recirculation	50	306
			2 recirculations	50	611
			3 recirculations	50	917
Beta device	20	Batch		10	73
			2	10	147
			5	10	367
		Flow	1 recirculation	50	61
			2 recirculations	50	122
			3 recirculations	50	183
	15	Batch	10	10	550
	25		5	10	458
			10	10	917
			20	10	1833
Surfaguide plasma device	500	Batch	5	50	45833
	1000		3	50	55000

3.5.4 Plasma replication and upscaling results

Table 28 summarises the specific energy and gas consumption for each plasma treatment. The specific energy consumption was between 590 and 652 kWh/m³, with the highest energy consumption for the Ar and O₂ gas mixture (649 kWh/m³ on average), and the lowest for pure Ar gas (594 kWh/m³ on average).

Table 28: Specific energy and gas consumption of plasma treatment experiments performed with LL from Rastatt landfill

	Gas Mixture	Plasma Energy in kWh/m ³	Ar gas consumption in Nm ³ /m ³	O ₂ /H ₂ gas consumption in Nm ³ /m ³
A1	Ar 200 sccm	592	14.4	0
A2	Ar 200 sccm	590	14.4	0
A3	Ar 200 sccm	600	14.4	0
B1	Ar 120 sccm - O ₂ 80sccm	650	8.64	5.76
B2	Ar 120 sccm - O ₂ 80sccm	644	8.64	5.76
B3	Ar 120 sccm - O ₂ 80sccm	652	8.64	5.76
C1	Ar 195 sccm - H ₂ 5sccm	622	14.04	0.36
C2	Ar 195 sccm - H ₂ 5sccm	598	14.04	0.36
C3	Ar 195 sccm - H ₂ 5sccm	616	14.04	0.36

The flocculation (pretreatment) and plasma treatments resulted in a discoloration of the water (Figure 52). Differences between the plasma treatments were observed, with the most pronounced effect visible after the argon-oxygen plasma treatment.

Figure 52: Water samples, from left to right: untreated (RO), pretreated (R1), after argon plasma treatment (A 1-3), after argon-oxygen plasma treatment (B 1-3), after argon-hydrogen plasma treatment (C 1-3). Figure provided by Fraunhofer IGB.

During flocculation, the COD was reduced by about 21% from 811 mg/L to 668 mg/L. Plasma treatment did not show a consistent trend in COD or TOC reduction.

Absorbable organic fluorine (AOF) levels increased in all experiments (see Annex A). However, when PFAS undergo mineralisation, a decrease in AOF levels is expected, as fluorine is released in inorganic forms. This could indicate a transformation of detected PFAS into organic fluorine compounds that adsorb more readily. The lowest increase in AOF levels was found after plasma treatment with Ar-H₂ (17-67%), and the highest increase was found after plasma treatment with Ar (42-342%).

The analysis of PFAS was conducted using targeted methods and a total oxidizable precursor (TOP) assay (Table 29) by an external laboratory (Eurofins Umwelt West GmbH). The TOP approach is an indirect method that employs strong oxidising agents at elevated temperatures to convert PFAS precursors into quantifiable terminal perfluorinated acids (see also D1.3). The oxidation products are subsequently analysed by targeted methods.

In the pretreated LL (R1), 13 PFAS were detected, of which 2 were just above the LOQ (PFNA and PFOSA). 8 of these substances were removed below the LOQ in all experiments, and two others (PFHxA and PFOA) were removed above 95% in all experiments. Table 29 lists the PFAS detected as well as their corresponding carbon chain length, initial concentration in pretreated LL (R1) and average removal percentage. Notably, PFBA was the predominant PFAS with an initial concentration in the pretreated LL (R1) of 2.5 µg/l followed by PFBS (1 µg/l), PFHxA (0.79 µg/l) and PFOA (0.67 µg/l). For PFAS with carbon chain lengths <5, the removal was lower than for PFAS with longer carbon chains. The average removal in all trials of PFBA (C₄) was 81%. In the total oxidizable precursor (TOP) assay, the initial PFBS concentration was about twice as high and the average removal was 86%, with no significant differences in removal between the gas mixtures. For PFBA (C₄), no significant difference in removal was observed between the gas mixtures, and the average removal was around 20% in all trials. This was also seen for TOP PFBA analysis, with an average removal of 18% across all

trials and slightly higher concentrations. PFPeA (C₅) showed the highest removal with the Ar-H₂ gas mixture (34 %, see Annex A). This may indicate that the combination with H₂ gas, which promotes reductive reactions, is advantageous compared to Ar-O₂, which promotes oxidative reactions. However, in the TOP PFPeA analysis, the initial concentration was 2.5-times higher and the difference in removal between Ar-O₂ (51%) or Ar-H₂ (56%) was smaller (see Annex A).

In the tests where only Ar gas was used (A1-A3), the removal of PFPeA, PFBA, and PFBS fluctuated more than in the tests with other gas mixtures (see Annex A). Trial A3 showed the lowest removal and even an increase in concentration of 7% for PFPeA.

Additional results with initial concentrations and removal of PFAS in each trial are provided in Annex A.

Table 29: PFAS substances with carbon chain length that were found in R1; PFNA and PFOSA were just above their LOQ before Plasma treatment

PFAS present in R1	Carbon chain length	Concentration in R1 in µg/L	Average removal in all trials	Concentration in R1 in µg/L (TOP)	Average removal over all trials (TOP)
Perfluorobutanoic acid (PFBA)	4	2.5	20%	2.7	18%
Perfluorobutanesulfonic acid (PFBS)	4	1	81%	2.1	86%
Perfluoropentanoic acid (PFPeA)	5	0.15	24%	0.41	51%
Perfluoropentanesulfonic acid (PFPeS)	5	0.025	<LOQ: 0.01 µg/l	0.03	<LOQ: 0.01 µg/l
Perfluorohexanoic acid (PFHxA)	6	0.79	>95%	0.88	>95%
Perfluorohexanesulfonic acid (PFHxS)	6	0.11	<LOQ: 0.01 µg/l	0.12	<LOQ: 0.01 µg/l
Perfluoroheptanoic acid (PFHpA)	7	0.21	<LOQ: 0.01 µg/l	0.27	<LOQ: 0.01 µg/l
1H,1H,2H,2H-Perfluorooctane sulfonic acid (H4PFOS)	8	0.035	<LOQ: 0.01 µg/l	<LOQ: 0.01 µg/l	-
Perfluorooctanoic acid (PFOA)	8	0.67	>97%	0.66	>97%
Perfluorooctanesulfonic acid (PFOS)	8	0.17	<LOQ: 0.01 µg/l	0.14	<LOQ: 0.01 µg/l
Perfluorooctanesulfonamide (PFOSA)	8	0.011	<LOQ: 0.01 µg/l	<LOQ: 0.01 µg/l	-
Perfluorononanoic acid (PFNA)	9	0.018	<LOQ: 0.01 µg/l	0.016	<LOQ: 0.01 µg/l
Capstone product B	15	0.036	<LOQ: 0.015µg/l	<LOQ: 0.015 µg/l	-
Sum 11 PFT (carboxylic acids)		4.3	50%	5	52%

Bioassays were also conducted on the samples, following the procedure described in D1.5 (Behnisch et al., 2021).

In Table 30, the final PFAS CALUX analysis results for the LL samples discussed above and extracted using WAX-SPE are summarised. For all samples, the CALUX results are expressed as the concentration of PFOA equivalents per litre of processed water. Graphical representation of all PFAS CALUX bioanalysis results are presented in Figure 66 (Annex A). For all samples, the activity was higher than the activity of the procedure blank. Furthermore, the PFAS activity in all samples exceeded the effect-based trigger values (EBT) derived for drinking water (3.0 µg PFOA-BEQ/l sample) and surface water (4.3 µg PFOA-BEQ/l sample). The procedure blank (PB) sample did not exceed EBT values. Furthermore, samples of LL before and after pretreatment (R0 and R1) showed the lowest PFAS CALUX activity, whereas samples C1-C3 (Ar-H₂ treatment) showed the highest PFAS CALUX activity. Therefore, the toxicological potential increased after plasma treatment while the concentrations of PFAS analysed decreased. This suggests the formation of more toxic transformation products. However, the exact cause of this increase remains unclear and needs further investigation.

Table 30: PFAS CALUX analysis results measured by BDS of HLB-SPE water sample extracts

Sample	PFAS CALUX activity	PFAS CALUX LOQ	Increase in activity compared to R1
	BEQ (µg PFOA/l sample)		%
PB	2.2	0.42	
R0	23	0.4	
R1	20	0.5	
A1	25	0.4	25%
A2	38	0.4	90%
A3	33	0.4	65%
B1	23	0.4	15%
B2	29	0.4	45%
B3	32	0.4	60%
C1	53	0.4	165%
C2	56	0.5	180%
C3	66	0.4	230%

Conclusion

The plasma experiments showed >95% removal of PFAS with carbon chain length above C₅ no matter the gas mixture. While PFPeS (C₅) was removed below the LOQ in all experiments, PFPeA (C₅) showed the highest removal (34%) with Ar-H₂ gas mixture. PFBA and PFBS (C₄) removal did not depend on the gas mixture and was about 20% and 81%, respectively. Overall, the results do not indicate a clear difference in PFAS removal depending on the gas mixtures investigated.

The results indicate that plasma treatment can destroy PFAS with carbon chain length above C₅ and initial concentration < 1 µg/L with a high energy and gas input e.g. for pure argon gas of about 594 kWh/m³ and 14.4 Nm³/m³.

Other studies that treated real water matrixes such as contaminated groundwater, landfill leachate or aqueous film-forming foams (AFFF) with plasma, also achieved high removal (>90%) for PFAS with carbon chain length >C5 (Thagard et al., 2021; Holsen et al., 2021; Thagard et al., 2025). Thagard et al. (2021) found lower removal for PFAAs <C6 (0-95%) due to their generation during plasma treatment of long-chain PFAAs and PFAS precursors and limited accumulation at the plasma-liquid interface of the reactor. The electrical energy per order (EEO) in the pilot plasma reactor for PFAS contaminated groundwater treatment was on average 16 ± 5.8 kWh/m³ with respect to PFOA and PFOS (Thagard et al., 2021). In a 500 mL batch plasma reactor, landfill leachate was treated with an EEO of 20 to 36 kWh/m³ with respect to PFOA and PFOS and with 100 m³/m³ argon gas (5L/min for 10min treatment of 500mL) (Holsen et al., 2021). The plasma treatment of 250mL undiluted AFFF was also investigated by Thagard et al. (2025). After 86h of treatment, all quantified PFAS with carbon-chain length >C3 were degraded below the limit of detection. However, the argon flow was 2-5 L/min and the EEO about 3500 kWh/m³, underscoring the challenge in removing short-chain PFAS. Singh et al. (2020) achieved high removal of short-chain PFAS in LL by plasma treatment with the addition of CTAB (as assumed in the LCA). They reported an EE/O of 20 to 36 kWh/m³.

Overall, the energy demand for plasma treatment of PFAS in LL and other complex matrixes reported in literature highly differ. Regarding the removal of long-chain PFAS in LL, the experimental setup of Fraunhofer IGB consumed less Ar gas (14.4 m³/m³) than the batch experiment (100 m³/m³) from Holsen et al. (2021). However, Holsen et al. (2021) reported EE/O between 20 to 36 kWh/m³ whereas the Fraunhofer experiment consumed about 600 kWh/m³. The EE/O was not determined in the Fraunhofer experiments.

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It remains unclear why AOF as well as PFAS CALUX activity (higher toxicity potential, because covering up to 7500 PFAS, Sosnowska et al. 2025) increase after plasma treatment while the chemical analysis of the PFAS decreases. One hypothesis to be tested is that the PFAS detected by target analysis are transformed into organic fluorinated compounds, which are both more toxic and more readily adsorbed. Overall, the formation of additional PFAS-specific toxicity assessed by the PFAS-CALUX test puts the usefulness of plasma treatment to achieve zero-pollution in doubt. At current state it is unknown if e.g. a biological post-treatment after application of plasma could reduce the toxicity again as reported e.g. for ozonation for quaternary treatment (for mutagenicity). Further repeated studies are strongly recommended to perform to confirm these first findings of this preliminary research study.

3.6 Assessment of performance and comparative analyses of removal of PFAS

3.6.1 Assessment of RO/NF and pyrolysis system to treat landfill leachate

3.6.1.1 Interpretation of LCA results

Energy analysis

Regarding the pyrolyzer, Pyreg P500 was taken as a reference for estimating the energy consumption and production (“Home - PYREG GmbH” 2024). In particular, this system can work with 1070 t/y of dry material consuming 16 kW and producing an excess of thermal energy up to 1125000 kWh/y (Figure 53). The capacity of this reactor is able to treat all the generated flows of sludge and concentrate at Jesi LTP.

	P500 STANDARD UNIT
Combustible rating	500 kW
Annual throughput <small>DS, dry substance</small>	up to 1,070 t
Annual production	540 t ± 5 %
Maximum thermal capacity	up to 150 kW _{th}
Annual excess thermal energy	1,125,000 kWh
Annual operation hours	up to 7,500 h
Power consumption	up to 16 kW _{el}
Size	l 9,000 mm w 3,000 mm h 9,800 mm
Additional technology module with flue gas cleaning system <small>flue gas scrubbers, activated carbon filters</small>	l 6,000 mm w 3,000 mm h 5,800 mm
<small>Based on sewage sludge, dried (90 % DS) > 11 MJ/kg DS, approx. 60 % organics.</small>	

Figure 53: Characteristics of Pyreg P500 technology (“Home - PYREG GmbH” 2024)

The incineration technology considered was the municipal waste incinerator presented by Jungbluth and Dinkel (2007). In this incineration, the raw sludge enters at a water content of 73%. The internal energy consumption of the waste incinerator is 0.839 MJ heat and 0.144 kWh (0.518 MJ) electricity per kilogram incinerated waste. At a water content of 73%, the dewatered raw sludge has a lower heating value of 3.2 MJ/kg. As shown in Figure 54, in this average situation, no net energy can be generated from dewatered raw sludge in a municipal waste incinerator.

Dewatered raw sludge lower heating value	MJ/kg	3.20	
Energy input per f.u.	MJ/f.u.	0.57	
		Heat	Electricity
Gross energy efficiency	%	25.57%	13.0%
Generated gross energy	MJ/f.u.	0.147	0.074
Internal consumption	MJ/kg	0.839	0.518
	MJ/f.u.	0.150	0.093
Generated net energy	MJ/f.u.	-0.0039	-0.01833

Figure 54: Energy generated from dewatered raw sludge in a municipal waste incinerator (Jungbluth and Dinkel 2007)

Table 31 and Table 32 summarise data on thermal and electrical energy consumed and produced for the four simulated scenarios. The same data are depicted in Figure 55 and Figure 56.

Table 31: Thermal energy consumed and produced by the four analysed scenarios (MJ/d)

Energy	NF + IN	NF + PY	RO + IN	RO + PY
Energy consumption of the biodryer	0,00E+00	1,06E+04	0,00E+00	1,67E+04
Excess thermal energy from pyrolysis	0,00E+00	-1,16E+04	0,00E+00	-1,82E+04
Thermal energy consumed for incineration	6,49E+03	0,00E+00	1,02E+04	0,00E+00
Thermal energy generated for incineration	-4,75E+03	0,00E+00	-7,45E+03	0,00E+00
TOTAL	1,74E+03	-9,67E+02	2,73E+03	-1,52E+03

Table 32: Electrical energy consumed and produced by the four analysed scenarios (kWh/d).

Energy	NF + IN	NF + PY	RO + IN	RO + PY
Electrical energy consumed for incineration	1,25E+03	0,00E+00	1,96E+03	0,00E+00
Electrical energy generated for incineration	-6,70E+02	0,00E+00	-1,05E+03	0,00E+00
Energy consumption of the evaporator	2,25E+03	2,25E+03	2,99E+03	2,99E+03
Energy consumption of the NF system	2,82E+02	2,82E+02	0,00E+00	0,00E+00
Energy consumption of the pyrolyser	0,00E+00	4,37E+02	0,00E+00	6,85E+02
Energy consumption of the RO system	0,00E+00	0,00E+00	4,04E+02	4,04E+02
TOTAL	3,11E+03	2,97E+03	4,30E+03	4,08E+03

Figure 55: Thermal energy consumed and produced by the four analysed scenarios

Figure 56: Electrical energy consumed and produced by the four analysed scenarios

In the analysed scenarios, RO produced higher amount of concentrate compared to NF. Hence, it is needed to add higher amount of sludge to treat by co-pyrolysis the produced concentrate. It explains the higher production of thermal energy for the scenario using RO compared to scenarios using NF. Overall, pyrolysis resulted to be more energy efficient than incineration with a higher production of thermal energy, which can be obtained by combustion of syngas and bio-oil, and a lower consumption of electrical energy. Systems using NF had lower electrical energy consumption than

system using RO membranes. This fact is related to the lower of produced concentrate that needs to be evaporated and to the lower electrical energy consumption of NF membrane filtration compared to RO filtration.

Results of LCA

The results of the LCA application for the selected four scenarios are given for all the environmental impact categories in absolute value in Table 33 and normalised by the impacts of a person with his normal activities in Table 34.

Table 33: Environmental impacts of the four scenarios in the different categories given in absolute values

Environmental categories	UoM	NF + IN	NF + PY	RO + IN	RO + PY
EOFP	kg NOx eq./m ³	5,27E-02	1,12E-01	7,74E-02	1,70E-01
FEP	kg P eq./m ³	3,49E-02	3,42E-02	5,34E-02	5,24E-02
FETP	kg 1,4-DBC eq./m ³	4,17E+00	4,10E+00	6,18E+00	6,08E+00
FFP	kg oil eq./m ³	3,17E+00	2,74E+00	4,33E+00	3,65E+00
GWP	kg CO ₂ eq./m ³	1,23E+01	1,08E+01	1,70E+01	1,48E+01
HOFP	kg NOx eq./m ³	4,91E-02	1,11E-01	7,21E-02	1,68E-01
HTPc	kg 1,4-DBC eq./m ³	3,33E+01	3,30E+01	4,95E+01	4,91E+01
HTPnc	kg 1,4-DBC eq./m ³	1,42E+02	1,37E+02	2,17E+02	2,09E+02
IRP	kBq Co-60 eq./m ³	9,91E-01	9,22E-01	1,35E+00	1,24E+00
LOP	m ² x y/m ³	7,41E-01	6,59E-01	9,07E-01	7,79E-01
MEP	kg N eq./m ³	2,33E-03	4,72E-04	3,59E-03	6,79E-04
METP	kg 1,4-DBC eq./m ³	5,88E+00	5,73E+00	8,73E+00	8,49E+00
ODP	kg CFC11 eq./m ³	5,49E-06	3,76E-06	7,71E-06	5,00E-06
PMFP	kg PM2.5 eq./m ³	2,81E-02	3,23E-02	3,46E-02	4,12E-02
SOP	kg Cu eq./m ³	1,85E-01	1,64E-01	2,24E-01	1,92E-01
TAP	kg SO ₂ eq./m ³	8,62E-02	1,01E-01	1,06E-01	1,29E-01
TETP	kg 1,4-DBC eq./m ³	2,00E+02	9,61E+01	2,78E+02	1,14E+02
WCP	m ³ /m ³	2,99E-01	2,92E-01	3,48E-01	3,37E-01

Table 34: Environmental impacts of the four scenarios in the different categories given in people equivalent

Environmental categories	UoM	NF + IN	NF + PY	RO + IN	RO + PY
EOFP	people eq./m ³	2,97E-03	6,29E-03	4,36E-03	9,58E-03
FEP	people eq./m ³	5,37E-02	5,26E-02	8,22E-02	8,06E-02
FETP	people eq./m ³	1,65E-01	1,63E-01	2,45E-01	2,41E-01
FFP	people eq./m ³	3,22E-03	2,78E-03	4,41E-03	3,72E-03
GWP	people eq./m ³	1,54E-03	1,36E-03	2,13E-03	1,85E-03
HOFP	people eq./m ³	2,39E-03	5,37E-03	3,50E-03	8,19E-03
HTPc	people eq./m ³	3,23E+00	3,21E+00	4,81E+00	4,77E+00
HTPnc	people eq./m ³	4,56E-03	4,39E-03	6,94E-03	6,68E-03
IRP	people eq./m ³	2,07E-03	1,92E-03	2,82E-03	2,59E-03
LOP	people eq./m ³	1,20E-04	1,07E-04	1,47E-04	1,26E-04
MEP	people eq./m ³	5,04E-04	1,02E-04	7,78E-04	1,47E-04
METP	people eq./m ³	1,35E-01	1,32E-01	2,01E-01	1,95E-01
ODP	people eq./m ³	9,14E-05	6,26E-05	1,29E-04	8,33E-05
PMFP	people eq./m ³	1,10E-03	1,26E-03	1,35E-03	1,61E-03
SOP	people eq./m ³	1,54E-06	1,37E-06	1,87E-06	1,60E-06
TAP	people eq./m ³	2,10E-03	2,46E-03	2,58E-03	3,14E-03
TETP	people eq./m ³	1,32E-02	6,32E-03	1,83E-02	7,52E-03
WCP	people eq./m ³	1,12E-03	1,10E-03	1,30E-03	1,26E-03

Table 35 and Figure 57 present the contribution of the various processes to climate change. In all the scenarios, the process primarily responsible for climate change is the energy consumed to evaporate the concentrate. Its contribution to the total impact is 42% in the NF + IN scenario, 47% in the NF + PY scenario, 40% in the RO + IN scenario, and 46% in the RO + PY scenario. The negative values in Table 36 are related to the recovery of thermal energy through syngas combustion. Considering the total emissions, the scenarios with pyrolysis are better compared to the incineration ones. In particular, the NF + PY scenario improved by 12% compared to the NF + IN scenario and the RO + PY by 13% compared to the RO + IN scenario. Pyrolysis has the advantage to operate in site by compact and small reactors. On the contrary, incineration are big plants and further costs for transportation are needed. Moreover, for climate change category, NF seems to be more sustainable than RO filtration.

Table 35: Contribution of the processes to climate change (kgCO₂eq./m³).

Process	NF + IN	NF + PY	RO + IN	RO + PY
Antiscalant	1,51E+00	1,51E+00	1,58E+00	1,58E+00
Biodryer	0,00E+00	9,19E-01	0,00E+00	1,44E+00
Electrical energy incinerator	1,31E+00	0,00E+00	2,06E+00	0,00E+00
Emissions to air from incinerator	3,34E-02	0,00E+00	5,24E-02	0,00E+00
Energy consumed by NF	6,40E-01	6,40E-01	0,00E+00	0,00E+00
Energy consumed by RO	0,00E+00	0,00E+00	9,18E-01	9,18E-01
Energy consumed by the evaporator	5,12E+00	5,12E+00	6,80E+00	6,80E+00
Energy consumed by the pyrolyser	0,00E+00	9,93E-01	0,00E+00	1,56E+00
Energy produced by the pyrolyser	0,00E+00	-1,00E+00	0,00E+00	-1,57E+00
Landfill	2,37E+00	2,37E+00	3,73E+00	3,73E+00
NF membrane replacement	4,39E-12	4,39E-12	0,00E+00	0,00E+00
RO membrane replacement	0,00E+00	0,00E+00	1,94E-13	1,94E-13
Sulfuric acid	2,93E-01	2,93E-01	3,03E-01	3,03E-01
Thermal energy incinerator	1,50E-01	0,00E+00	2,36E-01	0,00E+00
Transport to the incineration	8,59E-01	0,00E+00	1,35E+00	0,00E+00
Emissions to air from bio-oil combustion	0,00E+00	1,06E-05	0,00E+00	1,66E-05
TOTAL	1,23E+01	1,08E+01	1,70E+01	1,48E+01

Figure 57: Contribution of the processes to climate change

Table 36 and Figure 58 present the contribution of the various processes to human toxicity (cancer). In this case, the process primarily responsible is the landfilling of the ash (incineration scenarios) and the biochar (pyrolysis scenarios). This process has a contribution to the total impact of 83% in the NF + IN, 83% the NF + PY scenarios, 87% in the RO + IN and 88% the RO + PY scenario. As in climate change analysis, the negative values in Table 36 are related to the recovery of thermal energy through syngas combustion. Considering the total emissions, the scenarios with pyrolysis are slightly better compared to the incineration ones (1%).

Table 36: Contribution of the processes to human toxicity (cancer) (kg 1,4-DBC eq./m3).

Process	NF + IN	NF + PY	RO + IN	RO + PY
Antiscalant	4,84E+00	4,84E+00	5,06E+00	5,06E+00
Biodryer	0,00E+00	1,65E-01	0,00E+00	2,59E-01
Electrical energy incinerator	1,11E-01	0,00E+00	1,75E-01	0,00E+00
Emissions to air from incinerator	1,96E-02	0,00E+00	3,08E-02	0,00E+00
Emissions to groundwater from incinerator	2,66E-02	0,00E+00	4,17E-02	0,00E+00
Energy consumed by NF	5,42E-02	5,42E-02	0,00E+00	0,00E+00
Energy consumed by RO	0,00E+00	0,00E+00	7,77E-02	7,77E-02
Energy consumed by the evaporator	4,33E-01	4,33E-01	5,76E-01	5,76E-01
Energy consumed by the pyrolyser	0,00E+00	8,40E-02	0,00E+00	1,32E-01
Energy produced by the pyrolyser	0,00E+00	-1,80E-01	0,00E+00	-2,83E-01
Landfill	2,75E+01	2,75E+01	4,31E+01	4,31E+01
NF membrane replacement	7,29E-13	7,29E-13	0,00E+00	0,00E+00
RO membrane replacement	0,00E+00	0,00E+00	2,86E-14	2,86E-14
Sulfuric acid	1,53E-01	1,53E-01	1,58E-01	1,58E-01
Thermal energy incinerator	2,71E-02	0,00E+00	4,25E-02	0,00E+00
Transport to the incineration	1,49E-01	0,00E+00	2,34E-01	0,00E+00
Emissions of PFAS from NF permeate	1,96E-03	1,96E-03	0,00E+00	0,00E+00
TOTAL	3,33E+01	3,30E+01	4,95E+01	4,91E+01

Figure 58: Contribution of the processes to human toxicity (cancer).

In Table 37 and Table 38 the results of the impact in the Marine Ecotoxicity (METP) and the Freshwater Ecotoxicity (FETP) are presented. In Figure 59 and Figure 60, the same results are showed graphically. As for the human toxicity (cancer), in both cases the process primarily contributing to the impact is the landfilling of the ash (incineration scenarios) or the biochar (pyrolysis scenarios).

Table 37: Contribution of the processes to marine ecotoxicity (kg 1,4-DBC eq./m3).

Process	NF + IN	NF + PY	RO + IN	RO + PY
Antiscalant	7,58E-01	7,58E-01	7,93E-01	7,93E-01
Biodryer	0,00E+00	6,96E-02	0,00E+00	1,09E-01
Electrical energy incinerator	4,38E-02	0,00E+00	6,87E-02	0,00E+00
Emissions to air from incinerator	4,46E-02	0,00E+00	7,01E-02	0,00E+00
Emissions to groundwater from incinerator	2,66E-02	0,00E+00	4,17E-02	0,00E+00
Energy consumed by NF	2,13E-02	2,13E-02	0,00E+00	0,00E+00
Energy consumed by RO	0,00E+00	0,00E+00	3,06E-02	3,06E-02
Energy consumed by the evaporator	1,70E-01	1,70E-01	2,26E-01	2,26E-01
Energy consumed by the pyrolyser	0,00E+00	3,31E-02	0,00E+00	5,19E-02
Energy produced by the pyrolyser	0,00E+00	-7,59E-02	0,00E+00	-1,19E-01
Landfill	4,64E+00	4,64E+00	7,29E+00	7,29E+00
NF membrane replacement	3,32E-13	3,32E-13	0,00E+00	0,00E+00
RO membrane replacement	0,00E+00	0,00E+00	1,15E-14	1,15E-14
Sulfuric acid	1,07E-01	1,07E-01	1,11E-01	1,11E-01
Thermal energy incinerator	1,14E-02	0,00E+00	1,79E-02	0,00E+00
Transport to the incineration	5,10E-02	0,00E+00	8,00E-02	0,00E+00
Emissions of PFAS from NF permeate	7,76E-06	7,76E-06	0,00E+00	0,00E+00
TOTAL	5,88E+00	5,73E+00	8,73E+00	8,49E+00

Table 38: Contribution of the processes to freshwater ecotoxicity (kg 1,4-DBC eq./m3).

Process	NF + IN	NF + PY	RO + IN	RO + PY
Antiscalant	5,59E-01	5,59E-01	5,85E-01	5,85E-01
Biodryer	0,00E+00	4,96E-02	0,00E+00	7,79E-02
Electrical energy incinerator	2,94E-02	0,00E+00	4,62E-02	0,00E+00
Emissions to air from incinerator	1,71E-03	0,00E+00	2,69E-03	0,00E+00
Emissions to groundwater from incinerator	2,20E-02	0,00E+00	3,45E-02	0,00E+00
Energy consumed by NF	1,43E-02	1,43E-02	0,00E+00	0,00E+00
Energy consumed by RO	0,00E+00	0,00E+00	2,06E-02	2,06E-02
Energy consumed by the evaporator	1,15E-01	1,15E-01	1,52E-01	1,52E-01
Energy consumed by the pyrolyser	0,00E+00	2,22E-02	0,00E+00	3,49E-02
Energy produced by the pyrolyser	0,00E+00	-5,41E-02	0,00E+00	-8,49E-02
Landfill	3,33E+00	3,33E+00	5,23E+00	5,23E+00
NF membrane replacement	1,96E-13	1,96E-13	0,00E+00	0,00E+00
RO membrane replacement	0,00E+00	0,00E+00	7,29E-15	7,29E-15
Sulfuric acid	6,29E-02	6,29E-02	6,51E-02	6,51E-02
Thermal energy incinerator	8,12E-03	0,00E+00	1,27E-02	0,00E+00
Transport to the incineration	2,17E-02	0,00E+00	3,41E-02	0,00E+00
Emissions of PFAS from NF permeate	1,21E-05	1,21E-05	0,00E+00	0,00E+00
TOTAL	4,17E+00	4,10E+00	6,18E+00	6,08E+00

Figure 59: Contribution of the processes to marine ecotoxicity

Figure 60: Contribution of the processes to freshwater ecotoxicity

3.6.1.2 LCC results

Table 39 summarises the results of LCC in terms of Net Present Values for the NF and the RO scenarios. Figure 61 shows the various contributions in the total present value in the NF and the RO operation scenarios.

Table 39: LCC results (Present Values).

NPV	NF	RO
NPV capital	153.450 €	157.850 €
NPV maintenance	1.208.328 €	1.443.928 €
NPV energy costs	2.572.993 €	3.448.900 €
NPV plant operation costs	7.392.557 €	7.667.425 €
NPV cost for disposal	2.117.730 €	3.322.960 €
TOTAL	13.445.057 €	16.041.063 €

Figure 61: Present Values and comparison between the scenarios

The RO system showed higher NPV compared to the NF systems, mainly due to higher disposal and energy costs. In fact, the RO system produces more concentrate and consequently more salts to be disposed of. Moreover, the energy consumption of the RO system is higher as it operates with higher pressures than the NF system.

Finally, it has to be considered that reported elaborations in this study were accomplished using Italian site-specific data, which may look quite different in countries such as Sweden, Denmark or France with lower carbon footprints or Germany and Poland with a higher footprint. Furthermore, the health impact effects related to PFAS in the LCA study were assumed similar to PCB, and they may result underestimated due to the knowledge gap.

3.6.1.3 Technical feasibility for the scale-up of co-pyrolysis treatment

The scale-up of a co-pyrolysis pilot plant is a complex challenge requiring careful consideration of technical, managerial and economic variables. It is essential to ensure the technical efficiency of gas treatment and waste management systems by adapting the process to the variability of large-scale raw materials. At the management level, solutions for continuous maintenance and monitoring must be implemented, ensuring a stable and efficient operation of the plant.

On a large scale, the variability of raw materials can have a significant impact as it is difficult to obtain continuous supplies of sludge and concentrate with homogeneous characteristics. This variability can affect the content of organic or inorganic substances by changing the behaviour of the sludge during pyrolysis affecting the amount of bio-oil and biochar produced and the overall performance of the process. Metals and salt content in reverse osmosis concentrate may act as catalysts, but variations in their concentration could modify the effectiveness of the process. A more corrosive salt concentrate can accelerate the deterioration of equipment, requiring more resistant materials and

more frequent maintenance. Moreover, the formation of slag or ash in the reactor could complicate waste management and increase time for cleaning operation. The amount and composition of the gas produced by pyrolysis may also vary, affecting its usability for energy production or other processes.

First of all, it is necessary to implement equalization tanks to ensure the feed entering the pyrolyzer is more uniform, improving process stability. To reduce fluctuations the tanks have to be continuously mixed. It is important to ensure that the material has uniform size to insert into the conveying system. Using crushers or grinders to reduce particle size with vibrating sieves to separate particles of inappropriate size and provide that only homogeneous material is processed. Managing these fluctuations across large quantities requires process control and real-time monitoring systems. To address the variability of characteristics, an advanced control system will be needed with sensors monitoring the input composition of sludge and concentrate. These data must be used to automatically adjust operating conditions to optimize production and ensure the quality of final products. Since pyrolysis temperature may increase or decrease based on the organic content and concentration the system should be adjusted frequently to maintain optimum operating conditions. The HRT of materials in the reactor could be adjusted to ensure total decomposition of organic materials and optimal transformation of inorganic components. The flow of nitrogen as inert gas may also need to be adjusted to compensate chemical composition variability of the feed, preventing unwanted reactions with oxygen. To avoid compromising the controlled atmosphere inside the pyrolyzer, the use of rotary valves for continuously feeding while maintaining system pressure could be an optimal solution. Structural characteristics of rotary valves vary depending on the flow and the nature of the material being processed. For example, for a specific flow of approximately 100 kg/h, rotary valves with a single rotor without a solid shaft are particularly advantageous since they are designed for non-uniform materials (i.e. sludge or heterogeneous mixtures). They allow cutting and shredding of the material, preventing blockages. The absence of a solid shaft reduces the risk of clogging, allowing the material to flow free. The presence of only the rotor ensures the material can move unobstructed, improving transport efficiency. These valves provide effective sealing between sections of the system with different pressures, preventing the release of gases or the entrance of oxygen from the outside.

As mentioned before the maintenance of an inert atmosphere with nitrogen in the pyrolysis reactor which requires anaerobic conditions is necessary because even a small loss of nitrogen could cause oxygen to enter from the external environment, compromising the inert atmosphere. In full scale, therefore, constant monitoring of the oxygen concentration within the reactor is necessary to ensure that the atmosphere remains inert. Maintaining a constant flow of nitrogen can be costly, especially on a large scale. Nitrogen shall be supplied in sufficient volumes to compensate for any losses or to renew the inert atmosphere. This involves the use of large nitrogen storage or the need for on-site production facilities which require high capital expenditure and operating expenses. To reduce costs, it may be useful to consider a nitrogen recirculation system in which the nitrogen is recovered, purified and reused. To be considered also aspects related to safety systems considering the nitrogen may pose a risk to operator safety. Appropriate ventilation systems and sensors must be installed to detect critical nitrogen concentrations. Nitrogen is usually stored as a liquefied gas at low temperatures or in high pressure cylinders. This means additional risks related to the handling of compressed gases, which require specific safety measures. Alternatively, the use of vacuum pump

should be tested to maintain inert atmosphere in the thermo-chemical reactor with absence of oxygen. This solution may avoid the flow of nitrogen in the reactor saving costs and reducing the complexity of the system.

Cleaning operations performed manually at the laboratory scale require subsequent large-scale automation to prevent interruptions in the continuous operation of the plant. It is necessary to add vibrating systems along the screw or at critical points to prevent material accumulation in certain areas. This continuous movement prevents the material from compacting or sticking. Implementing self-cleaning devices in the screw or transport section such as the use of rotating brushes, scraper knives or compressed air jets can help keep surfaces free from build-up. In addition, cleaning and maintenance operations can be facilitated by designing a pyrolysis plant with removable sections. Regular cleaning is essential to avoid the accumulation of residues, scale or blockages within system parts, especially in screws, pipes, reactors and gas treatment systems. Each module should be equipped with quick connectors and bolted flanges to simplify disassembly and reassembly. The cochlea, being one of the most susceptible parts to accumulation of material, should be designed in removable sections. Each cochlea segment can be easily separated to allow direct access to critical areas for cleaning. Install inspection windows along the screw and other key points in the plant to allow for quick cleaning. Provide removable access doors or purge valves in sections which are most subject to fouling (for example in combustion chamber or in syngas piping). In particular, in the gas treatment sections (such as condensers or scrubbers), the insertion of removable panels facilitates the cleaning of condensed residues that could clog the pipes or heat exchange surfaces.

To simplify operational management about bio-oil the choice to avoid the condensation system and use all the syngas produced by co-pyrolysis to power a turbine and recover heat is a pragmatic strategy on a real scale. In this way it is possible to improve overall system efficiency, especially when there are issues related to condensate management and pipeline maintenance. This strategy can be considered a more advantageous solution if the market or demand for bio-oil does not justify the additional costs and complexities about its management. Condensates produced during the cooling of pyrolytic steam can solidify causing blockages within pipes and channels, especially if bio-oil is not handled properly. The management of bio-oil channels requires frequent cleaning and specific equipment, increasing operational complexity. Avoiding the condensation system eliminates a complex section of the plant, reducing the number of critical components and simplifying daily operations. Burning the syngas directly to power a turbine (or internal combustion engine) allows electricity to be generated by a gas turbine for example. The heat generated by syngas combustion can be recovered and also used for heating input drying processes given the need for the input material to be as dry as possible to avoid reducing the performance of the pyrolytic process.

Before moving to full-scale implementation, it is essential to conduct continuous tests in lab-scale to investigate potential aspects that have not yet been considered, which could lead to issues difficult to manage at the real scale. Among these, the production of biochar and its final handling / disposal needed additional evaluation. It will be important to determine the expected volume of biochar in continuous operation and evaluate its variability based on feedstock and pyrolysis conditions to understand if it matches with regulatory standards and market demands. Continuous testing not only reduces the risks associated with scaling up but also ensures a gradual transition by addressing critical challenges in advance.

3.6.2 Assessment of plasma technology to treat PFAS in landfill leachate

The following categories of input are considered in the study: Energy; Materials; Transport.

The output flows considered are as follows:

- Emissions to air - they are generated outside the system boundaries (upstream energy production) and will be directly calculated with the LCA software;
- Emissions to water - these include PFAS that are not reduced during the treatment, and nitrates, produced from the nitrogen in the surrounding air during the plasma treatment process.

The estimated input and output values of the flows are presented in the Table 40.

Table 40: Estimated input and output values in LCA of plasma treatment

Inputs				
Energy, kWh/m³ system input				
Type	A1 RO1/P	A2 RO2/P	A3 RO2/E	Reference
Plasma generation				
High voltage (HV) power supply - 40kV, for the plasma generator	26	18.72	No	Singh et al. 2021 and Singh et al. 2019-a
Low voltage (LV) power supply - 210-230V, for cooling of the transformer and the capacitors - fans and pumping	3.88	3.14	No	Catalogues of Wilo, Vikiwat, ProMinent and Mouser
Aeration				
Compressor for recirculation of argon (99.35% of the flow)	1.16	0.33	No	Catalogue of IN-ECO
Reagent dosing				
Mixing of the preparation tank and pumping (vertical mixer and dosing pumps)	4.92	4.08	No	Catalogue of Helisem and ProMinent
Evaporator^a				
Energy consumption (heating, vacuum, recirculation pumping, cleaning, etc.)	No	No	28	Catalogue of Condorchem Enviro Solutions
RO unit				
Pumping, backwash, reagent (sulfuric acid and antiscalant) preparation and dosing, etc.	No	6.55	6.55	Thrun 2020 and catalogues of ProStream and ProMinent
Materials, kg/m³ system input				
Type	A1	A2	A3	Reference
Aeration of plasma reactor				
Gas carrier (Argon) - mass	0.70	0.28	No	ESTCP Final Report – Hagelin et al. 2022; Singh et al. 2021 and Singh et al. 2019-a
Reagent dosing for plasma				
Reagent Cetrimonium bromide (CTAB) - 0.4mM	0.15	0.06	No	Singh et al. 2021
Water mass for solution preparation	492.85	197.14	No	-
RO unit				
Sulfuric Acid	No	6	6	Topal et al. 2022
Antiscalant	No	0.005	0.005	Membrane manufacturers websites (e.g. https://www.watertechnologies.com/ https://www.roagua.com)
Delivery, t*km/m³ system input				
Type	A1	A2	A3	Reference
Plasma reactor				
Delivery of Argon (approx. 8.5 m ³ =300cf vessels)	1.33	0.54	No	https://gascylindersource.com/shop/argon-cylinders/new-300-cuft-steel-argon-cylinder/
Delivery of Cetrimonium bromide (CTAB)	0.06	0.02	No	-
Evaporator				
Delivery of the remaining solid phase after evaporation to the closest incineration plant	No	No	18.57	Catalogue of Condorchem Enviro Solutions
RO unit^b				
Delivery of Antiscalant**	No	0	0	-
Delivery of Sulfuric acid consumption**	No	0	0	-

<i>Outputs</i>				
<i>Emissions to water^c, kg/m³ system input</i>				
Type	A1	A2	A3	Reference
PFAS	0.50x10 ⁻⁶	0.49x10 ⁻⁶	No	Singh et al. 2021
Nitrates	0.10	0.04	No	Pandey et al. 2023; Ruamrungsri et al. 2023
RO unit				
PFAS	No	0.60x10 ⁻⁷	0.60x10 ⁻⁷	-

The impact assessment was carried out utilising two software applications: Umberto LCA software and OpenLCA 2.2.0.

Umberto LCA software

The potential impact for each of the ReCiPe2016 categories was normalised and expressed as people equivalent/m³ (Table 41).

Table 41: Abbreviations for the 18 midterm impact categories of the ReCiPe2016 methodology have been estimated.

EOFP	Photochemical ozone formation potential: ecosystem	HOFP	Photochemical ozone formation potential: human health
FEP	Freshwater eutrophication potential	LOP	Land use related impact (soil quality)
FETP	Freshwater Eco toxicity potential	MEP	Marine eutrophication potential
FFP	Fossil resources scarcity potential	METP	Marine Eco toxicity potential
GWP	Global warming potential	ODP	Ozone depletion potential
SOP	Mineral resources scarcity potential	PMFP	Particulate matter formation potential
HTPc	Human toxicity potential (cancer)	TAP	Terrestrial acidification potential
HTPnc	Human toxicity potential (non-cancer)	TETP	Terrestrial Eco toxicity
IRP	Ionising radiation potential	WCP	Water use (scarcity potential)

The total score for each scenario is the sum of the impacts (equal weighting scores):

- Scenario 1 (Plasma treatment of the entire main concentrate): 0.5322
- Scenario 2 (Second stage RO unit added to reduce the concentrate volume and increase PFAS concentration): 0.5049
- Scenario 3 (Second stage RO unit added to reduce the concentrate volume, followed by an evaporation installation, after which the sludge/salts are transported for incineration off-site): 0.6423

The total scores are to be interpreted as follows (with the most favourable option at the top of the ranking): **Scenario 2, Scenario 1, Scenario 3.**

The calculated normalised midterm impact categories are provided in the Table 42 below.

Table 42: Environmental impacts of the three scenarios in the different midterm impact categories given in people equivalent/m³

Environmental categories	UoM	Scenario 1	Scenario 2	Scenario 3
EOFP	people eq./m ³	0,001955347	0,001752543	0,00268169
FEP	people eq./m ³	0,058706928	0,053458775	0,056726385
FETP	people eq./m ³	0,057035271	0,061795443	0,094272328
FFP	people eq./m ³	0,005199952	0,004650401	0,005879667
GWP	people eq./m ³	0,002487552	0,002215694	0,00271147
HOFP	people eq./m ³	0,001651276	0,001481512	0,002245567
HTPc	people eq./m ³	0,321236229	0,291530402	0,355641572
HTPnc	people eq./m ³	0,001384269	0,001343211	0,00166682
IRP	people eq./m ³	0,024085733	0,021535251	0,022297875
LOP	people eq./m ³	0,000146735	0,000107557	0,000112228
MEP	people eq./m ³	0,002167318	0,001147952	0,000536253
METP	people eq./m ³	0,045278101	0,049392763	0,074934649
ODP	people eq./m ³	0,00010664	8,59385E-05	9,38061E-05
PMFP	people eq./m ³	0,001757005	0,002282764	0,002525589
SOP	people eq./m ³	9,47515E-07	9,21582E-07	1,62258E-06
TAP	people eq./m ³	0,00230912	0,003576902	0,003935101
TETP	people eq./m ³	0,006000097	0,007547318	0,015070972
WCP	people eq./m ³	0,000696537	0,000994278	0,000967684

Figure 62: The potential midterm impact by categories for each scenario

These medium-term impact categories have been aggregated by material and energy flows (Table 43).

Table 43: Aggregated midterm impacts by material/energy flows for the three scenarios (given in people equivalent)/m³

Material/energy flow	Scenario 1	Scenario 2	Scenario 3
Antiscalant	no	0,00205272	0,00205272
Argon	0,016665597	0,00666624	no
CTAB	0,011902241	0,0047609	no
Electricity (high voltage)	0,298573153	0,21497267	no
Electricity (low voltage)	0,147422628	0,20870071	0,51139074
Nitrate	0,001453077	0,00058123	no
PFAS	0,000249449	0,00027639	2,9934E-05
Sulfuric acid	no	0,04449203	0,04449203
Transport	0,007361809	0,00296591	0,08433586
Water	0,048577103	0,01943084	no

The results demonstrate that electricity, irrespective of its voltage, constitutes the primary contributor to the observed environmental and human impact. The second most notable contributor is transportation, followed by the use of sulphuric acid in the regeneration of the membranes within the reverse osmosis unit. With the exception of the FEP, Scenario 3 exhibits the highest negative impact across the other three impact categories. Scenarios 1 and 2 demonstrate closely comparable performance.

Another important aspect of the analysis pertains to the manner in which each stage of the respective scenario contributes to the studied impact (Table 44).

Table 44: Aggregated midterm impacts by stages for the three scenarios (given in people equivalent)/m³

Process	Scenario 1	Scenario 2	Scenario 3
Areation	0,040879334	0,01441071	
Plasma generation	0,356002852	0,26144928	
Plasma treatment	0,001702527	0,00085762	2,9934E-05
Reagent dosing	0,133620345	0,08468765	
RO unit		0,14349436	0,14349436
Evaporator			0,49877698

The analysis of the results indicates that the evaporator has the highest potential impact, followed by plasma generation (bigger in Scenario 1) and operation of the RO unit. As with the other impact categories, Scenario 3 has the highest potential for global warming, largely due to evaporation.

Open LCA

The Open LCA provides single score results, which are based on the aggregated impact score obtained after a weighting. The single scores of the three scenarios were calculated as:

- Scenario 1: 0,00553
- Scenario 2: 0,00511
- Scenario 3: 0,00585

The single scores are to be interpreted as follows (with the most favourable option at the top of the ranking): **Scenario 2, Scenario 1, Scenario 3**. Notwithstanding the divergent values when compared with the Umberto LCA, the ranking of the scenarios remains identical.

It is observed that the database of the Open LCA is more limited in its scope than the one in the Ecoinvent database. Consequently, the categories exhibiting the highest negative potential impact differ between the two. For instance, in Umberto LCA, the top four impacts are HTPc, FEP, FETP and METP, while in OpenLCA, the top four impacts are Particulate matter, Acidification, Resource use (fossils) and POF - all of them due to the energy mix of the country.

In accordance with the ISO 14044:2006 standard, the interpretation of an LCA should encompass the following components:

- Identification of significant issues based on the results of the LCI phase;
- Evaluation of the study itself, including an assessment of its comprehensiveness, sensitivity and consistency;
- Conclusions, limitations and recommendations.
- The following section will provide a discussion of the aforementioned components.

Identification of significant issues based on the results of the LCI phase

Energy Considerations

Although energy is generated outside the systems' boundaries (an upstream process), given the energy-intensive nature of plasma technologies, the study assessed the environmental impact of energy consumption. Compared to energy, other flows such as materials and transport have a negligible impact, i.e. environmental performance is highly sensitive to the energy usage. The study's results are highly dependent on the national energy mix, which predominantly relies on non-renewable sources like coal.

PFAS impact assessment

Beyond energy assessment, understanding the impact of plasma technology on PFAS emissions is crucial given the specific goal of the study. A deeper insight into the environmental and human health effects of PFAS is needed, as current knowledge is limited. Expanding LCA databases is necessary to improve assessments related to PFAS impact.

Limitations of the Ecoinvent Database

In this LCA, polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs) were used as a surrogate to estimate the environmental and health impacts of PFAS. This decision was based on research (Feng et al., 2021) highlighting the correlation between the health effects of PCBs and PFAS. The Ecoinvent database lacks a generic

antiscalant, leading to the use of phosphoric acid production as a substitute in the analysis. Similarly, due to the absence of cetrimonium bromide data, "non-ionic surfactant production, fatty acid derivative" was used instead.

Evaluation of the study itself, including an assessment of its comprehensiveness, sensitivity and consistency

Evaluation Scope

The study evaluates all input flows, including energy, materials, and transportation, during the operational phase of the systems (Scenario 1, Scenario 2, and Scenario 3). The production of reactors, plasma sources, membranes, cables, and related components is not included in the study. Excluding these components may lead to discrepancies in impact category results, particularly due to frequent membrane replacement in Scenarios 2 and 3.

Environmental Impact - comparison of the alternatives

Scenario 2 has the lowest environmental impact, with scores of **0.5049 (Umberto LCA)** and **0.00511 (Open LCA)**. Scenario 1 follows, with scores of **0.5322 (Umberto LCA)** and **0.00553 (Open LCA)**. Scenario 3 (evaporation and incineration) is the most energy-intensive and least environmentally favourable having the highest impact, with scores of **0.6423 (Umberto LCA)** and **0.00585 (Open LCA)**. Plasma treatment (Scenarios 1 and 2) shows superior environmental performance than Scenario 3. Scenario 2 outperforms Scenario 1 due to its supplementary **RO process**, which reduces liquid volume while increasing PFAS concentration, lowering plasma reactor energy demand.

Potential for Further Optimization

Further research into methods for reducing flow and increasing PFAS concentration before plasma treatment appears worth as this could enhance efficiency. One promising approach is recirculating the retentate through RO membranes multiple times (Thrun, 2020).

Need for Experimental Validation

To enhance credibility, the study's assumptions and data set should be verified through further experiments.

4 Conclusions, limitations and recommendations

In this report are reported results of the assessment of innovative technologies to treat landfill leachate and remove PFAS. Particularly, a combination of membrane technologies and thermal treatment has been investigated in the Italian case study, whereas plasma technology has been investigated in the Bulgarian case study.

A pilot-plant system equipped with NF and RO membrane was operate at Jesi WWTP (Italy) to treat 2 m³/h of landfill leachate. Then, the produced concentrate and sludge were treated by a pyrolysis reactor to completely remove the concentrated PFAS.

Membrane removal technologies for PFAS proved to be a useful treatment to remove PFAS from the produced permeate, with nanofiltration average removal of PFAS reached almost 90% taking as sum of PFAS. A full removal of PFAS was achieved by using RO, considering an LOQ of 20 ng/l. Internal recycle of the produced concentrate helped in both the cases to reduce the volume of produced brine and concentrate PFAS. During the following thermal treatment, the removal of PFAS from LLTP sludge mixed with RO/NF concentrate was evaluated after Pyrolysis treatment and there was almost complete removal during optimal condition of 600 °C and residence time of 20 minutes. The PFAS analysis included very complex matrices from biochar to bio-oil and even to Syngas after trapping the PFAS using XAD resin. However, mass flow analysis through the different pyrolysis products results complicated due to transformation of PFAS and precursors. In the biochar, formation of dioxins and furans were not detected after pyrolysis reaction. However, high concentration of heavy metals was found. Valorisation opportunity of char in agriculture can be hypothesized for municipal sludge not impacted by heavy metals. On the contrary, use of char as waste fuel can be tested due to its residual carbon content.

All these data and parameters were then used as an input for Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) where a comparison between different scenarios has been evaluated, including NF + Pyrolysis, NF + Incineration, RO + Pyrolysis, RO + Incineration. Considering the total emissions, the scenarios with pyrolysis are better compared to the incineration ones. Moreover, for climate change category (calculated as CO₂ equivalent production), NF seems to be more sustainable than RO filtration. In this regard, LCA suggests that efforts generated for a complete elimination of PFAS by RO may generate impacts (e.g., climate change) that do not justify this need. However, more research that includes risk assessment approach is needed to better support this conclusion, which may have underestimated the health impact related to PFAS discharge. Furthermore, it is noteworthy to highlight that energy data used in the elaboration are typical of an Italian case study and may be different in other European Countries.

The research done in the frame of the project to develop an innovative approach to treat landfill leachate and to obtain a near zero pollution discharge by implementing plasma technologies undoubtedly led to noteworthy results. High potential of plasma treatment for degradation, not only for removal, of PFAS contaminants in landfill leachate was demonstrated.

The results obtained show that the degradation degree depends on the PFAS compound, the plasma system and its operational regime. All plasma devices show high effectiveness in long-chain PFAS compounds degradation (from 40 % to > 90 % depending on the plasma source). Only one plasma

device (the Beta device) displayed similar degradation amounts of short-chain PFAS as for long-chain PFAS. The highest effectiveness of 95 % in degradation was accomplished for long-chain PFAS (PFDA) both in the individual PFAS compounds and in their mix when treatment was performed with the Pin-jets plasma device.

The PFAS degradation by plasma treatment is a result of C-C bond destruction and formation of shorter-chain PFAS compounds as by-products. Two new substances products of the degradation have been observed to form in the samples after the plasma treatment, PFNA and PFHpA.

The results obtained and analysed with the fluorescence method show that treatment with various plasma sources reduces the toxicity of the infiltrate and the infiltrate spiked with PFAS which depends on both the concentration of PFAS and the type of plasma treatment. Higher toxicity reduction as a result of plasma treatment occurs at higher concentrations of long-chain PFAS.

The objective of LCA related to plasma technologies was to conduct a preliminary assessment of their environmental performance, comparing it with processes that have already been applied on a larger scale for PFAS destruction - evaporation and incineration. Bearing in mind the assumptions used in this LCA, the results suggest that further investigation into plasma technologies may be worthwhile, particularly if pre-treatment is employed to reduce flow and increase concentration. Further analysis is required in order to gain a more robust understanding of two key areas: firstly, the optimal concentration and flow prior to plasma reactors; and secondly, the most economically, technically and environmentally feasible technologies for the pre-treatment for concentrating the flows.

A perspective solution for the removal of PFAS and other pollutants with higher effectiveness is the combination of plasma treatment with other methods.

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Annex A

Plasma upscaling and replication results

The following tables (Table 45 to Table 48) show PFAS concentration before and after plasma treatment and the respective percentage of removal.

Table 45: Plasma treatment of LL. Initial concentration and removal of PFAS per trial. Part A

PFAS	C-chain length	Concentration in µg/l		Removal in %		
		R0	R1	A1	A2	A3
Perfluorobutanoic acid (PFBA)	4	2.5	2.5	-20%	-32%	-12%
Perfluorobutanesulfonic acid (PFBS)	4	1	1	-87%	-86%	-56%
Perfluoropentanoic acid (PFPeA)	5	0.16	0.15	-27%	-33%	7%
Perfluoropentanesulfonic acid (PFPeS)	5	0.022	0.025	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ
Perfluorohexanoic acid (PFHxA)	6	0.74	0.79	<LOQ	<LOQ	-96%
Perfluorohexanesulfonic acid (PFHxS)	6	0.097	0.11	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ
Perfluoroheptanoic acid (PFHpA)	7	0.21	0.21	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ
Perfluorooctanoic acid (PFOA)	8	0.6	0.67	<LOQ	<LOQ	-98%
Perfluorooctanesulfonic acid (PFOS)	8	0.18	0.17	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ
Perfluorooctanesulfonamide (PFOSA)	8	0.012	0.011	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ
1H,1H,2H,2H-Perfluorooctane sulfonic acid (H4PFOS)	8	0.035	0.035	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ
Perfluorononanoic acid (PFNA)	9	0.01	0.018	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ
Capstone product B	15	0.038	0.036	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ
Sum 11 PFT (carboxylic acids)		4.2	4.3	-51%	-58%	-44%

Table 46: Plasma treatment of LL. Removal of PFAS per trial. Part B

	Removal in %					
	B1	B2	B3	C1	C2	C3
Perfluorobutanoic acid (PFBA)	-16%	-24%	-16%	-20%	-20%	-20%
Perfluorobutanesulfonic acid (PFBS)	-85%	-82%	-82%	-88%	-84%	-82%
Perfluoropentanoic acid (PFPeA)	-27%	-13%	-20%	-33%	-35%	-33%
Perfluoropentanesulfonic acid (PFPeS)	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ
Perfluorohexanoic acid (PFHxA)	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	-98%
Perfluorohexanesulfonic acid (PFHxS)	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ
Perfluoroheptanoic acid (PFHpA)	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ
Perfluorooctanoic acid (PFOA)	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ
Perfluorooctanesulfonic acid (PFOS)	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ
Perfluorooctanesulfonamide (PFOSA)	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ
1H,1H,2H,2H-Perfluorooctane sulfonic acid (H4PFOS)	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ
Perfluorononanoic acid (PFNA)	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ
Capstone product B	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ
Sum 11 PFT (carboxylic acids)	-49%	-53%	-47%	-49%	-51%	-51%
Perfluorobutanoic acid (PFBA)	-16%	-24%	-16%	-20%	-20%	-20%

Table 47: Plasma treatment of LL. Initial concentration and removal of PFAS per trial based on TOP assay. Part C

PFAS	C chain length	Concentration in µg/l		Removal in %		
		R0	R1	A1	A2	A3
TOP Perfluorobutanoic acid (PFBA)	4	2.8	2.7	-19%	-19%	-11%
TOP Perfluorobutanesulfonic acid (PFBS)	4	2.1	2.1	-90%	-89%	-71%
TOP Perfluoropentanoic acid (PFPeA)	5	0.44	0.41	-51%	-56%	-34%
TOP Perfluoropentanesulfonic acid (PFPeS)	5	0.032	0.03	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ
TOP Perfluorohexanoic acid (PFHxA)	6	0.85	0.88	<LOQ	<LOQ	-96%
TOP Perfluorohexanesulfonic acid (PFHxS)	6	0.11	0.12	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ
TOP Perfluoroheptanoic acid (PFHpA)	7	0.26	0.27	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ
TOP Perfluorooctanoic acid (PFOA)	8	0.67	0.66	<LOQ	-98%	-98%
TOP Perfluorooctanesulfonic acid (PFOS)	8	0.17	0.14	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ
TOP Perfluorononanoic acid (PFNA)	9	0.01	0.016	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ
TOP Sum 11 PFT (carboxylic acids)		5	5	-52%	-52%	-46%

Table 48: Plasma treatment of LL. Removal of PFAS per trial based on TOP assay. Part D

	Removal in %					
	B1	B2	B3	C1	C2	C3
TOP Perfluorobutanoic acid (PFBA)	-11%	-22%	-19%	-19%	-22%	-22%
TOP Perfluorobutanesulfonic acid (PFBS)	-90%	-87%	-86%	-90%	-87%	-86%
TOP Perfluoropentanoic acid (PFPeA)	-56%	-49%	-49%	-59%	-54%	-56%
TOP Perfluoropentanesulfonic acid (PFPeS)	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ
TOP Perfluorohexanoic acid (PFHxA)	<LOQ	-99%	-99%	<LOQ	-99%	-98%
TOP Perfluorohexanesulfonic acid (PFHxS)	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ
TOP Perfluoroheptanoic acid (PFHpA)	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ
TOP Perfluorooctanoic acid (PFOA)	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ
TOP Perfluorooctanesulfonic acid (PFOS)	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ
TOP Perfluorononanoic acid (PFNA)	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ
TOP Sum 11 PFT (carboxylic acids)	-50%	-54%	-52%	-54%	-54%	-54%

Plots in Figure 63 showing concentrations of PFAS below the LOQ are plotted as LOQ divided by 2. The LOQ is 0.01 µg/L for all PFAS except capstone product B for which the LOQ is 0.015 µg/L.

Figure 63: Concentrations of PFAS compounds present in the pre-treated LL(R1). If a compound was below its LOQ, the concentration is assumed to be half the LOQ. PFAS with a carbon chain length of C₄ are shown in red, C₅ in orange, C₆ in blue, C₈ in purple and > C₈ in green

Figure 64: Change in COD during plasma treatment.

Figure 65: Change in AOF during plasma treatment.

Figure 66: PFAS CALUX analysis results of serial dilutions of landfill leachate sample extracts. Results are expressed as induction of luminescence, relative to the maximum response of the reference compound PFOA. Figure provided by BDS.

Annex B

Table 49: LCI of the NF + PY scenario.

Element	UdM	Value	Process in Ecoinvent v3.10	Reference
Influent to NF	m3/d	169	-	-
Permeate from NF	m3/d	94	-	-
Concentrate from NF	m3/d	75	-	-
Energy consumption of the NF system	kWh/d	281,69	market for electricity, medium voltage (IT)	
PFAS tot in the effluent	mg/d	64,6	polychlorinated biphenyls (emissions to water, unspecified)	(Feng, Song, and Mo 2021)
Energy consumption of the evaporator	kWh/d	2250	market for electricity, medium voltage (IT)	("Evaporators Evaporatori EVALED" 2024) https://www.evalad.com/en/evaporators
Salt produced and entering to the pyrolyser	kg/d	580,2	-	-
Dry sludge entering to the pyrolyser from municipal WWTP (70%)	kg/d	2395	-	-
Dry sludge entering to pyrolyser from LLTP (70%)	kg/d	367,8	-	-
Energy consumption of the bio-dryer	MJ/d	10637	heat production, biomethane, at boiler condensing modulating <100kW (Europe without Switzerland)	-
Energy consumption of the pyrolyser	kWh/d	436,65	market for electricity, medium voltage (IT)	("Ho-e - PYREG GmbH" 2024)
Biochar production	kg/d	1169,50	-	-
Biochar to landfill	kg/d	1169,50	treatment of residues, MSWI[F]-WWT-SLF, waste paperboard, residual material landfill (CH)	-
Bio-oil production	kg/d	250,7	-	-
Syngas production	kg/d	1611,67	-	-
Antiscalant NF	kg/d	183,79	purification of wet-process phosphoric acid to industrial grade, product in 85% solution state (RoW)	-
Sulphuric acid 30%	kg/d	1759,68	sulphuric acid production (RER)	-
Number of membranes	n/d	0,3087	-	(Bordbar et al. 2022)
Excess thermal energy from pyrolysis	MJ/d	14737,08	heat production, biomethane, at boiler condensing modulating <100kW (Europe without Switzerland)	("Ho-e - PYREG GmbH" 2024)
Emissions to air from pyrolyser				
CO ₂	kg/d	21,10	Carbon dioxide, non-fossil (emission to air, unspecified)	(Hosseinian et al. 2024)
CO	kg/d	0,21	Carbon monoxide, non-fossil (emissions to air, unspecified)	(Hosseinian et al. 2024)
NO _x	kg/d	15,32	Nitrogen oxides (emission to air, unspecified)	(Hosseinian et al. 2024)

Table 50: LCI of the RO + PY scenario.

Element	UdM	Value	Process in Ecoinvent v3.10	Reference
Influent to RO	m ³ /d	169	-	-
Permeate from RO	m ³ /d	69,3	-	-
Concentrate from RO	m ³ /d	99,7	-	-
Energy consumption of the RO system	kWh/d	403,85	market for electricity, medium voltage (IT)	-
PFAS tot in the effluent	mg/d	0	polychlorinated biphenyls (emissions to water, unspecified)	(Feng, Song, and Mo 2021)
Energy consumption of the evaporator	kWh/d	2991	market for electricity, medium voltage (IT)	(“Evaporators Evaporatori EVALED” 2024)
Salt produced and entering in the pyrolyser	kg/d	910,4	-	-
Dry sludge entering to the pyrolyser from municipal WWTP (70%)	kg/d	3967,38	-	-
Dry sludge entering to pyrolyser from LLTP (70%)	kg/d	367,85	-	-
Energy consumption of the bio-dryer	MJ/d	16690,67	heat production, biomethane, at boiler condensing modulating <100kW (Europe without Switzerland)	-
Energy consumption of the pyrolyser	kWh/d	685,16	market for electricity, medium voltage (IT)	(“Ho-e - PYREG GmbH” 2024)
Biochar production	kg/d	2483,71	-	-
Biochar to landfill	kg/d	2483,71	treatment of inert waste, inert material landfill (RoW)	-
Bio-oil production	kg/d	393,38	-	-
Syngas production	kg/d	2528,89	-	-
Antiscalant RO	kg/d	192,226	purification of wet-process phosphoric acid to industrial grade, product in 85% solution state (RoW)	-
Sulphuric acid 30%	kg/d	1820,247	sulphuric acid production (RER)	-
Number of membranes	n/d	0,308676	-	(Bordbar et al. 2022)
Excess thermal energy from pyrolysis	MJ/d	23124,16	heat production, biomethane, at boiler condensing modulating <100kW (Europe without Switzerland)	(“Ho-e - PYREG GmbH” 2024)
Emissions to air from pyrolyser				
CO ₂	kg/d	33,11	Carbon dioxide, non-fossil (emission to air, unspecified)	(Hosseinian et al. 2024)
CO	kg/d	0,33	Carbon monoxide, non-fossil (emissions to air, unspecified)	(Hosseinian et al. 2024)
NO _x	kg/d	24,03	Nitrogen oxides (emission to air, unspecified)	(Hosseinian et al. 2024)

Table 51: LCI of the NF + IN scenario.

Element	UdM	Value	Process in Ecoinvent v3.10	Reference
Influent to NF	m3/d	169	-	-
Permeate from NF	m3/d	94	-	-
Concentrate from NF	m3/d	75	-	-
Energy consumption of the NF system	kWh/d	281,69	market for electricity, medium voltage (IT)	
PFAS tot in the effluent	mg/d	64,6	polychlorinated biphenyls (emissions to water, unspecified)	(Feng, Song, and Mo 2021)
Energy consumption of the evaporator	kWh	2250	market for electricity, medium voltage (IT)	-
Salt produced and going to incineration	kg/d	580,2	-	-
Antiscalant NF	kg/d	183,79	purification of wet-process phosphoric acid to industrial grade, product in 85% solution state (RoW)	-
Sulphuric acid 30%	kg/d	1759,68	sulphuric acid production (RER)	-
Number of membranes	n/d	0,308676	-	(Bordbar et al. 2022)
Dewatered sludge going to incineration from municipal WWTP (TS% = 25)	kg/d	6706,00	-	-
Dewatered sludge going to incineration from LLTP (TS% = 25)	kg/d	1030,00	-	-
Transport	ton*km/d	1330,59	market for transport, freight, lorry >32 metric ton, EURO4	-
Electrical energy consumed	kWh/d	1248,50	market for electricity, medium voltage (IT)	(Jungbluth and Dinkel 2007)
Thermal energy consumed	MJ/d	6490,50	heat production, biomethane, at boiler condensing modulating <100kW	(Jungbluth and Dinkel 2007)
Electrical energy generated from incineration	kWh/d	670,45	market for electricity, medium voltage (IT)	(Jungbluth and Dinkel 2007)
Thermal energy generated from incineration	MJ/d	4749,90	heat production, biomethane, at boiler condensing modulating <100kW	(Jungbluth and Dinkel 2007)
Ash	kg/d	1460,17	treatment of inert waste, inert material landfill (RoW)	-
Emissions from incineration				
Emissions to Air				
Sulfur dioxide	kg/d	1·17E+00	Sulfur dioxide (emission to air, unspecified)	(Alyaseri and Zhou 2017)
Carbon dioxide, biogenic	kg/d	1·40E+02	Carbon dioxide, non-fossil (emission to air, unspecified)	(Alyaseri and Zhou 2017)
Nitrogen oxides	kg/d	3·58E+00	Nitrogen oxides (emissions to air, unspecified)	(Alyaseri and Zhou 2017)
Ammonia	kg/d	3·25E-03	Ammonia (emissions to air, unspecified)	(Alyaseri and Zhou 2017)
Dinitrogen monoxide	kg/d	1·89E-02	Dinitrogen monoxide (emissions to air, unspecified)	(Alyaseri and Zhou 2017)

Element	UdM	Value	Process in Ecoinvent v3.10	Reference
Cyanide	kg/d	3.69E-03	Cyanide (emissions to air, unspecified)	(Alyaseri and Zhou 2017)
Arsenic	kg/d	1.05E-03	Arsenic ion (emissions to air, unspecified)	(Alyaseri and Zhou 2017)
Cadmium	kg/d	5.28E-03	Cadmium II (emissions to air, unspecified)	(Alyaseri and Zhou 2017)
Chromium	kg/d	1.79E-03	Chromium III (emissions to air, unspecified)	(Alyaseri and Zhou 2017)
Copper	kg/d	3.52E-03	Copper ion (emissions to air, unspecified)	(Alyaseri and Zhou 2017)
Mercury	kg/d	8.80E-06	Mercury II (emissions to air, unspecified)	(Alyaseri and Zhou 2017)
Manganese	kg/d	1.49E-03	Manganese II (emissions to air, unspecified)	(Alyaseri and Zhou 2017)
Nickel	kg/d	1.58E-03	Nickel II (emissions to air, unspecified)	(Alyaseri and Zhou 2017)
Lead	kg/d	6.65E-06	Lead II (emissions to air, unspecified)	(Alyaseri and Zhou 2017)
Tin	kg/d	1.41E-02	Tin ion (emissions to air, unspecified)	(Alyaseri and Zhou 2017)
Zinc	kg/d	4.22E-02	Zinc II (emissions to air, unspecified)	(Alyaseri and Zhou 2017)
Silicon	kg/d	7.74E-02	Silicon (emissions to air, unspecified)	(Alyaseri and Zhou 2017)
Calcium	kg/d	4.56E-01	Calcium (emissions to air, unspecified)	(Alyaseri and Zhou 2017)
Aluminum	kg/d	6.67E-02	Aluminum III (emissions to air, unspecified)	(Alyaseri and Zhou 2017)
Magnesium	kg/d	7.39E-03	Magnesium (emissions to air, unspecified)	(Alyaseri and Zhou 2017)
Particulates	kg/d	1.45E+04	Particulate Matter, > 2.5 um and < 10 um (emission to air, unspecified)	(Alyaseri and Zhou 2017)
Barium	kg/d	5.63E-03	Barium II (emissions to air, unspecified)	(Alyaseri and Zhou 2017)
Potassium	kg/d	1.23E-02	Potassium I (emissions to air, unspecified)	(Alyaseri and Zhou 2017)
Selenium	kg/d	1.06E-04	Selenium IV (emissions to air, unspecified)	(Alyaseri and Zhou 2017)
Titanium	kg/d	5.47E-03	Titanium ion (emissions to air, unspecified)	(Alyaseri and Zhou 2017)
Carbon monoxide	kg/d	2.15E+01	Carbon monoxide, non-fossil (emissions to air, unspecified)	(Alyaseri and Zhou 2017)
VOC, volatile organic compounds	kg/d	3.31E+00	VOC, volatile organic compounds (emissions to air, unspecified)	(Alyaseri and Zhou 2017)
Furan	kg/d	2.28E-09	Furan (emissions to air, unspecified)	(Alyaseri and Zhou 2017)
Dioxin, 2,3,7,8 Tetrachlorodibenzo-p-	kg/d	6.50E-09	Dioxin, measured as 2,3,7,8 Tetrachlorodibenzo-p-dioxin (emissions to air, unspecified)	(Alyaseri and Zhou 2017)
Emissions to water				
Ammonium, ion	kg/d	5.34E-01	Ammonium (emissions to water, unspecified)	(Alyaseri and Zhou 2017)

Element	UdM	Value	Process in Ecoinvent v3.10	Reference
Nitrogen	kg/d	3.66E-02	Nitrogen (emissions to water, unspecified)	(Alyaseri and Zhou 2017)
BOD5, Biological oxygen demand	kg/d	1.35E-01	BOD5, Biological oxygen demand (emissions to water, unspecified)	(Alyaseri and Zhou 2017)
COD, Chemical oxygen demand	kg/d	4.53E-01	COD, Chemical oxygen demand (emissions to water, unspecified)	(Alyaseri and Zhou 2017)
TOC, Total organic carbon	kg/d	1.06E-01	TOC, Total organic carbon (emissions to water, unspecified)	(Alyaseri and Zhou 2017)
DOC, Dissolved organic carbon	kg/d	1.06E-01	DOC, Dissolved organic carbon (emissions to water, unspecified)	(Alyaseri and Zhou 2017)
Sulfate	kg/d	9.81E-01	Sulfate (emissions to water, unspecified)	(Alyaseri and Zhou 2017)
Nitrate	kg/d	2.48E+00	Nitrate (emissions to water, unspecified)	(Alyaseri and Zhou 2017)
Phosphate	kg/d	2.78E-02	Phosphate (emissions to water, unspecified)	(Alyaseri and Zhou 2017)
Chloride	kg/d	1.10E-01	Chloride (emissions to water, unspecified)	(Alyaseri and Zhou 2017)
Emissions to Groundwater				
BOD5, Biological oxygen demand	kg/d	3.11E-01	BOD5, Biological oxygen demand (emissions to water, ground)	(Alyaseri and Zhou 2017)
COD, Chemical oxygen demand	kg/d	9.52E-01	COD, Chemical oxygen demand (emissions to water, ground)	(Alyaseri and Zhou 2017)
TOC, Total organic carbon	kg/d	3.77E-01	TOC, Total organic carbon (emissions to water, ground)	(Alyaseri and Zhou 2017)
DOC, Dissolved organic carbon	kg/d	3.77E-01	DOC, Dissolved organic carbon (emissions to water, ground)	(Alyaseri and Zhou 2017)
Sulfate	kg/d	4.51E+00	Sulfate (emissions to water, ground)	(Alyaseri and Zhou 2017)
Nitrate	kg/d	1.47E-01	Nitrate (emissions to water, ground)	(Alyaseri and Zhou 2017)
Phosphate	kg/d	2.28E-01	Phosphate (emissions to water, ground)	(Alyaseri and Zhou 2017)
Arsenic, ion	kg/d	9.71E-05	Arsenic ion (emissions to water, ground)	(Alyaseri and Zhou 2017)
Cadmium, ion	kg/d	1.26E-06	Cadmium II (emissions to water, ground)	(Alyaseri and Zhou 2017)
Cobalt	kg/d	6.34E-04	Cobalt II (emissions to water, ground)	(Alyaseri and Zhou 2017)
Chromium VI	kg/d	5.80E-04	Chromium VI (emissions to water, ground)	(Alyaseri and Zhou 2017)
Copper, ion	kg/d	2.03E-02	Copper, ion (emissions to water, ground)	(Alyaseri and Zhou 2017)
Mercury	kg/d	6.54E-06	Mercury II (emissions to water, ground)	(Alyaseri and Zhou 2017)
Manganese	kg/d	2.05E-02	Manganese II (emissions to water, ground)	(Alyaseri and Zhou 2017)
Molybdenum	kg/d	3.54E-04	Molybdenum VI (emissions to water, ground)	(Alyaseri and Zhou 2017)
Nickel, ion	kg/d	2.20E-03	Nickel II (emissions to water, ground)	(Alyaseri and Zhou 2017)

Element	UdM	Value	Process in Ecoinvent v3.10	Reference
Lead	kg/d	4.97E-04	Lead II (emissions to water, ground)	(Alyaseri and Zhou 2017)
Tin, ion	kg/d	9.03E-04	Tin, ion (emissions to water, ground)	(Alyaseri and Zhou 2017)
Zinc, ion	kg/d	1.07E-03	Zinc II (emissions to water, ground)	(Alyaseri and Zhou 2017)
Silicon	kg/d	2.32E-01	Silicon (emissions to water, ground)	(Alyaseri and Zhou 2017)
Iron, ion	kg/d	5.65E+00	Iron ion (emissions to water, ground)	(Alyaseri and Zhou 2017)
Calcium, ion	kg/d	3.95E+00	Calcium II (emissions to water, ground)	(Alyaseri and Zhou 2017)
Aluminum	kg/d	9.92E-01	Aluminium III (emissions to water, ground)	(Alyaseri and Zhou 2017)
Magnesium	kg/d	4.70E-01	Magnesium (emissions to water, ground)	(Alyaseri and Zhou 2017)

Table 52: LCI of the RO + IN scenario.

Element	UdM	Value	Process in Ecoinvent v3.10	Reference
Influent to RO	m ³ /d	169	-	-
Permeate from RO	m ³ /d	69,3	-	-
Concentrate from RO	m ³ /d	99,7	-	-
Energy consumption of the RO system	kWh/d	403,85	market for electricity, medium voltage (IT)	-
PFAS tot in the effluent	mg/d	0	polychlorinated biphenyls (emissions to water, unspecified)	(Feng, Song, and Mo 2021)
Energy consumption of the evaporator	kWh/d	2991	market for electricity, medium voltage (IT)	-
Salt produced and going to incineration	kg/d	910,4	-	-
Antiscalant NF	kg/d	192,226	purification of wet-process phosphoric acid to industrial grade, product in 85% solution state (RoW)	-
Sulphuric acid 30%	kg/d	1820,247	sulphuric acid production (RER)	-
Number of membranes	n/d	0,308676	-	(Bordbar et al. 2022)
Dewatered sludge going to incineration from municipal WWTP (TS% = 25)	kg/d	11108,67	-	-
Dewatered sludge going to incineration from LLTP (TS% = 25)	kg/d	1030,00	-	-
Transport	ton*km/d	2087,85	market for transport, freight, lorry >32 metric ton, EURO4	-
Electrical energy consumed	kWh/d	1959,05	market for electricity, medium voltage (IT)	(Jungbluth and Dinkel 2007)
Thermal energy consumed	MJ/d	10184,3	heat production, biomethane, at boiler condensing modulating <100kW	(Jungbluth and Dinkel 2007)

Element	UdM	Value	Process in Ecoinvent v3.10	Reference
Electrical energy generated from incineration	kWh/d	1052,02	market for electricity, medium voltage (IT)	(Jungbluth and Dinkel 2007)
Thermal energy generated from incineration	MJ/d	7453,14	heat production, biomethane, at boiler condensing modulating <100kW	(Jungbluth and Dinkel 2007)
Ash	kg/d	2291,17	treatment of inert waste, inert material landfill (RoW)	-
Emissions from incineration				
Emissions to Air				
Sulfur dioxide	kg/d	1.84E+00	Sulfur dioxide (emission to air, unspecified)	(Alyaseri and Zhou 2017)
Carbon dioxide, biogenic	kg/d	2.20E+02	Carbon dioxide, non-fossil (emission to air, unspecified)	(Alyaseri and Zhou 2017)
Nitrogen oxides	kg/d	5.61E+00	Nitrogen oxides (emissions to air, unspecified)	(Alyaseri and Zhou 2017)
Ammonia	kg/d	5.10E-03	Ammonia (emissions to air, unspecified)	(Alyaseri and Zhou 2017)
Dinitrogen monoxide	kg/d	2.97E-02	Dinitrogen monoxide (emissions to air, unspecified)	(Alyaseri and Zhou 2017)
Cyanide	kg/d	5.80E-03	Cyanide (emissions to air, unspecified)	(Alyaseri and Zhou 2017)
Arsenic	kg/d	1.65E-03	Arsenic ion (emissions to air, unspecified)	(Alyaseri and Zhou 2017)
Cadmium	kg/d	8.28E-03	Cadmium II (emissions to air, unspecified)	(Alyaseri and Zhou 2017)
Chromium	kg/d	2.81E-03	Chromium III (emissions to air, unspecified)	(Alyaseri and Zhou 2017)
Copper	kg/d	5.52E-03	Copper ion (emissions to air, unspecified)	(Alyaseri and Zhou 2017)
Mercury	kg/d	1.38E-05	Mercury II (emissions to air, unspecified)	(Alyaseri and Zhou 2017)
Manganese	kg/d	2.35E-03	Manganese II (emissions to air, unspecified)	(Alyaseri and Zhou 2017)
Nickel	kg/d	2.48E-03	Nickel II (emissions to air, unspecified)	(Alyaseri and Zhou 2017)
Lead	kg/d	1.04E-05	Lead II (emissions to air, unspecified)	(Alyaseri and Zhou 2017)
Tin	kg/d	2.21E-02	Tin ion (emissions to air, unspecified)	(Alyaseri and Zhou 2017)
Zinc	kg/d	6.62E-02	Zinc II (emissions to air, unspecified)	(Alyaseri and Zhou 2017)
Silicon	kg/d	1.21E-01	Silicon (emissions to air, unspecified)	(Alyaseri and Zhou 2017)
Calcium	kg/d	7.16E-01	Calcium (emissions to air, unspecified)	(Alyaseri and Zhou 2017)
Aluminum	kg/d	1.05E-01	Aluminum III (emissions to air, unspecified)	(Alyaseri and Zhou 2017)
Magnesium	kg/d	1.16E-02	Magnesium (emissions to air, unspecified)	(Alyaseri and Zhou 2017)
Particulates	kg/d	2.28E+04	Particulate Matter, > 2.5 um and < 10 um (emission to air, unspecified)	(Alyaseri and Zhou 2017)
Barium	kg/d	8.83E-03	Barium II (emissions to air, unspecified)	(Alyaseri and Zhou 2017)

Element	UdM	Value	Process in Ecoinvent v3.10	Reference
Potassium	kg/d	1.93E-02	Potassium I (emissions to air, unspecified)	(Alyaseri and Zhou 2017)
Selenium	kg/d	1.66E-04	Selenium IV (emissions to air, unspecified)	(Alyaseri and Zhou 2017)
Titanium	kg/d	8.59E-03	Titanium ion (emissions to air, unspecified)	(Alyaseri and Zhou 2017)
Carbon monoxide	kg/d	3.37E+01	Carbon monoxide, non-fossil (emissions to air, unspecified)	(Alyaseri and Zhou 2017)
VOC, volatile organic compounds	kg/d	5.19E+00	VOC, volatile organic compounds (emissions to air, unspecified)	(Alyaseri and Zhou 2017)
Furan	kg/d	3.58E-09	Furan (emissions to air, unspecified)	(Alyaseri and Zhou 2017)
Dioxin, 2,3,7,8 Tetrachlorodibenzo-p-	kg/d	1.02E-08	Dioxin, measured as 2,3,7,8 Tetrachlorodibenzo-p-dioxin (emissions to air, unspecified)	(Alyaseri and Zhou 2017)
Emissions to water				
Ammonium, ion	kg/d	8.38E-01	Ammonium (emissions to water, unspecified)	(Alyaseri and Zhou 2017)
Nitrogen	kg/d	5.74E-02	Nitrogen (emissions to water, unspecified)	(Alyaseri and Zhou 2017)
BOD5, Biological oxygen demand	kg/d	2.11E-01	BOD5, Biological oxygen demand (emissions to water, unspecified)	(Alyaseri and Zhou 2017)
COD, Chemical oxygen demand	kg/d	7.10E-01	COD, Chemical oxygen demand (emissions to water, unspecified)	(Alyaseri and Zhou 2017)
TOC, Total organic carbon	kg/d	1.66E-01	TOC, Total organic carbon (emissions to water, unspecified)	(Alyaseri and Zhou 2017)
DOC, Dissolved organic carbon	kg/d	1.66E-01	DOC, Dissolved organic carbon (emissions to water, unspecified)	(Alyaseri and Zhou 2017)
Sulfate	kg/d	1.54E+00	Sulfate (emissions to water, unspecified)	(Alyaseri and Zhou 2017)
Nitrate	kg/d	3.88E+00	Nitrate (emissions to water, unspecified)	(Alyaseri and Zhou 2017)
Phosphate	kg/d	4.37E-02	Phosphate (emissions to water, unspecified)	(Alyaseri and Zhou 2017)
Chloride	kg/d	1.73E-01	Chloride (emissions to water, unspecified)	(Alyaseri and Zhou 2017)
Emissions to Groundwater				
BOD5, Biological oxygen demand	kg/d	4.89E-01	BOD5, Biological oxygen demand (emissions to water, ground)	(Alyaseri and Zhou 2017)
COD, Chemical oxygen demand	kg/d	1.49E+00	COD, Chemical oxygen demand (emissions to water, ground)	(Alyaseri and Zhou 2017)
TOC, Total organic carbon	kg/d	5.92E-01	TOC, Total organic carbon (emissions to water, ground)	(Alyaseri and Zhou 2017)
DOC, Dissolved organic carbon	kg/d	5.92E-01	DOC, Dissolved organic carbon (emissions to water, ground)	(Alyaseri and Zhou 2017)
Sulfate	kg/d	7.07E+00	Sulfate (emissions to water, ground)	(Alyaseri and Zhou 2017)
Nitrate	kg/d	2.31E-01	Nitrate (emissions to water, ground)	(Alyaseri and Zhou 2017)
Phosphate	kg/d	3.58E-01	Phosphate (emissions to water, ground)	(Alyaseri and Zhou 2017)

Element	UdM	Value	Process in Ecoinvent v3.10	Reference
Arsenic, ion	kg/d	1.52E-04	Arsenic ion (emissions to water, ground)	(Alyaseri and Zhou 2017)
Cadmium, ion	kg/d	1.98E-06	Cadmium II (emissions to water, ground)	(Alyaseri and Zhou 2017)
Cobalt	kg/d	9.95E-04	Cobalt II (emissions to water, ground)	(Alyaseri and Zhou 2017)
Chromium VI	kg/d	9.10E-04	Chromium VI (emissions to water, ground)	(Alyaseri and Zhou 2017)
Copper, ion	kg/d	3.19E-02	Copper, ion (emissions to water, ground)	(Alyaseri and Zhou 2017)
Mercury	kg/d	1.03E-05	Mercury II (emissions to water, ground)	(Alyaseri and Zhou 2017)
Manganese	kg/d	3.22E-02	Manganese II (emissions to water, ground)	(Alyaseri and Zhou 2017)
Molybdenum	kg/d	5.55E-04	Molybdenum VI (emissions to water, ground)	(Alyaseri and Zhou 2017)
Nickel, ion	kg/d	3.46E-03	Nickel II (emissions to water, ground)	(Alyaseri and Zhou 2017)
Lead	kg/d	7.80E-04	Lead II (emissions to water, ground)	(Alyaseri and Zhou 2017)
Tin, ion	kg/d	1.42E-03	Tin, ion (emissions to water, ground)	(Alyaseri and Zhou 2017)
Zinc, ion	kg/d	1.67E-03	Zinc II (emissions to water, ground)	(Alyaseri and Zhou 2017)
Silicon	kg/d	3.64E-01	Silicon (emissions to water, ground)	(Alyaseri and Zhou 2017)
Iron, ion	kg/d	8.86E+00	Iron ion (emissions to water, ground)	(Alyaseri and Zhou 2017)
Calcium, ion	kg/d	6.19E+00	Calcium II (emissions to water, ground)	(Alyaseri and Zhou 2017)
Aluminum	kg/d	1.56E+00	Aluminium III (emissions to water, ground)	(Alyaseri and Zhou 2017)
Magnesium	kg/d	7.37E-01	Magnesium (emissions to water, ground)	(Alyaseri and Zhou 2017)

Table 53: LCI of the NF and RO membranes (Bordbar et al. 2022).

Component	Amount for NF module (kg/m ³)	Amount for RO module (kg/m ³)	Process in Ecoinvent v3.10
ABS (Acrylonitrile-butadiene-styrene copolymer)	-	$2,90964 \times 10^{-13}$	acrylonitrile-butadiene-styrene copolymer production (RER)
Polyester	$4,79452 \times 10^{-11}$	$2,0077 \times 10^{-13}$	polyester resin production, unsaturated (RER)
Polysulfone	$1,0274 \times 10^{-11}$	$2,12833 \times 10^{-13}$	polysulfone production, for membrane filtration production (GLO)
DMF (N,N-dimethylformamide)	$4,10959 \times 10^{-11}$	$8,52231 \times 10^{-12}$	N,N-dimethylformamide production, direct synthesis (RER)
MPD (meta-phenylene diamine)	$4,62329 \times 10^{-13}$	$9,00922 \times 10^{-16}$	meta-phenylene diamine
TMC (trimesoyl chloride)	$1,19178 \times 10^{-12}$	$2,69506 \times 10^{-15}$	trimesoyl chloride production, for membrane filtration production (GLO)
Phosphoric acid	$3,20548 \times 10^{-12}$	$6,31159 \times 10^{-14}$	phosphoric acid production, dihydrate process (RER)
Polypropylene (spacers)	$5,13699 \times 10^{-11}$	$4,26565 \times 10^{-13}$	polypropylene production, granulate (RER)
Epoxy resin (glue)	$1,16438 \times 10^{-11}$	$1,17299 \times 10^{-14}$	epoxy resin production, liquid (RER)
PVC (permeate tube)	$1,78082 \times 10^{-11}$	$1,3347 \times 10^{-15}$	polyvinylchloride production, bulk polymerisation (RER)
IPA (isopropanol)	$5,82192 \times 10^{-12}$	$2,10215 \times 10^{-14}$	isopropanol production (RER)